

AUSBILDUNG

Masterarbeiten der PH Zürich

Janina Duojiao Justus

Graded readers in the EFL classroom

A literary and linguistic analysis of Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein, or The Modern Prometheus* and its graded reader versions and a practical implication into the EFL classroom

Abstract

The use of literature in the foreign language classroom to promote linguistic and transversal skills has long been advocated for. This master thesis considers the learning potential of graded readers in the English second language classroom. First, it examines the extent to which graded readers differ from the original on linguistic and literary grounds. The findings suggest that linguistic simplifications occur primarily at the level of sentence structure and difficulty of words. The consequences of linguistic simplifications on the literary meaning of the text were examined in terms of the indirect and direct characterisation of the characters' emotions, and it was found that the characters' emotions are less present in the graded readers in comparison to the original. Based on these findings, a teaching project was developed based on the approach of

task-based language teaching, which aims at recovering the loss of the characters' emotions and promoting the language competences Reading and Dialogic speaking, as well as the transversal competence Empathy. The teaching project suggests that task-based language teaching is particularly well suited for working with literature, as it overlaps with language skill specific methodology as well as suggestions of literature methodology. In addition, task-based language teaching allows sufficient freedom for open-ended assignments for empathy development. With regard to the use of graded readers in the classroom, it is shown that they are particularly suitable for meaning-focused in- and output projects, but that they add little value to accuracy-focused teaching projects.

Keywords

Graded readers, reading, dialogic speaking, empathy, task-based language teaching

Bibliografie

Justus, Janina Duojiao. 2023. *Graded readers in the EFL classroom. A literary and linguistic analysis of Mary Shelley's Frankenstein, or The Modern Prometheus and its graded reader versions and a practical implication into the EFL classroom*. Masterarbeit. Zürich: Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18834171>

Dieses Werk steht unter der Lizenz CC-BY 4.0 International (Creative Commons: Namensnennung) – Copyright PH Zürich.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18834171

2023

Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich
Lagerstrasse 2
CH 8090 Zürich
www.phzh.ch

Graded readers in the EFL classroom

A literary and linguistic analysis of Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein, or The Modern Prometheus* and its graded reader versions and a practical implication into the EFL classroom.

Master thesis at Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich

Department Sekundarstufe I

written by

Justus, Janina Duojiao

submitted to

Dr. Nicole Frey Büchel
Dr. Sabine Binder

Zürich, May 2023

Preface

During my studies at the Pädagogische Hochschule Zurich, I was surprised to find out that literature is not a competence in the subject area English of curriculum 21. This absence was met with great disbelief from me, since I learned English primarily by reading books and could not understand why such a large learning resource was omitted. The curriculum focuses on the four language skills, as well as *Languages in focus* and *Cultures in focus* (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 50 ff.). Teachers have to follow the curriculum, and working on the competences of the curriculum already takes a lot of time, which could result in teachers completely ignoring literature as a teaching resource. However, since I have a great interest in literature, I decided at the beginning of my master thesis that I wanted to investigate how literature can be used to foster the competences of the curriculum. Thus, both the curriculum and the learning potential of literature would be combined. The choice of the specific literary text fell on Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein, or The Modern Prometheus 1818 Text*. The text was chosen for two reasons. On the one hand, I personally like the text, as it deals with many interesting topics, such as responsibility and social acceptance, and on the other hand, I anticipate that the popularity of Victor's and the creature's story will generate intrinsic interest in the pupils.

Thanks to the support of my two supervisors Dr. Nicole Frey Büchel and Dr. Sabine Binder, I have decided to demonstrate the subject-specific and transversal learning potential of literature by means of different tasks. At this point, I would also like to thank my two supervisors, who patiently supported me during the process with the help of personal conversations and mail correspondence.

A special thanks also goes to my friends and family who supported me with many hours of conversations during the entire writing process. A special thanks goes to Sascha Liechti and Eiichirō Oda, who supported me with their patience and ideas during the master thesis and beyond.

Abstract

The use of literature in the foreign language classroom to promote linguistic and transversal skills has long been advocated for. This master thesis considers the learning potential of graded readers in the English second language classroom. First, it examines the extent to which graded readers differ from the original on linguistic and literary grounds. The findings suggest that linguistic simplifications occur primarily at the level of sentence structure and difficulty of words. The consequences of linguistic simplifications on the literary meaning of the text were examined in terms of the indirect and direct characterisation of the characters' emotions, and it was found that the characters' emotions are less present in the graded readers in comparison to the original. Based on these findings, a teaching project was developed based on the approach of task-based language teaching, which aims at recovering the loss of the characters' emotions and promoting the language competences *Reading* and *Dialogic speaking*, as well as the transversal competence *Empathy*. The teaching project suggests that task-based language teaching is particularly well suited for working with literature, as it overlaps with language skill specific methodology as well as suggestions of literature methodology. In addition, task-based language teaching allows sufficient freedom for open-ended assignments for empathy development. With regard to the use of graded readers in the classroom, it is shown that they are particularly suitable for meaning-focused in- and output projects, but that they add little value to accuracy-focused teaching projects.

Key words: graded readers, reading, dialogic speaking, empathy, task-based language teaching

Table of contents

Preface	2
Abstract	3
1 Introduction	7
1.1 Aim and scope	7
1.2 Material	8
2 Theory	11
2.1 Graded readers	11
2.1.1 What are graded readers?	11
2.1.2 How publishers grade	12
2.1.3 Research on graded readers	15
2.2 Literature in the EFL classroom	16
2.2.1 Learning a language through literature	16
2.2.2 Reading	18
2.2.3 Dialogic speaking	25
2.2.4 Developing empathy through literature	28
2.3 Increasing accessibility through teaching methods	31
2.3.1 Motivation	31
2.3.2 Heterogeneity	33
3 Linguistic analysis	35
3.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature	37
3.2 Passage 2: The creature's request	41
3.3 Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth	44
3.4 Summary	47
4 Literary analysis	49
4.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature	50
4.2 Passage 2: The creature's request	56
4.3 Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth	63
4.4 Summary	64
5 Practical transfer into a classroom project	65
5.1 Task-design	66
5.1.1 Task-based language teaching	66
5.1.2 Scaffolding reading	71
5.1.3 Pre-, while- and post-activity	71

5.2	Classroom framework	72
5.3	Worksheets for Passage 1: The birth of the creature	73
5.4	Worksheets for Passage 2: The creature's request	89
5.5	Worksheets for Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth	103
6	Discussion and outlook	112
7	Bibliography	118
8	Appendix	123
8.1	Linguistic analysis Passage 1 OR	123
8.2	Linguistic analysis Passage 1 RR	129
8.3	Linguistic analysis Passage 1 MR	132
8.4	Linguistic analysis Passage 1 SFB	137
8.5	Linguistic analysis Passage 2 OR	138
8.6	Linguistic analysis Passage 2 RR	154
8.7	Linguistic analysis Passage 2 MR	160
8.8	Linguistic analysis Passage 2 SFB	165
8.9	Linguistic analysis Passage 3 OR	166
8.10	Linguistic analysis Passage 3 RR	170
8.11	Linguistic analysis Passage 3 MR	173
8.12	Scaffolding of reading	176
8.13	Passage 1 RR	177
8.14	Passage 1 MR	180
8.15	Passage 2 RR	184
8.16	Passage 2 MR	186
8.17	Passage 3 RR	187
8.18	Passage 3 MR	189

Table of figures

Figure 1: Multi-level model of reading (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 15). _____	19
Figure 2: Competence descriptions of 1) Understanding texts (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 54). _____	25
Figure 3: Competence description of 1) Dialogic speaking (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 58) _____	28
Figure 4: Competence descriptions of 1) Understanding texts, with regard to empathy (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 54) _____	30
Figure 5: Task-as-a-workplan TBLT (Grimm et al. 2015, 70) _____	66
Figure 6: Task types. Adapted from Nunan 2004, 59 - 61. _____	69
Figure 7: Worksheet Passage 1, RR _____	78
Figure 8: Worksheet Passage 1, MR _____	82
Figure 9: Bloom's Taxonomy (adapted from Bloom 1973, 24 ff.) _____	84
Figure 10: Worksheet Passage 2, RR _____	94
Figure 11: Worksheet 2, MR _____	98
Figure 12: Worksheet Passage 3, RR _____	106
Figure 13: Worksheet Passage 3, MR _____	108

List of tables

Table 1: Richmond Readers grading scale _____	11
Table 2: Linguistic comparison "The birth of the creature" _____	38
Table 3: Linguistic comparison "The creature's request" _____	42
Table 4: Linguistic comparison "The death of Elizabeth" _____	45
Table 5: Learning objectives of Passage 1 _____	74
Table 6: Learning objectives of Passage 2 _____	90
Table 7: Learning objectives of Passage 3 _____	104

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim and scope

Curriculum 21 focuses on the competences *Listening, Reading, Speaking, Writing, Languages in focus* and *Cultures in focus* (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 50 ff.). However, even though literature is not explicitly formulated as a competence, this does not mean that it cannot be a beneficial learning resource for the English foreign language (EFL) classroom. Many experts, for example Hesse, describe that literature can be used to acquire different linguistic competences in addition to literary ones (Hesse 2009, 31 ff.). While Hesse strongly concentrates on the acquisition of language skills through literary work, other experts go further and consider literature as an opportunity for holistic learning. Ghosn, for example, describes how literature can also help pupils work on their personal or social skills, e.g., by developing empathy (2002, 176). The holistic learning aspect is particularly interesting, as learning is no longer viewed in isolation based on individual competences, but as an education on the whole person (Grimm et al. 2015, 66).

However, since original texts are often too difficult for learners to understand, other texts which are feasible in terms of their linguistic requirements must be chosen. One way of doing this is to use graded readers. Graded readers are texts that have been adapted both linguistically and in terms of content and are recommended specifically for language learners (Hill 1997, 57). However, linguistic adaptations also change the literary material, with the result that pupils no longer encounter the text with its intended meaning. To investigate the literary consequences of linguistic simplifications and the potential of learning a language holistically through literature, the following research questions have been formulated.

1. How do the linguistic simplifications in graded reader versions of *Mary Shelley's Frankenstein, or the Modern Prometheus 1818 Text* change the literary meaning of the material in comparison to the original text?
2. How can task-based language teaching introduce secondary school pupils to literature and improve their *Reading, Dialogic speaking, and Empathy* skills and help them work out literary meaning that was changed or lost during the simplification process between the original and graded readers?

The master thesis is structured as follows.

In the first part, the theoretical foundation for the second research question will be presented. There, graded readers will be introduced, followed by an introduction to the competences *Reading*, *Dialogic speaking*, and *Empathy* in the context of the EFL classroom. In addition, two different parameters “motivation” and “heterogeneity” will be presented to determine how they can be used in task-designs to facilitate learners’ access to the text. In the second part of the thesis, the text *Frankenstein, or The Modern Prometheus 1818 Text* by Mary Shelley will be compared to three different graded reader versions on the basis of three exemplary scenes with regard to their linguistic simplification. The linguistic analysis allows insight into how the texts differ based on various categories, e.g., sentence structure or difficulty of words. The findings allow for a more customised use of the works for the classroom project. In the third part of the thesis, the consequences of the linguistic analysis for the literary material will be examined. In this context, the first research question will be answered. Those findings, as well as the theory from the first part, will be used in the classroom project which focuses on the second research question. Exemplary tasks will be designed to illustrate how literature can be used to support pupils in acquiring both linguistic and transversal competences. In this context, worksheets and learning goals are presented and commented on the basis of the theory. On this note, I would like to express my gratitude to Macmillan and Richmond Readers for their generous permission to use extracts from their graded readers, which have significantly enhanced the quality and comprehensiveness of my master thesis. Finally, the discussion of the results follows, in which the most important findings will be summarised, and the research questions answered. The part is concluded with an outlook on further ideas that build on the master thesis and extend the findings.

1.2 Material

Mary Shelley’s 19th-century novel *Frankenstein, or the Modern Prometheus 1818 Text* was chosen for several reasons. Firstly, it is a literary classic that has been fascinating people for generations, both in literature and media (Laurence 2018). Its cultural significance not only stems from its compelling story, but also from the underlying topics that carry through the novel. As Laurence puts it: “Its two central tragedies – one of overreaching and the

dangers of 'playing God', the other of parental abandonment and societal rejection – are as relevant today as ever" (Laurence 2018). Secondly, the original uses a lot of different rhetoric devices to allow its readership to engage with the material more thoroughly by allowing them to interpret and assign meaning to the text. Thirdly, since the original is so popular, many different publishing houses have published their graded reader version of the classic. The vast number of different editions one can choose from is especially attractive in regard to working with the material in a heterogeneous class, as the material itself is already adapted to the language proficiency of the respective pupils.

Generally, graded reader versions differ from the original in five categories: publishing houses, the CEFR (Common European Framework) classification, the content, the presentation, and the accompanying tasks.

Publishing houses and CEFR

The different versions used for these analyses are provided by Macmillan Readers (MR), with about 1100 words and A2 CEFR language level, Richmond Readers (RR), with approximately 1200 words and B1 CEFR level, and Starry Forest Books (SFB), which carries an A1 level and contains approximately 70 different headwords. Even though no CEFR classification could be found for the original version (OR), it can still be claimed to score the highest on the CEFR rating scale due to its grammatical, syntactical, and lexical difficulty, thus making it the most challenging text among the four versions¹.

Content

Regarding the story and the plots, there are big differences between the versions. While RR and MR stay close to the original, SFB takes more liberties, such as why Victor creates the creature or how their relationship develops over the course of the novel. However, even though RR and MR resemble OR in most parts, certain elements of the story deviate from the original in all graded readers by either being changed, added, simplified, or omitted.

¹ Whilst this paper works with three different graded reader versions of Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein, Or the Modern Prometheus*, many other graded reader versions can be found, such as:

- Mary Shelley. 2020. *Frankenstein*. London: Penguin Books Ltd.
- Mary Shelley. 2015. *Frankenstein*. London: Pearson Education Limited.
- Mary Shelley. 2018. *Frankenstein*. London: Penguin UK.
- Mary Shelley. 2016. *Frankenstein*. Oxford: Oxford University ELT.
- Mary Shelley. 2008. *Frankenstein*. London: Usborne Publishing Ltd.

For example, in MR's version the entire frame narrative has been omitted. Whereas in the original the story begins and ends with Captain Robert Walton, in MR's version the story begins directly with Victor introducing himself and going to Ingolstadt. The omission of the frame narrative results in many changes in the content of the book. For example, through Robert Walton's letters the question arises of how credible Victor's story really is, highlighting the ambiguity and uncertainty that runs through the novel. Letters are often deeply personal and subjective, thus encouraging the reader to critically engage with the events of the novel and question the motivations of the characters. The endings also differ between OR and MR. While in the original Victor dies in Antarctica without having met the creature in the end, in MR's version Victor and the creature meet before Victor's death and have a conversation, in which Victor comes to realise that he is to blame for the death of the people dearest to him. Overall, RR's version represents the original most authentically among the graded readers, having kept the frame narrative, sticking close to OR's story and similarly structuring plots. SFB clearly differs from OR's version the most. Clearly targeted to a young audience, the book omits most critical moments or significantly tones them down. For example, no character is harmed in the story and even in the end, the story concludes with both protagonists still being alive.

Representation

Unlike OR, all graded reader versions contain illustrations of selected events, sometimes coloured (e.g., SFB), and sometimes black and white (e.g., MR, RR). In every case, the illustrations graphically support the text by either mirroring what is written or adding further information to it. SFB goes as far as telling the majority of the novel through colourful and cartoonish illustrations. It is also noticeable that the illustrations in all graded reader versions feature clothes resembling common male daywear from the early 19th century. In the illustrations Victor and other male characters are frequently pictured wearing a white shirt, a waistcoat, a coat that was cut in at the waist, breeches, buckles or a tie, and pantaloons, in addition to tall boots which usually extend to the knees. All these garments represent typical male daywear for the early 19th century (Tortora 2010, 319; Byrde 1992, 91 – 93; le Bourhis 1989, 112). Furthermore, the graded readers use a considerably larger text font and bigger line spacing than the OR by Oxford World's Classics, which supports younger or weaker readers by providing visual relief (Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 43).

Tasks

Regarding the structure of the graded readers, it is evident that some were designed for in-classroom use. Two of the three graded reader versions (e.g., MR, RR) are accompanied by assignments, questions, and vocabulary, which indicates that the material was designed with a clear didactic function in mind. Additionally, MR and RR feature different CDs with additional material that can be used for in-classroom activities.

2 Theory

2.1 Graded readers

2.1.1 What are graded readers?

Graded readers are simplified versions of extended texts, in most cases fiction, which are designed for English learners (Hill 1997, 57). These simplified versions use limited lexis, determined by frequency and usefulness, and syntax, determined by simplicity (Hill 2008, 185). However, graded readers are not limited to simplified versions of an original text but may also be texts specifically written for second language acquisition, such as *Mystery of Allegra*² and *The Boy-King Tutankhamun*³ (Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 55). Based on the lexical and grammatical simplification publishing houses (e.g., MR and RR) typically categorise the adapted versions into distinct levels, based on their total number of headwords and CEFR and ESOL difficulty level. The classification system of RR, for example, has five levels, as shown in table 1.

Level	Headwords	CEFR	ESOL
Level 1	500 – 600	A1	-
Level 2	600 – 800	A2	KET
Level 3	1000 – 1200	B1	PET
Level 4	1400 – 1800	B2	FCE
Level 5	2200 – 2600	C1	CAE

Table 1: Richmond Readers grading scale

² Foreman, Peter. 2016. *The Mystery of Allegra*. Oxford: Oxford University ELT.

³ Lauder, Scott Angus and Walter McGregor. 2016. *The boy-King Tutankhamun*. Oxford: Oxford University ELT.

The genres among titles currently in print range from thriller/crime, to romance and anything in between. The vast number of genres and titles allow for a great teaching resource, as teachers can choose material according to the pupils' linguistic needs and topical preferences.

Graded readers do not only differ in terms of lexis and syntax, but also in terms of content, activities, reading support and graphic representation. The linguistic and literary differences will be discussed in chapter "3 Linguistic analysis" and "4 Literary analysis" using the example of Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein, or the Modern Prometheus 1818 Text*. Many graded readers feature a set of post-reading activities, with some publishers even featuring pre- and while-reading activities, such as MR. The variety of these exercises varies greatly between the different graded readers. Some publishers (e.g., MR) offer a vast variety of activities, such as multiple-choice comprehension questions, vocabulary activities, characterisations, as well as grammar and writing activities, whilst others, such as RR, focus more on comprehension questions and only feature a few grammar activities. In terms of reading support, most publishers do little to help learners understand the text, apart from the linguistic simplification (Hill 2008, 192). If editors do provide support, they "[...] most do it in an unhelpful way" (Hill 2008, 192). Even if support is given, Hill argues that it is unnecessary, tedious or adds confusion and thus does not help the readers engage with the material (Hill 2008, 192 – 194).

With regards to the visual representation of graded readers, Hill criticises that "[...] the font used in graded readers is too small. It is astonishing that publishers should be so insensitive to the needs of learners who are unfamiliar with roman letters and unaccustomed to reading. In addition, the type is often too grey, the paper off-white, the text or background coloured, the margins narrow, and the lines long and close together" (Hill 2008, 190). The graded readers further differ in terms of illustrations. While some publishers offer plenty of colourful visual support, such as SFB, other publishing houses, such as MR, rely much less on illustrations as reading support, as a result of which their graded readers are quite text heavy.

2.1.2 How publishers grade

In chapter "2.1.1 What are graded readers?" it has been established that editors grade

original texts by either limiting lexis or grammar structures. However, the question remains how exactly they put this simplification into practice.

Lexis

Graded readers are categorised by their lexical difficulty. However, even though many publishers use lexis for their classification, there is a difference with regard to the number of headwords that are considered appropriate at each level (Claridge 2012, 12). For example, while Penguin Readers considers 600 words to be an appropriate number of headwords for the level “Elementary”, MR almost doubles the number of headwords to 1100 (Penguin n.d., 1; Macmillan 2014, i). Claridge elaborates that it is impossible for publishers to know, which words readers already know, as it depends on the readers interests and experiences (Claridge 2012, 12). Also, certain texts and genres may require words that are outside the expected lexicon of readers, but publishers have come to accept the need to maintain flexibility in how many and which words are used for a particular language level and novel (Claridge 2012, 112). Not only the number of headwords plays a role in classifying texts, but also the type and difficulty of words the reader encounters. Lucas explains that the simplification of words takes place on three levels: 1) replacement, 2) omission and 3) addition (1991, 243). In the first case words that are considered too advanced for a level are substituted for another, easier word. For example, the word “rebel” can be substituted by the word “boy” (Blum and Leventson 1987, 406). Whilst “boy” is certainly easier to understand, “rebel” carries more meaning, as it reveals the boy’s rebellious nature, which is lost in the process of replacement. Additionally, Dirks argues that the attempted simplification may not always result in an easier text. English learners can profit from their native language and their interlingual competences and understand words, which would be classified as “too difficult” in the publishers’ grading scale. However, if these words are replaced by their anglicised counterparts, it may increase the text’s difficulty for certain audiences (Dirks 2004, 15). In the second level 2) omission words are simply omitted and in the last level 3) addition difficult words get additional information, for example in the form of paraphrasing (Blum and Leventson 1978, 412).

Grammar

In terms of grammar, only Penguin Readers publicly communicates, how they adapt the

original texts grammatically and syntactically. For each level Penguin Readers strongly regulates the frequency of different parts of speech, the usage of grammar structures, as well as the type of sentence structures that are accepted to use. For example, in level 1 two clauses can be joined with “because”, whereas in level 3 the editors may use main clauses, subordinate clauses, zero and first conditional, relative clauses, participle clauses, among others, thus allowing the readers to encounter many different grammatical and syntactical structures (Penguin, n.d.).

Hill goes on to describe that simpler editions of texts generally rely on simpler sentence structures (2008, 196). For example, he describes that dialogue and simple sentences are more commonly used in simpler graded reader versions (Hill 2008, 196). Dirks supports the idea, that the syntactical difficulty increases with language level. She argues that the more difficult graded readers increase the relative number of main and subordinate clauses to the number of sentences, which in turn increases the complexity of the sentences (Dirks 2004, 39). In addition, Dirks also reveals, that the average sentence length increases with language level (Dirks 2004, 36). The shorter sentences for easier versions could be a result of editors attempting to convey information as compactly as possible.

Content

As established in the previous two grading scales, the changes in lexis and grammar already change the content, as shown in the example of “rebel” and “boy”. However, in some cases editors take this a step further and actively change parts of the story and plots. Out of three publishing houses (RR, MR, and SFB) only MR publicly discusses how they change the content of a text to ease understanding. They state that they limit plots and descriptions to an absolute minimum, as well as omitting cultural background information where deemed unnecessary (Macmillan 2014, 2). Furthermore, MR does not include sensitive topics such as strongly religious or culturally controversial topics (Claridge 2012, 111). In addition, MR adapts the storyline of its graded readers to follow a linear narrative, thus avoiding any frame or embedded narratives (Claridge 2012, 111). This can be seen in MR’s version of *Frankenstein*, where the entire frame narrative is omitted. However, omitting, abridging, or replacing narratives, topics or entire plots has a huge influence on the story as a whole and thus can significantly change the literary meaning of a text.

2.1.3 Research on graded readers

Research on graded readers in the EFL classroom has produced various results, some highlighting their potential for language acquisition, and others pointing out disadvantages and limited learning possibilities. The majority of the research however focuses on extensive reading programs rather than instructed teaching approaches and thus aligns little with the classroom project for this master thesis. However, the most important potentials and challenges will be highlighted nevertheless since the findings help to narrow down learning objectives and the framework conditions of the teaching project in chapter “5 Practical transfer into a teaching project”.

Numerous studies attribute positive learning effects to graded readers in fluency (cf. Hill 1997, 58; Nation and Ming-Tzu 1999, 356; Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 62). Nation and Deweerdt attribute this rise in fluency to the simpler lexis. Learners do not encounter too many too difficult words and can thus practice their fluency, as long as they are reading texts within their language proficiency level (2001, 62). Furthermore, Claridge also attributes an increase in reading motivation to graded readers, as language learners can read within their proficiency level and are thus not discouraged by words and grammatical structures that are too difficult for them to understand (Claridge 2012, 112). Nation and Deweerdt also attribute a high learning potential to graded readers when it comes to meaning-focused input approaches (2001, 49 ff.). Meaning-focused input involves incidental learning and focuses on the message of a text, thus forming a comprehension-based approach (Nation and Deewerdt 2001, 57). For the pupils to be able to focus on the meaning of the text, the texts needs to be linguistically manageable to them. Graded readers are particularly well suited to this teaching approach because linguistic difficulties, e.g., grammar and lexis, are eliminated in the simplification process, allowing learners to focus on the text and its message, rather than being held up by lexical and grammatical difficulties. While graded readers may be considered a valuable resource for fluency training, motivation, and meaning-focused approaches, learning the target language with graded readers is much more difficult. A study conducted by Nation and Ming-Tzu revealed that in order for pupils to progress in the target language solely through extensively reading graded readers, they must read about one book per week and five per level (1999, 375). Yano et al. further criticise graded readers for lowering the learners' output, if the graded reader is

below the learners' language proficiency (1994, 191), and not aiding in comprehension as the linguistic simplification may remove key words or passages, as well as preventing learners from engaging with challenging material (1994, 214). However, Nation and Deweerdt argue, that there are plenty of high-quality simplified texts, which do assist readers in comprehension, thus nullifying part of the criticism directed towards graded readers (2001, 56 – 57). Lastly, graded readers are also repeatedly criticised for not being authentic (cf. Hill 1997, 57). 'Authentic' in this case means that an 'authentic' text is produced with native speakers in mind and offers 'real' language input (Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 56). However, the question that arises is, whether the argument of authenticity is really valid. Especially with regards to meaning-focused approaches pupils need to focus on the message of the text, rather than on the 100% authentic language, thus the criticism can be voided in a meaning-focused approach (Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 56 – 57).

In conclusion, graded readers are great for increasing learners' reading motivation but lack in benefits for language acquisition. Thus, the classroom project in chapter "5 Practical transfer into a teaching project" will focus more on meaning-focused in- and output rather than practicing specific language forms.

2.2 Literature in the EFL classroom

Working with graded readers in the EFL classroom is about learning with and about literature (cf. Hill 1997, 57; Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 55). In this chapter, a closer look at language acquisition through literature will be taken. In the first sub-chapter, different linguistic and non-linguistic skills which can be promoted through the engagement with literature are presented, thus highlighting the holistic possibilities of language acquisition through literature (cf. Ghosn 2002, 176). After the brief overview of the potential of language acquisition through literature, the different competences of the second research question *Reading, Dialogic speaking, and Empathy* will be discussed in detail.

2.2.1 Learning a language through literature

With the focus of second language acquisition lying on teaching the four basic language skills, vocabulary and grammar, literature has often been considered of secondary importance in the EFL classroom (Nünning and Surkamp 2006, 12). However, learning a

language through literature has its origin in early childhood. Parents read age-appropriate books to and with their children and use this to both entertain and educate them (Grimm et al. 2015, 175). Thus, language learning with the help of literature is not an invention of scholars, but already occupies a place in our first socialisation. However, when it comes to using literature as a learning resource for in-class activities, things get a little more complicated. Firstly, by looking at curriculum 21, one quickly realises that it does not include “literature” as a competence within the subject area English (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 50 ff.). Instead, it focuses on the competences *Speaking, Reading, Writing, Listening, Languages in focus* (e.g., grammar and vocabulary) and *Cultures in focus*. This raises the question, why teachers should include literature in their teaching, if it is not recommended by the curriculum.

Literature is a great learning tool, as it offers learners a more realistic and natural example of language in comparison to textbooks (Richards and Schmidt 2002, 42). However, as already established in chapter “2.1.3 Research on graded readers”, this is not always the case with graded readers as they are often abbreviated and edited versions of an original text. While Nünning and Surkamp strongly advise teachers not to opt for graded readers because they are unauthentic (2006, 45), others are in favour of graded readers as they allow pupils to engage with material within their language proficiency (Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 57). However, Long states, that any fictional literature allows readers to experience real life events fictionally and thus involve pupils in real and authentic communicative activities, such as prediction and debating topics on or around a text (1986, 58). Thus, literature, whether it is abbreviated or original, offers readers to engage in authentic scenarios and in some cases language, rather than the fabricated texts in textbooks.

Furthermore, literature allows pupils to engage with countless different cultures and raises their awareness, which ideally leads to the pupils valuing, respecting, and tolerating other ways of life (Okyar 2021, 332 – 333). This idea is supported by Nünning and Surkamp, who argue, that literature allows readers to get an insight into other times, cultures, and people (2006, 33). Additionally, literature does not only allow pupils to engage with different worlds and cultures, but it also contributes to their personal development. Ghosn argues that good literature has the potential power “to transform, to change attitudes, and to help eradicate prejudice while fostering empathy, tolerance, and an awareness for global problems” (2002, 176). Grimm et al. further argue that literature allows readers to engage with

real-life problems in a fictional setting and learn how to deal with them, thus offering them a safe space to explore (2015, 175). Thus, readers can work on their personal and social competences through their engagement with literary material. Literature further allows pupils to improve more challenging cognitive skills, such as critical thinking and creativity (Naji et al. 2019, 7). This can be achieved through challenging tasks that relate to the literary material (Okyar 2021, 333). Potential activities could be to compare conflicts, analyse characters or confront pupils with questions without pre-determined answers that require them to engage with the material more thoroughly (Okyar 2021, 333).

Lastly, reading literature, accompanied by matching classroom activities, helps improve basic language skills, such as reading, speaking, writing, and listening (Okyar 2021, 334). However, in order to promote these skills through literature, the texts need to be chosen carefully. Not every book is suitable for classroom activities. Grimm et al. compiled a list of requirements for selecting a text for in-classroom use. According to them, texts should be manageable in terms of language level and topics, interesting and engaging, offer insight into other cultures, comparable to learners' lives and cultures, and motivate active and creative work (2015, 190).

If one compares the different competences that can be promoted with literature, it is striking that large parts of the curriculum 21 can be covered with it. Pupils can work on the language competences *Speaking, Reading, Writing, Listening*, as well as *Languages in focus* and *Cultures in focus*. It further allows pupils to engage with themselves and the lives and cultures of other people, which in turn allows pupils to work on their transversal competences. Language teaching with literature thus enables holistic learning. The question now is how literature can be used to promote these skills in concrete ways. For this purpose, the following sub-chapters discuss how the competences *Reading, Dialogic speaking* and *Empathy* can be fostered with the help of literature.

2.2.2 Reading

As established in chapters “2.1.3 Research on graded readers” and “2.2 Literature in the EFL classroom” a lucrative way to teaching and learning with literature is a focus on meaning and text comprehension. In order for pupils to be able to properly understand and reflect

on the message of the text, they first need to be able to read and comprehend the material. The following sub-chapter takes a look into the definition of reading, what challenges learners face in the EFL classroom, how engaging with literature can improve reading skills and is lastly linked to curriculum 21.

What is reading?

Reading can be divided into two categories: The mere reading and decoding of the text, and the active processing of what is read (Alyousef 2006, 66 – 67). Thus, in order to understand a text correctly, the content must not only be understood semantically and syntactically, but also requires the reader to actively engage with the statements of the text in order to understand it. The latter is further defined more precisely as reading being an "activity involving constant guesses that are later rejected or confirmed" (Paran 1996, 25). Thus, it becomes clear that reading is a multi-layered process, which consists of lexical, grammatical, syntactic, and contextual knowledge. Rosebrock and Nix have summarised the multi-layered process of reading in the multi-level model of reading (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Multi-level model of reading (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 15).

From the model it can be deduced that reading is more than just decoding words and

putting information together in a meaningful way. Rather, reading consists of both linguistic and text-linguistic knowledge (process level), as well as the subjective processing of what is read (subject level) and the social relevance of what is read (social level) (Alyousef 2006, 24; Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 15). Therefore, it is clear that reading is both a linguistic and a personal task.

The process level in the multi-level model of reading concerns the linguistic competences required for readers to understand a text. Readers need to decode words correctly, have adequate fluency, and have sufficient text linguistic knowledge to recognise superstructures (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 17; Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 37). For the process level to be successful, readers need both bottom-up strategies, where readers focus on the individual words and information, and top-down strategies, where prior knowledge helps pupils to understand information, anticipate actions and reject expectations (Alyousef 2006, 66 – 67). For a successful comprehension of the text, the individual processes (e.g., bottom-up and top-down) of the process level must run automatically (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 18). If this is not the case, fluency, for example, can suffer, which prevents the formation of global coherence (Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 37). Grimm et al. further describe visual skills, the ability to perceive a written text, as a necessary process for reading (2015, 123).

The subject level involves both personal prerequisites that readers bring with them, such as motivation, and the subjective interpretation of the text. Reading is not only a cognitive task, but also requires a personal and affective engagement of the reader (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 21). Due to the personal engagement, a text demands a constant creation of (personal) meaning, which in turn increases the personal relevance of the text (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 21).

The multi-level model of reading is completed by the social level. The engagement with literary material allows readers to subsequently discuss it in their social environment and to participate in literary life (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 23). Not only is the text processed more deeply through the subsequent communication of what has been read, but the text also takes on a different meaning in the reader's personal life as it becomes part of their social life. (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 23 - 26).

Now that it has been shown which sub-processes are included in reading, the question arises as to what distinguishes a good reader from an inexperienced reader. Good readers

use reading strategies that inexperienced readers do not. However, these can, and should, be fostered by teachers. The list of strategies varies from one researcher to the other. However, the following list compiled by Amin includes the most frequently mentioned strategies.

- Predicting (anticipating actions and events)
 - Visualising (creating and storing a mental image of the text)
 - Making connections (making connections of events or figures within the text or the readers themselves)
 - Summarising (distinguishing core ideas from secondary information)
 - Questioning (asking questions to the texts and answering them while reading)
 - Inferring (using one's own knowledge and the text to read between the lines)
- (Amin 2019, 37)

The different strategies can be assigned to the different levels of the multi-level model of reading by Rosebrock and Nix (see figure 1). All strategies can be assigned to the process level, although some strategies can also be assigned to other levels in addition to the process level. For example, *Inferring* can also be assigned to the subject level, as the readers need to use their prior knowledge to identify inexplicit meaning and interpret it accordingly. Both the multi-level model of reading and the six strategies of good readers indicate that reading is an active construction of meaning. For example, Rosebrock and Nix's model shows that the linguistic prerequisites for reading only make up a small part of the entire reading process, whilst the majority of it consists of decoding messages, creating coherence, recognising connections, and interpreting and reflecting on the text. This, however, does not mean that the linguistic requirements are irrelevant. On the contrary, they form the basis for comprehension and without linguistic competences, comprehension and meaning construction are impossible (Grimm et al. 2015, 123). Amin also shows that a good reader differs from an inexperienced one in that they constantly engage with the material in order to construct meaning, for example through *Questioning*. In summary, reading must be viewed as a meaningful interaction between the reader and the text instead of a passive consumption of the material.

The focus on meaning overlaps with the theory presented in chapters "2.1.3 Research on graded readers" which states that literature is particularly well suited for teaching when the

learning objectives focus on understanding and interpreting the text as a whole rather than learning language forms.

Different kinds of reading

When it comes to reading, there are different types of reading, each of which serves a different purpose. Most commonly there are three kinds of reading.

Reading for gist

This type of reading focuses on understanding the main message of the literary material (Grimm et al. 2015, 122). The text is only briefly scanned, with the aim of understanding the text as a whole rather than subtleties (Neugebauer und Nodari 2012, 49).

Scanning

The goal of this reading strategy is to extract specific information from the text (Grimm et al. 2015, 122). For this purpose, the text is usually also only superficially scanned, but the readers look for keywords and -information (Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 49).

Reading for detailed understanding

The aim of this strategy is to understand the text, or the text passage, very precisely. In this strategy, every word, every implication, and every detail must be precisely understood by the reader. This method is often used to understand core passages very precisely (Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 49).

Challenges for reading in the EFL classroom

In the EFL classroom learners face many difficulties. First of all, the process level in the multi-level model of reading creates challenges (see figure 1). Grimm et al. argue that learners need to pass a certain threshold of language proficiency to be able to read and understand a text in a foreign language, called the Linguistic Threshold (2015, 123). This Linguistic Threshold refers to both the lexical and grammatical knowledge of the learners. However, the increased linguistic difficulty of texts in a foreign language not only confronts language learners with lexical and syntactical challenges, but also negatively affects other components of reading. For example, new, unfamiliar words are challenging in themselves,

but they also interfere with other processes, including fluency (Alyousef 2006, 64; Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 37). If learners encounter too many unfamiliar words or grammatical structures, they can no longer read fast enough to have fluency, which in turn prevents them from accessing global coherence, and thus reading comprehension. Thus, lexical and grammatical difficulty is critical to whether or not a text is understood. Without the necessary proficiency, language learners cannot engage with a literary text, which voids any didactic potential. Consequently, teachers must carefully select texts at an appropriate language level for the learners. However, the problems regarding the process level go further. In a foreign language, it is always possible that the first language will interfere with reading. This can lead to both a positive transfer, where pupils understand words that are considered too difficult by the CEFR, or a negative transfer, where they incorrectly transfer similar-sounding words from their first language into the foreign language (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 41 - 47). An example of this is when German native speakers use the word “bekommen” to translate the word “become”.

Another challenge, although this is not exclusively a problem of foreign language teaching, is the learner's self-concept as a reader. This problem can be assigned to the subject level of the multi-level model of reading. The self-concept about oneself as a reader and one's relationship to literature has an enormous impact on how learners approach a text (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 22). If one's self-concept is that they do not like to read, they will approach literature hesitantly regardless of the text, its content and linguistic difficulty (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 22). The problem is further negatively reinforced by their self-concept as a language learner, which could lead to even more rejection (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 49).

Last but not least, reading, especially in the foreign language classroom also has a motivational problem. Reading, especially with the additional linguistic difficulties of a foreign language, is considered stressful and boring, which is why many readers already approach a text with a negative attitude (Grimm et al. 2015, 122).

How to improve reading skills through literature

As demonstrated above, learners encounter many challenges when reading in the EFL classroom. In order to balance the challenges and enable pupils to work on their reading skills, several suggestions can be found. To address the challenges on the process level,

the approach of pre-, while-, and post-reading is recommended (Grimm et al. 2015, 123). In the pre-phase of reading, readers prepare for the text. Activities for this phase consist of, for example, learning vocabulary or making assumptions about the text based on clues (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 133). This could assist the pupils in overcoming the Linguistic Threshold or allow them to view superstructures. In the while-phase, learners engage with the text. Possible activities consist of learners applying different reading strategies, such as *Predicting* or *Inferring* (cf. Amin 2019, 37; Grimm et al. 2015, 123). In the post-phase, the readers use their knowledge of the material to answer questions or expand their understanding of the text, for example by interpreting it (Grimm et al. 2015, 123). To address the motivational issues on the subject level, a book should be chosen that is interesting to the learners, appealing to them, and appropriate to their language level (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 132; Grimm et al. 2015, 190). This should solve motivational problems and therefore enable a better access to the text.

Another interesting approach is the one of collaborative reading, which is introduced by Grabe and Stoller (2011, 157). As already seen in the multi-level model of reading, reading is a communicative task and is ideal for communicative activities with others (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 15). Learners can therefore assist each other to process and understand a text more thoroughly. According to Grabe and Stoller, communication does not have to be limited to the post-reading phase, as suggested by Rosebrock and Nix. Pupils can also work together in the pre- and while-phase of reading, e.g., by skimming and discussing texts together (while-reading) or by looking at pictures and discussing their assumptions on the content (pre-reading) (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 157).

One way to implement the three phases, as well as the collaborative reading approach, is through the *Scaffolding of reading*. This approach was specifically designed to help learners understand and contextualise information from a text (Neugebauer 2008, 2). Readers are supported with concrete work assignments instead of questions and are supported during all three phases by offering clear instructions on how to read and engage with a text (Neugebauer 2008, 2-3).

Reading in curriculum 21

Reading is one of the competences of the subject area English in curriculum 21. The competence is further divided into the following sub-competences.

A) Reading and understanding texts

B) Strategies

C) Language mediation

(Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 54 – 57).

The master thesis focuses on the sub-competence A) Reading and understanding texts. The sub-competence can be further divided into 1) Understanding texts, and 2) Describing the aesthetic impact of texts, for which the former will be focused on. The relevant competence descriptions for the target level can be found in figure 2.

3	d	» können in klar strukturierten Texten die Hauptinformationen oder Einzelinformationen verstehen, wenn das Thema vertraut ist (z.B. Geschichte, Reportage, Vorschrift).	
	A 2.2 GK 1.+2.FS	» können einfache kurze Anleitungen befolgen, wenn die Schritte illustriert sind (z.B. Experiment, Spiel, Rezept).	
		» können einfache persönliche Texte über vertraute Dinge verstehen (z.B. Brief, Blog).	
○	e	» können unterschiedlich lange Texte zu Themen, die sie interessieren, verstehen (z.B. vereinfachter literarischer Text, Buchbesprechung, Reportage).	
	B 1.1	» können klar strukturierten Hinweisen wichtige Informationen entnehmen (z.B. Bedienungsanleitung).	
		» können in unkomplizierten Texten zu Themen, die sie interessieren oder zu denen sie Vorkenntnisse haben, die Hauptaussagen verstehen (z.B. Reisebericht, Briefaustausch).	
	f	» können Texte im Wesentlichen verstehen, wenn das Thema vertraut ist (z.B. Auszug aus einem Jugendbuch, Songtext, unkomplizierter Sachtext).	
	B 1.2	» können klaren schriftlichen Anleitungen folgen (z.B. Lernprojekt, Gerätebedienung, Spiel).	
		» können in einfachen argumentativen Texten die zugrunde liegende Meinung oder Haltung erkennen (z.B. Blogeintrag).	

Figure 2: Competence descriptions of 1) Understanding texts (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 54).

2.2.3 Dialogic speaking

What is speaking?

Spoken language is both transactional and interactive. In the former case language is used to convey information, whereas in the latter it is used to maintain social relationships (Shumin 2002, 208). However, before a speaker can formulate a statement to fulfil any of these purposes, they first need to be skilled in different so-called features. Bygate defines these as phonological features, lexico-grammatical features, and discourse features (Bygate 2009, 415). Phonological features focus on the (correct) pronunciation of individual sounds and words. In any case, foreign language learners need to become familiar with a new phonetic system and be able to use it correctly. However, learning the correct

pronunciation of sounds is not equally easy for everyone. Learners whose first language differs significantly from the foreign language in terms of phonetics have particular difficulty acquiring the phonological feature (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 41 - 47). The second feature lexico-grammatical is a prerequisite that is not exclusive to speaking proficiency but for language in general. Language learners need to have the necessary lexical and grammatical repertoire for their communicative tasks in order to achieve a communicative goal. Lastly, language users also need discourse features that enable them to shape interactions with each other (Bygate 2009, 415). Grimm et al. adds that speaking consists of additional features, because speaking is not only a verbal act, but also consists of non-verbal cues and cultural nuances (2015, 117). Thus, Bygate's list of features would have to be extended by additional two features.

For speech to achieve the desired effect, however, speakers need more than just reasonable proficiency in these features. Speaking, both interactive and transactional, is always a process which consists of four phases: conceptualising (planning, what they want to say), formulating (using lexical and grammatical knowledge to formulate the message), articulating (externalising the inner speech) and repair (monitoring one's speech) (Bygate 2011, 419 - 420). Thus, it becomes evident that speaking needs to be prepared, uttered, and evaluated. These four phases can therefore be reformulated as pre- (conceptualising, formulating), while- (articulating, repair) and post-speaking (repair) phases. The repair phase can be assigned to multiple phases, as it can happen simultaneously to the speaking (e.g., monitor whether what they say achieves the communicative goal and adjusting the statement during the speaking), or follow (e.g., learn new structures to improve their speaking).

Challenges for dialogic speaking in the EFL classroom

The problems with speaking in the EFL classroom relate to the features formulated by Bygate (2011, 415). Grimm et al. state that the phonological and the lexico-grammatical features are difficult for many language learners (2015, 131). The difficulties arise from both a negative inference of the first language and a lack of foreign language proficiency (Grimm et al. 2015, 131). As already described by Grabe and Stoller, the first language can negatively influence foreign language acquisition by transferring known structures of the first language into the foreign language (2011, 41 - 47). This can negatively influence

both the phonetic feature and the lexico-grammatical feature. In addition to the possible negative inference of the first language, learners also face additional linguistic challenges from the foreign language itself. Just as a lack of vocabulary and grammatical structures can interfere with reading, it can also make speaking more difficult for learners, e.g., in the formulating phase in which they have to formulate their thoughts into coherent sentences (Grimm et al. 2015, 123). Another difficulty addressed by Grimm et al. is learner anxiety (2015, 213). If the environment is not welcoming to learners, for example, through a lack of acceptance for errors, acquisition of speaking skills can be hindered.

How to foster dialogic speaking skills through literature

Literature is an excellent tool for developing dialogic speaking competence. On the one hand, with regard to the multi-level model of reading (see figure 1), speaking about a text takes up a large part of the reading process (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 23 - 26). Talking about what has been read is thus an integral part of teaching literature, which is why it is only natural to work on the learners' speaking competences. Grimm et al. further describe that extensive exposure to interesting language material increases the possibility for meaningful communicative opportunities (2015, 130). Thus, if the literary material pupils work with is chosen to be meaningful and interesting, communicative opportunities increase. Grimm et al. go on to describe that in interactive activities, where Grimm et al. only refer to communicative activities between several people and does not refer to Shumin's interactive purpose of reading, the focus should be on the meaning of the statement and not on accuracy (Grimm et al. 2015, 130 - 131). As described earlier, literature is better suited for comprehension and meaning-focused in- and output approaches than for language- or accuracy-focused approaches. Thus, there is a synergy between the goals of teaching literature and speaking, as both focus on the meaning of the statement rather than on linguistic accuracy.

In general, Grimm et al. recommend paying attention to the following points in communicative tasks: 1) intrinsic motivation, 2) fluency before accuracy, 3) language support given by the teacher or the task, 4) encourage learners to avoid their first language, 5) create opportunities to celebrate success, 6) offer relevant and relatable topics (2015, 132).

Dialogic speaking in curriculum 21

Dialogic speaking is one of the competences of the subject area English in curriculum 21.

The relevant competence descriptions for the target level can be found in figure 3.

3	d A 2.2 GK 1.+2.FS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » können einfache Aussagen zu vertrauten Themen machen und darauf reagieren (z.B. etwas erklären, Verständnis prüfen). » können zu alltäglichen Aktivitäten Fragen stellen und beantworten (z.B. Freizeit, Reisen, Unterricht). » können ausdrücken, ob sie einverstanden sind oder lieber etwas anderes möchten (z.B. Vorschlag, Abmachung). » können vertraute Personen um einen Gefallen bitten und auf Bitten reagieren (z.B. etwas ausleihen, Wunsch äussern). 	
	e B 1.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » können zu vertrauten Themen auf einfache Art Informationen austauschen (z.B. Mode, Film, Musik). » können ihre Meinung sagen und nach der Meinung von anderen fragen (z.B. Diskussion, Interview, Gruppenarbeit). » können einfache Telefongespräche führen. 	
	f B 1.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> » können mit Gleichaltrigen längere Gespräche über gemeinsame Interessen führen, falls diese sich um gegenseitiges Verstehen bemühen (z.B. Ferienbekanntschaft, Austauschpartner/in). » können spontan Fragen stellen zu besonderen Ereignissen oder Erlebnissen (z.B. Ferien, Fest, Unfall). » können in Diskussionen oder bei Entscheidungen die eigene Haltung argumentativ einbringen, Vorschläge machen und die Meinungen anderer kurz kommentieren (z.B. Projektarbeit, Wahl der Lektüre, Streitgespräch) » können sich in alltäglichen Situationen beschweren (z.B. defektes Produkt). 	

Figure 3: Competence description of 1) Dialogic speaking (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 58)

2.2.4 Developing empathy through literature

What is empathy?

In everyday use, empathy is described as the ability to put oneself in the shoes of other people and to match one's reaction accordingly (Döring 2013, 297). The ability to feel empathy can be traced back to genetic predispositions as well as to socialisation processes and learning experiences (Döring 2013, 297). When speaking of empathy, two types can be distinguished:

- Cognitive empathy: The ability to mentally put oneself in other people's shoes and understand their thoughts, feelings, goals, etc. (Döring 2013, 297).
- Affective empathy: The ability to empathise with the emotional inner life of another. However, this is not just a 1:1 transfer of feelings. Rather, the relationship between the people involved is important. Döring describes that if a person is unlikable, one can feel a kind of counter-empathy (e.g., Schadenfreude) (2013, 297).

What does it take for people to feel empathy?

As described above, empathy can be learnt to some extent (cf. Döring 2013, 297). One way to learn empathy is by engaging with fictional characters from media (e.g., TV or books), although it must be mentioned that empathy, especially affective, with fictional characters is significantly lower than with real people (Döring 2013, 289).

For people to develop empathy the relationship with the characters is of foremost importance. If one likes a character, they are more likely to synchronise their own emotions with them (Döring 2013, 297). Thus, the characters in a story are central to empathy development. Another aspect is involvement. The more involved readers are in the story or characters, the more likely they are to feel empathy (Döring 2013, 299). Jamieson further advocates for the benefit of empathy learning through literature. She reveals that literature is an integral part of empathy learning because the readers can remain themselves while living the lives of others (2013, 229 - 230). Therefore, in a safe environment and with negligible risks, readers can imaginatively place themselves in other situations and synchronise their feelings and thoughts with the characters. Grimm et al. support this statement. They argue that readers can deal with their own problems through literature by engaging with the fictional characters' lives, which in turn helps learners in their real lives (Grimm et al. 2015, 175). In summary, it can be said that the characters play a vital role in empathy learning. How strong the experienced empathy is depends on how much the readers identify with the characters and the characters' subjective likeability.

Challenges for empathy acquisition in the EFL classroom

The challenges for empathy learning with literature in the EFL classroom are composed of the challenges of the previous chapters "2.2.2 Reading" and "2.2.3 Dialogic speaking". In order for readers to engage with the story and the characters, they need the necessary linguistic skills (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 123). If the Linguistic Threshold is too large, the readers cannot understand the material at all, which makes it difficult to experience empathy. Another difficulty, which was also addressed in chapter "2.2.2 Reading", is the self-concept as a (foreign language) reader. If one has a poor self-concept as a reader and a negative attitude towards the target language, the reader's involvement is massively disrupted, which makes perspective-taking with the characters exceedingly difficult (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 22; Grabe and Stoller 2011, 49).

How to foster empathy skills through literature

There are several ways to promote empathy through literature. First of all, it must be ensured that the texts are at a language level that the pupils can master so that they can access the text at all (Grimm et al. 2015, 123).

The choice of book also plays a key role in promoting empathy through literature. The characters, the plots and the story as a whole must be exciting, likeable, and relatable (Jamieson 2015, 236 - 238). This strengthens both the identification with the characters as well as perspective-taking, which both increases the readers empathy (Döring 2013, 305 - 308; Jamieson 2015, 236 - 238). Jamieson continues that empathy promotion must be accompanied with appropriate tasks (2015, 234 - 235). She suggests that pupils should always be encouraged to actively engage with the characters and analyse them (Jamieson 2015, 234 - 235). According to her, this can be achieved, for example, with close-reading procedures or assignments with clear empathy-related goals (Jamieson 2013, 234).

Empathy in curriculum 21

Empathy is listed as a learning objective in the subject areas English and Transversal competences of curriculum 21. In the subject area English, in the competence *Reading*, empathy can be found under A) Reading and understanding texts (see figure 4).

3	b	» können in einfache, mit Bildern illustrierte kurze Texte eintauchen (z.B. Comic, illustrierte Geschichte).	
	c	» können in Texten ästhetische Gestaltungsmittel entdecken und auf Deutsch beschreiben (z.B. Wortspiel in einem Prosatext, Slang in einem Comic, Reim in einem Gedicht).	FS2F.2.A.2.c FS3I.2.A.2.b
	d	» können sich in eine Geschichte hineinversetzen, neue Welten entdecken und zu eigenen Vorlieben finden (z.B. Kriminalgeschichte, Science Fiction, Comic).	

Figure 4: Competence descriptions of 1) Understanding texts, with regard to empathy (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2017, 54)

In figure 4 it can be seen that the pupils are expected to put themselves into "new worlds". Although there is no explicit mention of characters, they are an integral part of the narrative, which is why empathy promotion, although not explicitly mentioned, is also a goal of the competence *Reading*.

In the case of transversal competences, the promotion of empathy can be found in the *Social Competences*. The curriculum states that pupils should learn to empathise with

others both cognitively and affectively (Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich 2016, 15).

2.3 Increasing accessibility through teaching methods

To ensure that pupils go through the desired learning processes, tasks and lessons need to go beyond simply considering subject methodology. In this chapter, the influence of motivation and heterogeneity on learning and, conversely, on lesson planning will be shown.

2.3.1 Motivation

Motivation is an important prerequisite for learning. In this context, many different theories of motivation have been established. In the following, the motivation theory of the self-determination theory by Deci and Ryan (1985) will be presented. Put simply, motivation, according to Deci and Ryan, is an inner state that influences how learners interact with things (Woolfolk 2014, 386). Psychology distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Both types are important preconditions for learning but originate from very different sources. When learners are intrinsically motivated, they do something because they enjoy doing it. The task itself is enjoyable to them. By comparison, with extrinsic motivation learners do not perform a task out of personal enjoyment but because of outer consequences, be they positive or negative (Woolfolk 2014, 387 – 388). For learners to be able to fully engage with material, it is essential that they develop intrinsic motivation (Grimm et al. 2015, 177). In conclusion, motivation is not a given, but is dependent on the individual's assessment and relationship with the task.

As already shown in the multi-level model of reading (see figure 1), motivation, especially intrinsic, is a key factor in reading, and thus in engaging with literature (Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 15). If the pupils are motivated to engage with the text, the learning success is also greater. Kuty further analyses motivation in the context of literature and defines four aspects that influence how intrinsically and extrinsically motivated pupils are. These aspects are 1) reading competence, 2) attitude towards reading, 3) sociocultural context, and 4) material (Kuty 2015, 57 – 58). However, I would like to add a fifth point that influences motivation in regard to literature, especially in the EFL classroom, namely the method. The lesson plan and the activities that accompany reading assignments also have an impact

on motivation. If the tasks are boring or unsolvable, it lowers the reading motivation even if the material is interesting (cf. Dörnyei 2001, 75). It is important to mention that creating and maintaining motivation is a lengthy process for both the teacher and the pupils. The promotion of all aspects mentioned by Kutty is thus not possible within the framework of this master thesis. Rather, it will focus on how tasks can be designed to be motivating. Regarding the activities, Dörnyei elaborates, that in order for activities to be motivating and appealing to learners, the following points need to be considered:

Breaking the monotony of learning:

Teachers should opt for different teaching methods in order to bring variety and maintain motivation. This variety can be related to task types, language skills or organisational format (individual work, group work, pair work) (Dörnyei 2001, 74).

Making tasks more interesting:

No matter how much variety a teacher incorporates in their lessons, it is of no use if the tasks themselves are boring. To make sure this is not the case, the following list presents some suggestions:

- Tasks should be challenging (Dörnyei 2001, 76). However, teachers need to be wary as to not make the tasks too difficult. If a task is too demanding, it may decrease motivation (Woolfolk 2014, 62).
- The tasks and the material should appeal to the pupils' interests (Dörnyei 2001, 76).
- Tasks should be intriguing, e.g., by allowing multiple ways to solve it or dealing with ambiguous or paradox problems (Dörnyei 2001, 76).
- Tasks should ideally deal with issues that pupils can relate to, e.g., problems of their real lives (Dörnyei 2001, 76).
- Tasks should allow pupils opportunities to celebrate their achievements (Dörnyei 2001, 22).
- Tasks should be well structured and offer scaffolding (Brandt 2020, 293).

Finally, Dörnyei continues that in motivational teaching, learning objectives always need to be made transparent so pupils precisely know what is expected of them (Dörnyei 2001, 81 - 82). In addition, cooperative learning settings are particularly motivating for learners.

Slavin even defines cooperative learning as "one of the greatest success stories in the history of educational research" (1996, 43).

2.3.2 Heterogeneity

The average classroom nowadays is very heterogeneous (Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 9). Heterogeneity refers to the fact that everyone is different, or in other words, heterogeneous in terms of different features, ranging from hair colour to learning strategies (Trautmann and Wischer 2011, 39). However, when it comes to teaching it is important to understand which of these heterogeneous features influence learning (Trautmann and Wischer 2011, 37). According to Berger and Pfiffner, these features can be grouped into six categories.

- 1) cognitive performance (ability to understand process information)
 - 2) prior knowledge (different prior knowledge depending on subject and topic)
 - 3) language proficiency (different proficiency regarding linguistic skills and performative skills, e.g., speaking)
 - 4) Learning behaviour (motivation, use of learning strategies)
 - 5) social behaviour (autonomous learning, willingness to cooperate)
 - 6) sociocultural context (differences in how important learning is or how much learners are supported)
 - 7) migration (differences in culture, first language)
- (Berger and Pfiffner 2018, 13 - 15).

The features described apply to learning in general and are not exclusive to learning in the EFL classroom. Nevertheless, in the EFL classroom, special attention must be paid to levels 3) language proficiency and 7) migration.

Without the necessary language proficiency, pupils will not be able to participate in the lessons. According to Brandt, this level is one of the most important determiners of pupils' learning success (2020, 293). Hermes adds that learners have significantly more language problems in a foreign language than in their first language, hence why particular care must be taken in teaching to eliminate such difficulties in advance, for example through pre-activities (Hermes 1994, 251; Grimm et al. 2015, 123). As already explained by Grabe and

Stoller, migration, or the learner's first language, also has an influence on how they learn a foreign language. The more similar the foreign language is to the first language phonetically, grammatically, and lexically, the easier it is for learners to master the foreign language (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 41 - 47).

However, knowing how the learners differ from each other is only the beginning of accommodating their needs. In a next step, teachers must understand how learners can be supported to accommodate their needs (Trautmann and Wischer 2011, 69). This support takes shape in the methods and activities offered to the learners. If the selected activities and methods match the pupils needs, they can interact with the material more thoroughly and thus improve their learning (Klippert 2010, 80). In order for teachers to know how to adapt their material, they need to know what to adapt. Luder defined six dimensions, in which one's teaching can be differentiated.

- 1) Differentiating learning aims
- 2) Differentiating time per activity
- 3) Differentiating amount of material
- 4) Differentiating difficulty
- 5) Differentiating support
- 6) Differentiating media and presentation

(Luder 2019, 21)

In this context, Vogt mentions the teaching approach of task-based language teaching (TBLT) (Vogt 2017, 329). She argues that this approach is particularly well suited for heterogeneous language teaching, as it allows for holistic and open-ended, personally involving, and cooperative activities (Vogt 2017, 239). Grimm et al. define TBLT as follows: «The focus of a task is on meaning and appropriate interaction as well as process- and product-oriented performance as the means and goals of learning [...]. Learners employ their linguistic and cognitive resources to retrieve and exchange information or to discuss opinions in order to achieve an outcome that is not primarily a linguistic one» (Grimm et al. 2015, 69). In other words, the learner uses language to communicate, solve problems and achieve communicative goals rather than to practice specific forms. To accommodate this focus, teachers thus need to offer opportunities for meaningful and authentic interaction (Grimm et al. 2015, 69). However, TBLT does not only consist of incidental learning, but is

accompanied by explicit language learning, e.g., looking up words to solve an issue and receiving feedback (Grimm et al. 2015, 69). The focus on meaning however poses risks in the form of the fossilisation of errors (Grimm et al. 2015, 72). In order to avoid this issue, teachers need to either proactively anticipate problems and offer support or react after the learners' output (Grimm et al. 2015, 72). How exactly TBLT tasks are structured and assessed will be discussed in chapter "5.1.1 Task-based language teaching".

3 Linguistic analysis

As established in chapter "2.1.2 How publishers grade", graded readers are simplified in terms of their linguistic properties as well as their content. In the following chapter, the adaptation of linguistic properties in three core passages of *Frankenstein* between three different graded readers and the original will be examined, in order to determine how the passages differ linguistically.

The analysis has three main focuses.

The first focus is on lexis. As already pointed out in chapter "2.1.2 How publishers grade", the difficulty of the words, as well as the number of headwords has an influence on how difficult a version is rated. With regard to the difficulty of words Lucas mentions that in order to simplify texts, the individual words of the original are either 1) replaced, 2) omitted or 3) added (1991, 243). These statements will be examined on the basis of the three passages. For each version, the analysis examines how many words are used to retell the same passage as well as how lexically demanding the passages are within their respective versions. The absolute number of words can determine how much the passages have been effectively lexically abbreviated compared to the original. In addition, it can be examined how the words are distributed within the CEFR in terms of their difficulty. The hypothesis that underlies this focus is that the difficulty of words consistently decreases with the CEFR language level of the graded readers.

The second focus is on parts of speech. Specifically, the analysis examines how individual parts of speech are managed in comparison to the original. The focus originates from two hypotheses. In a first hypothesis it is assumed that especially adverbs and adjectives are

omitted relative to the total number of words in graded readers. This hypothesis stems from Lucas' findings, that lexical simplification takes part on three levels, the one concerning this focus being 2) omission (1991, 243). By simplifying the lexical challenges for the readers, unnecessary parts, such as lengthy descriptions of events that are not of core value to the story, are being avoided. Graded readers would thus focus more on driving the story forward and would drop the adjectives and adverbs, since they often only provide additional information and are not absolutely necessary for the understanding of the text. In a second hypothesis I expect that the relative number of verbs will be higher in the graded readers. By omitting detailed descriptions and focusing on driving the story forward, editors would need more action words to do so. Moreover, by omitting detailed descriptions the relative number of verbs should automatically increase.

The third focus is on sentence structure. In chapter "2.1.2 How publishers grade" it was described that the texts are simplified not only by lexis and content, but also grammatically. Dirks reveals that one way to do so is by reducing the average sentence length, and decreasing the relative number of subordinate and main clauses to the total number of sentences (2004, 39). Hill further specifies this by explaining that easier graded readers prefer to use simple sentences and dialogues to tell a plot, in order to keep the texts as easy as possible (2008, 196). In this focus of the analysis, those claims that 1) the relative number of main and subordinate clauses increases to the relative number of sentences with increasing language level, 2) the sentence length decreases with CEFR difficulty, and 3) easier versions use more dialogue to tell a plot, will be examined.

The results of the analysis are presented in tabular form and subsequently commented on. The focus of the commentary is on the hypotheses and claims of the three focuses lexis, parts of speech and sentence structure. However, before reading the tables, a few remarks need to be made in advance. The total sum of all parts of speech is in some cases more than the total number of words. This is because abbreviations (e.g., "don't") are counted in their unabbreviated form (e.g., "do not"). Additionally, the percentages added together may not add up to exactly 100% in some cases. This is because the percentages have been either rounded up or down from the second decimal place in each case. Lastly, when analysing the difficulty of words some words were not able to be categorised into one of the six language levels of the CEFR as of May 2023. These words were collected in the category "unlisted".

As already alluded to, three core passages from the original are analysed for this part. The choice of the respective scenes was challenging for several reasons. On the one hand, not every scene is present in every work. This leads to the fact that some scenes, which are important for the novel, e.g., Victor's vision of Elizabeth's death, cannot be used for the analysis. In addition, the scenes differ in length. While some scenes, for instance the scene in which the creature describes how it stayed in a hovel to observe Agatha and learnt her language, are described in a few sentences in the graded reader versions, they take up several pages in the original. This large discrepancy in length also made it difficult to determine, when a specific scene starts or ends. For that reason, I took the liberty to determine myself, when each passage starts or ends. The scenes will thus be briefly described at the beginning of each sub-chapter and the page numbers will be given. Because the characters are of significant importance for pupils to develop empathy (see chapter "2.2.4 Developing empathy through literature"), the scenes were also chosen to focus on the two protagonists – Victor and the creature. The choice of text passages to be analysed fell on passage 1: The birth of the creature, passage 2: The creature's request for a partner, and passage 3: The death of Elizabeth. The last scene, however, is not present in the SFB version. This may be accounted to the fact, that the book is aimed at toddlers and a graphic death had been considered unsuitable for the young audience by the editors. However, as this scene is incredibly important to the development of the two protagonists, the scene will be analysed regardless.

3.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature

As previously mentioned, the first passage that is being analysed is the moment, in which Victor's creature comes to live. The beginning of the scene was determined to be the moment Victor prepares his workshop for the creature's electrical revival and ends when Victor runs out of his laboratory in shock after seeing the creature.

The detailed results of the linguistic analysis can be found in the appendix "8.1 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 OR", "8.2 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 RR", "8.3 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 MR", "8.4. Linguistic analysis Passage 1 SFB". The evaluation of the results of the linguistic analysis can be seen in table 2 below.

	OR Part I, Chapter IV, p. 38 - 39	RR (B1) Chapter 5, p. 19 - 21	MR (A2) Chapter 2, p. 14 - 15	SFB (A1) p. 3 - 6
Number of words	311 (100%)	153 (100%)	221 (100%)	17 (100%)
Difficulty of words	A1 193 (62%) A2 36 (11,6%) B1 20 (6,4%) B2 13 (4,1%) C1 7 (2,3%) C2 7 (2,3%) Unlisted 35 (11,3%)	A1 113 (73,9%) A2 21 (13,9%) B1 15 (9,9%) B2 2 (1,3%) Unlisted 2 (1,3%)	A1 156 (70,6%) A2 35 (15,8%) B1 23 (10,4%) B2 4 (1,8%) C2 3 (1,4%)	A1 7 (41,2%) A2 2 (11,7%) B1 2 (11,7%) B2 1 (5,9%) Unlisted 5 (29,4%)
Number of sentences	13	15	34	5
Average number of words per sentence	23,9	10,2	6,5	3,4
Main clauses	18	18	41	4
Subordinate clauses	11	3	1	0
Noun	68 (21,1%)	35 (25,9%)	47 (21,3%)	6 (35,3%)
Article / determiner	50 (15,6%)	20 (13%)	40 (18,0%)	2 (11,8%)
Adjective	31 (9,6%)	14 (9,2%)	22 (10%)	0 (0%)
Verb	52 (16,1%)	30 (19,6%)	49 (22,1%)	4 (23,5%)
Adverb	19 (5,9%)	10 (6,5%)	13 (5,8%)	1 (5,9%)
Preposition	37 (11,5%)	14 (9,2%)	10 (4,5%)	0
Pronoun	27 (8,4%)	17 (11,1%)	19 (8,5%)	1 (5,9%)
Conjunction	22 (6,8%)	9 (5,8%)	16 (7,2%)	0
Other (Interjections, numerals, infinitive markers)	5 (1,6%)	4 (2,6%)	5 (2,3%)	4 (23,5%)

Table 2: Linguistic comparison "The birth of the creature"

It is noticeable that the passage differs considerably in terms of the total number of words between the different versions. OR's version clearly contains the most words (311) followed by the A2 version by MR (211), with RR's version ranking third with 153 words and lastly SFB with a significantly shortened version with only 17 words. The difference comes from with how much detail the different versions describe the passage. However, while the three graded reader versions have in common that they are all abbreviated versions of the original, they differ in what they modified. In the original version about a third of the total

number of words focuses on the events prior to the creature's revival, another third on Victor's description of his creation and the last third on Victor's reaction to it. RR's version follows OR's model very closely and the ratio of words used to describe individual scenes is similar. In some cases, RR even directly copies sentences or sentence fragments from the original, e.g., "[...] I collected the instruments of life around me [...]" (Shelley 1818, 38; Shelley 2012, 19.) MR on the other hand spends about half of its total wordcount on the description of the events that lead up to the creature's revival. It is worth mentioning here that the description of these events differs substantially from the original. While in the original the weather is described only incidentally, MR's version describes the weather in detail. However, not only that, but various descriptions are added that are not present within the original but are entirely creative contributions of the editors. For example, in the original there is no reference to lightning, wires or the like. In MR's version, however, it is described in detail how the weather and appliances in the laboratory contribute to the animation of the creature. These lengthy descriptions that are not present in the OR are responsible for MR's wordcount to be higher than RR's. Lengthy descriptions, however, are not entirely alien to the novel. While MR added it to a passage that does not originally include it, other passages in the original, e.g., the description of the Alps in Volume II chapter 1 (cf. Shelley 1818, 69 – 74), include very detailed and extensive description of nature and scenery. SFB handles the passage entirely differently from the other versions. It lacks any kind of description of the events that lead up to the animation, Victor's description of the creature or Victor's reaction. This can, however, be attributed to the fact that some parts, for example the physical appearance of the creature, are graphically illustrated rather than described. Though, the illustrations also vary from how the creature is described in the original, for example, in terms of the creature's skin colour.

If we look at the difficulty of words, we see that, in addition to the smaller wordcount, the difficulty of words has also been changed. The replacement of lexically challenging words with easier ones is evident in all versions. For example, the word "vanished" (C2) from the original is exchanged with "disappear" (B2) in RR's version. While in this example the meaning of the words remains similar, there are also examples where the exchanged word or phrase alters the intended meaning of the original. For example, in the original the creature is not even described as a monster in this passage. Victor uses a variety of other words, including "wretch" or "being," whilst all graded readers describe the creature as a

"monster" from the beginning. However, the use of the word "monster" has a significant impact on how the creature is portrayed. While words like "being" are neutral, "monster" already has a clear negative connotation and describes the creature as something scary and dangerous.

The four versions also differ in terms of the difficulty of words. OR is the only version that uses words from all six CEFR language levels. This version also has the smallest percentage of A1 and A2 words in relation to the total wordcount. Thus, it can be stated that this version is the most difficult in terms of difficulty of words. From the distribution of words between the language levels of the CEFR, RR and MR are similar, so it can be assumed that these versions are similarly challenging lexically. The only difference is that MR requires more words to be known and the larger vocabulary required may be considered a greater lexical challenge. SFB has the highest proportion of unlisted words. This finding stems from SFB using a lot of sounds to describe the scene, such as "Eek" or "Grr", which cannot be classified as specific words.

In summary, it can be stated that, with regard to the lexical difficulty, all versions have made significant simplifications compared to the original. The hypothesis, that the lexical difficulty consistently decreases with CEFR language level can only be partly verified in this passage. Whilst OR (C2) has the most challenging lexis and SFB (A1) the easiest, the versions MR (B1) and RR (B2) are of comparable lexical difficulty, thus the lexical difficulty does not consistently decrease with CEFR rating.

In terms of the second focus, parts of speech, table 2 provides an insight on how the different parts of speech are distributed over the total number of words. Surprisingly, there are no exceptionally large differences between the relative numbers of adjectives and adverbs among the different versions, as it was assumed in the first hypothesis of this focus. The more descriptive language of the original, however, can be seen in the number of prepositions used, with OR leading with 11.5%. The second hypothesis for this focus, which claims that the relative number of verbs increases with decreasing CEFR level, can be verified in this passage. OR (C2) has the smallest number of verbs with only 16,1%, followed by RR (B2) with 19,6%, MR (B1) with 22,1% and lastly SFB (A1) with 23,5%.

In terms of sentence structure, OR, despite having the largest number of words, has the fewest sentences compared to the other versions. Thus, OR also has the largest average number of words per sentence. In addition, OR has the most sophisticated sentence

structure, which can be seen in the relative number of main and subordinate clauses to sentences. The next challenging version, RR, is already significantly simplified regarding these categories. With a much smaller number of average words per sentence (10,2) and an overall simpler sentence structure the version is much easier to decipher for readers than OR (cf. Neugebauer and Nodari 2012, 43). MR simplified these categories even further. What is striking with this edition, is, that it has much more sentences than any other version and thus a very small number of average words per sentence. MR has 34 sentences, as opposed to OR with 13, RR with 15 and SFB with 5. The passage thus presents the content of the novel in much smaller portions. While this may help readers with understanding the text as the content is presented in a very compact form, it presents the readers with unauthentic language. As mentioned in chapter “2.1.3 Research on graded readers” this issue has already been criticised by different researchers and this sub-chapter validates their criticism. MR also tells the plot mainly using simple sentences and thus avoids many complex sentences. Lastly, SFB tells the entire passage using only main clauses, uses a lot of dialogue and has the smallest average number of words per sentences which comes to little surprise given that SFB uses only 17 words in the entire passage. Overall, the three claims by Hill (2008, 196) and Dirks (2004, 36 ff.) 1) the relative number of main and subordinate clauses increases to the relative number of sentences with increasing language level, 2) the sentence length decreases with CEFR difficulty, and 3) easier versions use more dialogue to tell a plot, can all be verified in this passage. OR has the highest number of main and subordinate clauses relative to number of sentences and the ratio decreases with each language level. Secondly, the average sentence length also decreases with the CEFR language level. Lastly, only the easiest version uses dialogue, thus confirming the third claim.

3.2 Passage 2: The creature’s request

The second passage that is being analysed is the creature’s request for a female companion. The scene starts with the creature voicing its request to Victor and ends with Victor agreeing to it. The detailed results of the linguistic analysis can be found in the appendix “8.5 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 OR”, “8.6 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 RR”, “8.7 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 MR”, “8.8 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 SFB”. The evaluation of the results of the linguistic analysis can be seen in table 3 below.

	OR Part II, Chapter IX, p. 118 - 122	RR (B1) Chapter 18, p. 55 - 56	MR (A2) Chapter 6, p. 32	SFB (A1) p. 15 - 16
Number of words	1447 (100%)	408 (100%)	247 (100%)	12 (100%)
Average difficulty of words	A1 929 (64,2%) A2 131 (9%) B1 133 (9,2%) B2 105 (7,3%) C1 37 (2,6%) C2 20 (1,4%) Unlisted 91 (6,3%)	A1 295 (72,3%) A2 56 (13,7%) B1 43 (10,5%) B2 6 (1,4%) C2 1 (0,2%) Unlisted 7 (1,7%)	A1 185 (74,9%) A2 39 (15,9%) B1 15 (6,1%) B2 6 (2,4%) Unlisted 1 (0,4%)	A1 5 (50%) A2 1 (10%) B1 2 (20%) Unlisted 2 (20%)
Number of sentences	63	46	39	4
Average number of words per sentence	22,9	8,8	6,3	3
Main clauses	124	58	42	3
Subordinate clauses	64	14	2	0
Noun	244 (16,9%)	58 (14,2%)	34 (13,8%)	3 (25%)
Article / determiner	188 (13%)	40 (9,8%)	28 (11,3%)	1 (8,3%)
Adjective	66 (4,6%)	26 (6,4%)	11 (4,5%)	0 (0%)
Verb / particle	347 (24%)	120 (29,4%)	72 (29,6%)	3 (25%)
Adverb	83 (5,7%)	27 (6,6%)	21 (8,5%)	2 (17%)
Preposition	152 (10,5%)	27 (6,6%)	17 (6,8%)	0 (0%)
Pronoun	239 (15,5%)	82 (20%)	50 (20,2%)	1 (8,3%)
Conjunction	104 (7,2%)	21 (5,1%)	9 (3,6%)	0 (0%)
Other (Interjections, numerals. Infinitive markers)	27 (1,9%)	8 (2%)	6 (2,4%)	2 (17%)

Table 3: Linguistic comparison "The creature's request"

Like chapter "3.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature", the substantial difference in the total number of words between the different versions is noticeable in this passage, although the difference is significantly larger in this passage as in passage 1. OR's version has the highest number of words with 1447, followed by RR with 408, MR with 247 and SFB with 12. However, in contrast to passage 1, where MR with a language level of B1 had a higher wordcount than RR with a language level of B2, the number of words consistently

decreases with the CEFR language level. Also, in this passage, it must be noted that MR once again adds information that is not found in the original passage, which artificially increases its total word count. However, the added information in MR is not entirely made up by the editors. The passage is an argument in which Victor threatens to kill the creature. This conversation takes place in the original, just not in this particular passage (cf. Shelley 1818, 77). Thus, the passage is not entirely made up, but it has been repositioned within the plot. Apart from that, all graded readers follow the original in content. RR is closest to the original in terms of content, but the heavily abridged version has the consequence that all sentences have been shortened as well as the content having been reduced, which makes copying entire phrases in this passage impossible. SFB is again quite different from the other versions. Although the creature's wish is introduced in the previous pages, there is no mention of it in the specific passage itself. Moreover, the request in this version consists only of the creature growling at Victor and Victor sending him away. Thus, both core elements of the passage are missing in this description. The readers get no insight into the creature's past, nor does Victor temporarily agree to the request.

In terms of the difficulty of words there are also similarities to passage 1, as lexical simplification can also be observed in this passage amongst all graded readers. In percentage terms, OR has the fewest simple words, followed by RR, MR and finally SFB. With this regard, the hypothesis of the lexical focus can be confirmed, as the proportional distribution of the words within the CEFR rating scale shows, that easier versions use a higher percentage of easier words. This can be seen, for example, in CEFR language level B1, where in RR 10.5% of the words can be assigned to this level, and in MR only 6.1%. Thus, in this passage, not only the larger vocabulary required in RR is a challenge for the readers, but also the greater difficulty of the words compared to MR. SFB requires the smallest vocabulary of all versions and also has the easiest vocabulary, which can be seen, for example, in the very high number of words in category A1 (50%). As for passage 1, it can be assumed that the different distribution of the difficulty of words among the versions is not only because there are fewer words in general, but also because words were exchanged purposefully. For example, the term "malicious" (C2) in OR was replaced with "evil" (B2) in RR and with "unhappiness" (B2) in MR.

Regarding the distribution of the parts of speech, it is noticeable that RR uses the most adjectives proportionally, and OR and MR use a similar percentage. The original also

performs surprisingly poorly in terms of adverbs and has the least of all versions at only 5.7%. The first hypothesis of this focus assumed that OR uses significantly more adjectives to describe the passages more precisely. In this case, this assumption does not hold. However, the second hypothesis that graded readers use a higher number of verbs to advance the plot is again confirmed in this passage. OR uses only 24% of its words for verbs, with RR and MR using close to 30% each. However, as with passage 1, OR uses significantly more prepositions than the other versions with 10.5%. Thus, in OR relations between different parts of speech are more accurately described through the use of prepositions, but actions or nouns are not described more accurately compared to the other versions.

In terms of sentence structure, a similar trend to passage 1 can be observed. OR has the most challenging sentence structure (124 main clauses and 64 subordinate clauses) and the highest average number of words per sentence (22,9). RR follows in second and also uses a rather complex sentence structure throughout this passage, with 58 main clauses and 14 subordinate clauses, and also ranks second in average number of words per sentence (8,8). MR on the other hand still consists mostly of simple or compound sentences by using mainly main clauses (42). Also, the average number of words per sentence for this version is similar to the one in passage 1 (6,3). Similar to passage 1 SFB is still only made of main clauses and offers a very small number of average words per sentence with only 3. Moreover, SFB also once again uses a lot of dialogue to tell the plot. Whilst dialogue is also used in the other versions, SFB exclusively uses this style of narration to narrate the plot. With these findings all three claims by Hill (2008, 196) and Dirks (2004, 36 ff.) of this focus can be verified. The relative number of main and subordinate clauses in relation to sentences, as well as the average sentence length, increase with CEFR level and the easier the version, the bigger the focus on dialogue.

3.3 Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth

The last passage for the linguistic analysis concerns Elizabeth's death. The scene starts with Victor noticing Elizabeth's scream and concludes with him fainting. The detailed results of the linguistic analysis can be found in the appendix "8.9 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 OR", "8.10 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 RR" and "8.11 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 MR". As stated in the introduction, this passage is not present in SFB. The evaluation of the results of the linguistic analysis can be seen in table 4 below.

	OR Part III, Chapter IV, p. 165	RR (B1) Chapter 26, p. 75 - 76	MR (A2) Chapter 8, p. 46 - 48
Number of words	203 (100%)	96 (100%)	103 (100%)
Average difficulty of words	A1 125 (61,5%) A2 22 (10,8%) B1 17 (8,4%) B2 12 (6%) C2 3 (1,5%) C2 6 (3%) Unlisted 18 (9%)	A1 72 (75%) A2 15 (15,7%) B1 7 (7,3%) B2 1 (2,1%) Unlisted 1 (1%)	A1 73 (70,9%) A2 13 (12,6%) B1 8 (8%) B2 4 (4%) C2 1 (1%) Unlisted 4 (4%)
Number of sentences	12	11	16
Average number of words per sentence	16,9	8,7	6,4
Main clauses	19	12	16
Subordinate clauses	2	0	1
Noun	38 (18,7%)	15 (15,6%)	27 (26,2%)
Article / determiner	31 (15,2%)	14 (14,6%)	19 (18,4%)
Adjective	18 (8,9%)	7 (7,3%)	10 (9,7%)
Verb / particle	44 (21,7%)	20 (20,9%)	18 (17,4%)
Adverb	17 (8,4%)	13 (13,6%)	10 (9,7%)
Preposition	14 (6,9%)	11 (11,5%)	7 (6,8%)
Pronoun	20 (9,6%)	12 (12,5%)	10 (9,7%)
Conjunction	17 (8,4%)	3 (3,1%)	1 (1%)
Other (Interjections, numerals, infinitive markers)	4 (2%)	1 (1%)	1 (1%)

Table 4: Linguistic comparison "The death of Elizabeth"

Similar to the other two tables OR once again has the highest wordcount with 203, followed by MR with 103 and then by RR with 96. In contrast to the other two passages, however, MR did not adapt the content largely, which is why both graded readers keep close to the original in terms of content, albeit in its abbreviated version. OR, RR and MR focus heavily on what has been done to Elizabeth, what she looks like and what injuries she has. Previously it was mentioned that graded readers focus on the important parts of a plot and tend to leave out seemingly irrelevant information, such as detailed descriptions of characters

and their surroundings (cf. Macmillan 2014, 2). In this case however, Elizabeth's death, how she died, and the cruelty of the crime is a kernel and thus an integral part of the story, which ends up deciding Victor's and the creature's fate for the rest of the story. As Elizabeth's death is a defining moment for Victor, the publishers of both graded reader versions decided to emphasise the cruelty of the crime and depict it in detail. RR, however, still follows the original more closely. This may seem surprising, considering that MR is closer to the original in terms of word count. This is because in MR some details, e.g., Elizabeth's body, are described somewhat differently from the original (cf. Shelley 2005, 47). In addition, some thoughts are formulated more explicitly. For example, in MR it is explicitly stated that the creature kills Elizabeth instead of Victor in order to take revenge on Victor (cf. Shelley 2005, 46), whereas in RR and OR the motif behind Elizabeth's death is only hinted at (cf. Shelley 1818, 165; Shelley 2012, 75).

Regarding the lexical exchange of words between the different versions, it can again be observed that difficult words from the original were exchanged for simpler ones in the graded readers. For example, "expire" from OR with the language level of C2 was replaced with "live" with a difficulty of A1 in RR, with the respective sentence missing entirely in MR. Also, OR is again the only version that uses words from all language levels. In this passage, however, in contrast to table 2 and table 3, MR is more difficult than RR in terms of lexical requirements, although MR has a lower CEFR level than RR. The hypothesis that assumed that the lexical difficulty consistently decreases with language level cannot be verified for this passage.

Also different from the previous passages is the distribution of parts of speech. Whereas the graded readers previously had significantly more verbs than OR in percentage terms OR has the most verbs in this passage. This is because events in this passage are often described with multiple verbs in the original. To illustrate this, Victor's fainting can be considered. In the original, there are several verbs related to the situation. Both "lose recollection" and "fainted" are used to describe Victor's fainting, while in RR only "collapsed" is mentioned and Victor remains entirely conscious in MR, thus missing the entire event. If this is applied to the whole scene, in addition to the general larger content, it becomes clear why the data in this passage is different from those in the previous tables.

However, similar to the previous two passages, OR once again scores second in adjectives and last in adverbs, thus once again disproving the hypothesis that graded readers have

a significantly smaller number of adjectives and adverbs in comparison to the original. In this passage it is also noticeable that OR does not have significantly more prepositions compared to the other passages, as was the case in the previous tables. Instead, OR has unusually many conjunctions. The remarkably high difference can mainly be attributed to OR using compound sentences, while the majority of sentences in the graded readers are simple sentences. Moreover, the adjectives used to describe Elizabeth's condition are often connected with conjunctions in OR. Also, the proportional number of verbs is highest in OR which contrasts the findings in the previous two tables and rebuts the hypothesis that graded readers use more verbs.

Regarding the average number of words per sentence, table 4 aligns with the results of table 2 and table 3. OR again has the longest sentences on average (16.9), whereas RR has the second longest sentences (8.7), and MR has the shortest with only 6.4 words per sentence. In addition, OR is still the version with the most complicated sentence structure, as can be seen in the number of sentences in relation to the number of subordinate and main clauses. Just like in passage 1 and 2, the versions RR and MR rarely make use of compound sentences or subordinate clauses and mainly consist of simple sentences, whereas OR tells the majority of the novel using compound or complicated sentences. However, in contrast to the previous two passage, MR is slightly more difficult than RR with regard to sentence structure, despite the easier overarching CEFR language level. Although, the question arises as to how much one subordinate clause really matters in terms of difficulty. For this passage, only one of three claims made in the introduction can be verified, which is that the average sentence length increases with CEFR rating. However, the first and third claim of this focus, which claim that the relative number of main and subordinate clauses increases to the relative number of sentences with increasing language level and that easier versions use more dialogue to tell a plot, cannot be verified. For the latter it can be observed that all three versions tell the plot exclusively through Victor's point of view.

3.4 Summary

By looking at the tables it becomes evident that linguistic and literary material is lost in the process of editing a literary classic, as the editors focus on what they consider to be the most important for the story and the plot and what is necessary for comprehension. Overall,

three hypotheses and three claims made by the theory of Dirks (2004, 36 ff.) and Hill (2008, 196) were examined. The first hypothesis assumed that the lexical difficulty consistently decreases along with the CEFR language level. Concerning the simplification on a lexical level Hill argues, that the difficulty of words is adapted to the appropriate language level of the respective graded readers (2008, 185). Thus, more difficult versions should include more difficult words. This hypothesis can only be partly verified. Whilst OR always uses the most difficult lexis there is no substantial difference between MR and RR. Lucas also argues in more detail that lexical adaptation occurs on three levels 1) replacement, 2) omission, and 3) addition (1991, 243). Only level 1) replacement and 2) omission could be observed in these passages. In all editions, difficult words from the original were replaced with simpler synonyms (e.g., passage 2 “malicious” in OR is replaced with “evil” in RR and “unhappiness” in MR), which corresponds to level 1) replacement. Level 2) omission can also be observed in the passages. Whereas the word “vanished” is used in OR and “disappeared” in RR, a replacement of the word “vanished” is missing entirely in MR. Level 3) addition could not be observed in the passages. Whilst in some cases inexplicit thoughts are explicitly formulated in MR, this does not account to level 3) addition, as it does not concern the simplification of an individual word but rather assist readers in comprehending the underlying messages of a text.

With regard to the parts of speech, the first hypothesis of this focus claimed that graded readers use significantly less adverbs and adjectives to tell the plot in comparison to the original. This hypothesis has proven to be false. In all three passages the graded readers did not substantially differ in their proportional distribution of adjectives and adverbs from the original. The second hypothesis which claimed that graded readers use more verbs than the original can be partly verified. Whilst this is the case for passage 1 and passage 2, passage 3 showed that the OR uses the most verbs in this respective scene.

With regard to the sentence structure of the different versions the three claims by Hill (2008, 196) and Dirks (2004, 36 ff.) were examined, namely 1) the relative number of main and subordinate clauses increases to the relative number of sentences, 2) the sentence length decreases with CEFR difficulty, and 3) easier versions use more dialogue to tell a plot. All three claims can be proven in this analysis. OR always had the highest relative number of main and subordinate clauses to the relative number of sentences and the longest sentences. Both factors decreased with CEFR language level. The easier versions also

used more dialogue to tell the plot, though the difference between the three versions was not large.

Overall, the linguistic simplification takes place on a sentence level (sentence structure and length) and a semantic level (e.g., substituting difficult words with easier ones) rather than a reduction in a particular part of speech. The findings align with the theory, which was discussed in chapter “2.1.2 How publishers grade”.

4 Literary analysis

Chapter 3 “Linguistic analysis” analysed in detail how the texts differ from each other linguistically regarding different categories. Based on the data, it became clear that many changes were made due to adapting the material to different language levels. These linguistic changes, e.g., the exchange of words, however, have consequences not only on the difficulty of the text, but also on the literary meaning of the passages. These changes in literary meaning were already briefly analysed in chapter 3 by exemplarily comparing exchanged words with each other and how they carry different meanings. Chapter “4 Literary analysis” builds on the findings of chapter 3 and expands on them.

The literary analysis serves as preparation for the classroom project and relates to the second research question, namely:

2. How can task-based language teaching introduce secondary school pupils to literature and improve their *Reading*, *Dialogic speaking*, and *Empathy* skills and help them work out literary meaning that was changed or lost during the simplification process between the original and graded readers?

In the classroom project, lost literary meaning, as a result of the linguistic simplification, is to be restored through activities. For the classroom project to be able to restore the literary meaning of the original, it must first be clarified in what way the characters differ concretely among the different versions. The loss of literary material will be exemplified by comparing how Victor and the creature are being characterised, both directly and indirectly. Direct characterisation refers to everything, that is explicitly stated by either the narrator or characters within the text, e.g. “I am anxious” (Neumann and Nünning 2008, 54). Indirect

characterisation refers to a character's speech (what they say and how they say it), actions (what they do and do not do) and their environment (e.g., where they live) (Neumann and Nünning 2008, 54). These features often unintentionally characterise characters. In the following sub-chapters Victor and the creature will be analysed individually with regard to their portrayal among the different versions. The focus on the characters and their emotions relates to the *Empathy* promotion of the teaching project. Since one of the goals of the master thesis is to work out how empathy can be fostered with the help of literature, the focus needs to lie on the characters, as empathy is the understanding of people's emotions and actions (Döring 2013, 297). Döring goes on to describe that for people to feel empathy the readers need to be able to engage with the characters emotionally and cognitively (2008, 305 – 308), thus the different characterisation of the characters emotions is of great importance for empathy development and will be used as data. The material for the analysis will be the same passages as in chapter "3 Linguistic analysis".

To analyse the literary differences among the different graded reader versions and the original as accurately as possible, only the specific passages will be considered for the analysis. Victor's and the creature's direct and indirect characterisation in other passages will thus not be considered. Also, only the literary material will be analysed. Any illustrations that accompany the text will not be focused on in this chapter.

4.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature

The respective passages, along with the linguistic analysis, can be found in appendix "8.1 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 OR", "8.2 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 RR", "8.3 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 MR", "8.4. Linguistic analysis Passage 1 SFB".

Victor

OR

In OR Victor is mainly characterised indirectly by his speech, his actions, and his environment. Little of Victor is characterised directly by himself.

By analysing Victor's indirect characterisation one can tell that he is a very smart, eloquent, and observant man, as well as a very emotional one. Firstly, we can see through his speech, that Victor is very **eloquent**. The speech he uses is features many difficult words and phrases (e.g., "amounted to agony", "endeavoured", etc.) and he uses many complex

sentences to convey his thoughts. Also, the words he uses are often very specific and indicate a large vocabulary (e.g., “dun white sockets”). By his speech we can also deduce that Victor is a very **observant** man. He describes his creature in great detail and focuses on minute details as well as the bigger picture. This can be seen for example in the following sentence: “His yellow skin scarcely covered the work of muscles and arteries beneath; his hair was of a lustrous black, and flowing; [...]” (Shelley 1818, 39). Through Victor’s actions and his environment one can also assume that Victor is **smart**, albeit **lonely** and **fanatic**. After all, he manages to breath life into an inanimate being, which alludes to Victor’s intelligence. However, Victor mentions that he had spent a lot of time in his dark laboratory in solitude to work on his creature and did not do much besides, which infers that Victor is a lonely person. Lastly, his extremely emotional reaction, in which Victor rushes out of his laboratory because he is too disgusted by the creature (cf. Shelley 1818, 39), shows Victor’s fanatic traits. Though it is understandable that Victor is disappointed that his creature does not look the way he wanted it to, the fact that he is that repulsed by it and cannot stand being in the same room, shows how emotionally taxing the creature is on Victor.

Victor personally also goes through plenty of emotions in this short passage. Victor starts off **anxious**. Victor directly uses the noun “anxiety” to describe his emotions (cf. Shelley 1818, 38). This reaction is understandable, considering that he had worked on the creature for the past two years and is eagerly waiting to see the results. This emotion is quickly followed by a mix of **disgust** and **disappointment**. Once the creature starts moving, Victor’s tone changes as he suddenly talks about his creature very negatively, e.g., by using words like “wretch” or “catastrophe”, while it was previously called “creature” (cf. Shelley 1818, 38 – 39). This language is also very condescending and shows that Victor has truly little sympathy for the creature, even though he is its creator. His disappointment and disgust are further highlighted, both directly and indirectly, in how he describes the creature. Whilst he describes the creature in great detail, he does so to highlight its imperfections and compares the creature’s looks to what it should have looked like, or at least what he envisioned it to look like which indirectly hints at Victor’s disappointment. Furthermore, he even directly mentions, how disgusted he is by his creation in the following sentence: «I had desired it with an ardour that far exceeded moderation; but now that I had finished, the beauty of the dream vanished and breathless horror and disgust filled my heart” (Shelley

1818, 39). In the end of the passage Victor becomes **desperate**. He remembers everything he gave up for the creature, how much energy he put into its creation, and how disappointed he is with the end result. Since Victor is so dissatisfied with the creature, the reader can assume that he is desperate and disappointed, since Victor envisioned the creature to be something quite different. The despair is also evident in the fact that Victor does not even manage to stay with the creature or sleep at the end, as he is too preoccupied with his supposed failure (cf. Shelley 1818, 39). With regard to Victor's physical appearance, nothing is mentioned or alluded to in this passage.

RR

In the linguistic analysis (see chapter "3.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature") it was already inferred that this version is closest to the original in terms of content. Thus, it comes to no surprise that many of Victor's original character traits and emotions shine through in this version. Similar to the original, due to Victor's speech and his actions readers can assume that Victor is a **smart** and **observant** man, as he also describes his surroundings and the creature in detail, e.g., "By its weak light, I saw the monster's eyes open" (Shelley 2012, 19) and also manages to animate a lifeless being. However, Victor is not as eloquent as in the original. This is due to the lexical simplification, in which many of the difficult words that Victor uses were exchanged for more common ones. However, Victor does not come across as lonely and fanatic as in the original. Though in this version he also mentions that he had worked on the creature for two years, which reveals his passion but also his loneliness, as he must have spent a lot of time on the creature and in solitude, he does not specify what sacrifices he made for the creature. This allows the readers to assume that the creature did not preoccupy his entire life for the past two years which characterises Victor as a less lonely person than in OR. Also, the reaction to the creature is less emotional, which makes Victor appear less fanatic. He still rushes out of the laboratory, but he does not seem to question his efforts and the sacrifices he made during the last two years. Victor's emotions in this passage align with the one's from the original for the most part. He also starts off **anxious**. Though it is not explicitly stated, Victor describes that his "heart beat painfully hard" (Shelley 2012, 19) which shows that even though Victor is excited for the creature to come to life, he is also a little uneasy about the situation. Victor also does not seem to be disgusted at the creature. Whereas in the original, Victor describes in detail

how much he distastes the looks of the creature, in RR he describes the creature's features neutrally without using any judgmental adjectives. However, Victor still voices his **disappointment** in the creature in several ways. Firstly, he only calls the creature a "monster" or "thing" (Shelley 2012, 19), thus stripping the creature of any humanity. Secondly, Victor also mentions that his "beautiful dream suddenly disappears" (Shelley 2012, 21) once he sees the creature awaken, which highlights how differently Victor pictured his creature to look like and his resulting disappointment. Additionally, Victor also states, how he cannot look at his own creation, as he is too repulsed by it (cf. Shelley 2012, 21).

MR

In this version, Victor is described quite differently from the original. Similar to the original, Victor's speech still suggests him to be a very **observant** man, as he describes in great detail how his creature comes to life (cf. Shelley 2005, 14 – 15). Even though the majority of this passage was heavily edited by the publishers, Victor's observant character traits still come through. Additionally, since Victor also manages to breathe life into a human being in this version, Victor is indirectly characterised as **smart** in this version as well. However, in this version Victor is not as eloquent as in the original. This is due to the lexical simplification. As many difficult words and sentences were replaced by simpler ones (see chapter "3.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature"), Victor's speech does not strike the reader as elaborate and complex as in the original. Also, Victor does not come across as lonely and fanatic anymore. This is because the scenes, in which Victor laments his efforts and sacrifices, as well as how long and under which conditions he worked on the creature, are missing. This strips the literary material from how invested and passionate Victor was in his endeavours and the resulting failure of his efforts are therefore less crushing to him. Regarding Victor's emotions, some changes can also be noted. Whilst Victor is very anxious in the original, he seems more **excited** about the creature's revival in this version. Victor describes that he smiles when he sees the creature, which suggests a pleasant anticipation as opposed to a negative one (cf. Shelley 2005, 15). Regarding his reaction to the creature, Victor also seems more **shocked** than disgusted, disappointed, and desperate. While he does describe the creature's appearance negatively, he does not focus as heavily on the creature's perceived ugliness and does not draw comparisons to what he would have liked the creature to look like. In this version Victor is also less condescending

towards the creature. While he does call it a “monster” (Shelley 2005, 15), he refrains from any other negative names, unlike the original.

SFB

This version of Victor is entirely different from the previous three. Due to the largely abbreviated version, every characteristic that Victor previously had is missing. It is difficult to assign any character traits to Victor. In this version he hardly speaks and when he speaks, he only makes sounds, e.g., “Eek!” (Shelley 2021, 4). This prevents Victor from being characterized as eloquent, smart, or observant, as he simply does not talk much or uses any real language for that matter. In addition, since the readers do not get any insight into how Victor feels whilst waiting for the creature to come alive, or how he feels once seeing it, the emotions fanatic, anxious, disgusted, condescending, disappointed and desperate cannot be seen anywhere in the text. This graded reader did not focus on the character’s emotions or reactions at all and only focused on the kernel of the passage.

The creature

OR

The creature is entirely directly characterised by Victor. The reader does not get any insight into who the creature is on a personal level, but the physical appearance of the creature is described in great detail. Victor says the following:

“His limbs were in proportion, and I had selected his features as beautiful. Beautiful! – Great God! His yellow skin scarcely covered the work of muscles and arteries beneath; his hair was of a lustrous black, and flowing; his teeth of a pearly whiteness; but these luxuriances only formed a more horrid contrast with his watery eyes, that seemed almost of the same colour as the dun white sockets in which they were set, his shrivelled complexion, and straight black lips.” (Shelley 1818, 39)

In this description Victor briefly takes in the entire creature before he focuses on the facial features. Victor describes, that all the limbs of the creature are “in proportion”, which suggests that the creature’s proportions were modelled after a human and that, only judging by its silhouette, Victor succeeded. However, when Victor goes on to describe the creature in more detail, e.g., its skin and eyes, the reader learns that, although every feature was

selected to be beautiful individually, their combination looks horrible. In the description of the creature's facial features Victor focuses on the hair, teeth, eyes, lips, and skin. In his description, Victor highlights the discrepancy between the individual beauty of the features and their horrible ensemble. While every feature individually is described positively, e.g., "[...] his hair was of lustrous black, and flowing; [...]" (Shelley 1818, 39), he also highlights how dissatisfied he is with the ensemble "[...] but these luxuriances only formed a more horrid contrast [...]" (Shelley 1818, 39). The creature is also described as "wretch", "catastrophe" and "being" by Victor (cf. Shelley 1818, 38 – 39). These descriptions are very condescending and strip the creature of any humanity.

RR

Similar to OR, the creature is directly characterised by Victor and the reader only gets an insight into the creature's physical appearance. However, the description of the creature's appearance is much shorter in this version and varies slightly in what is described in comparison to the original. In RR, Victor describes the creature as follows:

"The thing that came to life had enormous arms and legs. His hair was long and black and his teeth were very white. He had a horrible grey-white face and thin, black lips." (Shelley 2012, 20)

Unlike in the original, the readers learn that the creature must be much larger than a normal human being, as its limbs are "enormous" (cf. Shelley 2012, 20). However, we do not learn whether the limbs are in proportion and the creature's eyes are not mentioned. Also, in this version the creature's skin colour varies from the original, as it is now grey-white and not yellow anymore. Apart from these changes, RR describes the same features (hair, teeth, lips), although in an abbreviated way. In this version Victor also refrains from using too judgmental adjectives (e.g., "horrid" in OR) and describes the creature rather neutrally. However, by calling it a "monster" or "thing" he openly negatively labels the creature as something repulsive (cf. Shelley 2012, 19 – 20). In RR, the juxtaposition of the creature's intended beauty and its ugly reality is missing.

MR

Similar to OR and RR, the creature is solely directly characterised by Victor. However, the characterisation is much shorter. Unlike in the original, a general depiction of the creature's

physique is missing. Also, Victor only describes the creature's skin, eyes, and lips and leaves out any description of the creature's hair and teeth. The description is also rather neutral, as he only describes the colour of the skin and general appearance of the features, with the exception of calling the creature's smile "terrible", which is clearly negative (Shelley 2005, 15). Also, the juxtaposition of the creature's intended beauty and realised ugliness is missing in this version. However, as opposed to OR but similar to RR, the creature is also labelled as a "monster" in this version (cf. Shelley 2005, 15). Compared to the original, it can thus be stated that the creature is described much more briefly and neutrally in MR.

SFB

This version differs from the other three. It is the only version in which the creature speaks, though it only makes sounds, e.g., "Grrr" (Shelley 2021, 5). However, from this little statement, the readers cannot really infer any meaning. The sound could be the result of many different emotions and thus does not help the readers assign a specific meaning to it. In addition, this version lacks any physical description of the creature whatsoever. Solely based on the literary material, the readers do not know what the creature looks like. However, similar to RR and MR, the creature is labelled as a "monster!" by Victor, thus also suggesting a negative appearance of the creature (Shelley 2021, 4).

4.2 Passage 2: The creature's request

The respective passages, along with the linguistic analysis, can be found in appendix "8.5 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 OR", "8.6 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 RR", "8.7 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 MR", "8.8 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 SFB".

Victor

OR

Generally, similar to passage 1, Victor's speech also indirectly characterises him as an **eloquent** person, based on his use of difficult vocabulary and sentence structures.

In terms of his emotions, Victor starts off **hostile** towards the creature as he calls it a "being" and refers to its "wickedness" (Shelley 1818, 119). His rejection of the creature is reinforced after listening to the creature's initial request for Victor to create a female companion, as

Victor states that he “could no longer suppress the rage that burned within” him (Shelley 1818, 119). His hostility towards the creature even amounts to Victor rather being tortured by the creature, than consenting to the request (cf. Shelley 1818, 119). However, after listening to the creature, Victor’s previous dismissal of the request and initial hostility gives way to **compassion** as Victor starts to take the creature’s perspective into account. This shift in emotions is portrayed directly, e.g. “I was moved.” (Shelley 1818, 120), and indirectly, e.g., “[...] but I felt that there was some justice in his argument” (Shelley 1818, 120). This is an especially important moment for Victor’s relationship with the creature. In the previous passage and up until the creature’s elaboration of its request, Victor felt nothing but hatred and disgust for his creature but after listening to it, he starts to see behind the creature’s ugly appearance and understand the sentient being behind. He even directly assigns the creature the attribute of being a “sentient being” (Shelley 1818, 120), thus highlighting Victor’s shift from distinguishing between the creature’s physique and its character. Once Victor starts to feel compassion, he also starts to feel some **responsibility** for the creature’s wellbeing. Victor directly voices his responsibility as follows: “[...] and did I not, as his maker, owe him all the portion of happiness that it was in my power to bestow?” (Shelley 1818, 120). However, Victor remains **cautious** of the creature. He does not immediately give into the creature’s request but asks the creature many questions in return, e.g. “How can you, who long for the love and sympathy of man, persevere in this exile?” (Shelley 1818, 120). In addition, Victor’s hostility towards the creature does not instantly disappear. Moreover, he is still too absorbed by the creature’s physical appearance to really listen to its words. This can be seen in the following passage: “His words had a strange effect upon me. I compassionated him, and sometimes felt a wish to console him; but when I looked upon him, when I saw the filthy mass that moved and talked, my heart sickened, and my feelings were altered to those of horror and hatred” (Shelley 1818, 121). However, the kindled compassion leads Victor to try to see past the exterior and starts to reason with the creature, e.g., “[...] but have you not already shewn a degree of malice that should reasonably make me distrust you?” (Shelley 1818, 121). Eventually Victor can be convinced, that the creature is not all bad, e.g. “I thought of the promise of virtues which he had displayed on the opening of his existence [...]” (Shelley 1818, 121). Finally, after listening to the creature’s request and arguments, and **reflecting** on the possible consequences of his decision, Victor decides to accept the request. The fact that Victor ultimately

gives in to the request shows that he feels compassion and responsibility towards the creature, but the fact that he is very hesitant and argues with the creature allude to Victor's more cautious and reflective side.

RR

Similar to Passage 1, Victor does not appear as eloquent as in the original, as many difficult words and sentences were replaced for easier ones in the linguistic simplification. However, in terms of Victor's emotions and what triggers them, the two versions are similar. In the beginning Victor is also rather **hostile** towards the creature by referring to it as "monster" (Shelley 2012, 55). However, in addition to Victor's hostility he directly characterises himself to be "**shocked**" after listening to the creature's story, which is an additional emotion that is not present in the original (cf. Shelley 2012, 55). Although Victor is also dismissive of the creature's request in the beginning, he also quickly feels **compassionate**. For in this version, too, Victor directly acknowledges, that the words touched his heart and that "he [the creature] had made a good argument" (Shelley 2012, 56), which strongly resembles the developments in passage 1. In addition, Victor also acknowledges that he is dealing with a "sensitive creature" (Shelley 2012, 56). In addition, just like in OR, once Victor realises that the creature is a sentient being, he starts to feel responsible for its happiness, as shown in the following sentence: "I must give him a little happiness if I can" (Shelley 2012, 56). However, unlike in the OR, Victor never mentions the creature's physical appearance in this version, which leads to the omission of Victor's struggle to look past the creature's appearance and see it for its character. In this version of the passage Victor is also **cautious**, although not as much as in OR. Victor also does not automatically agree to the request but confronts the creature with arguments that would undermine its request, e.g., "But you have already done bad things" (Shelley 2012, 56). However, the back and forth of questions and answers between the creature and Victor is heavily abbreviated in comparison to the original. Eventually Victor can also be convinced to grant the creature's request. However, Victor is much less **reflective** in this version. Whilst he does reflect on the consequences of his actions, Victor blames the De Lacey family for the creature's malevolence and never mentions his own behaviour as the cause for the creature's behaviours. Whilst the original also does not explicitly discuss that Victor feels responsible for leaving the creature alone and enabling any following events, this version explicitly shifts

the blame unto the De Lacey family. However, overall, even though many passages were changed and abbreviated in this version, Victor's emotions and the development of the emotions remain similar to the original.

MR

In this version, Victor is vastly different from the original. Firstly, in terms of his speech Victor is not as eloquent as in the original, which can be attributed to the lexical simplifications in chapter "3.2 Passage 2: The creature's request". Regarding Victor's emotions he is mainly **hostile** towards the creature. This can be seen in his speech, as he calls the creature a "Monster", as well as his continuous decline of the request (cf. Shelley 2005, 32). His hostility is reinforced, as Victor shows no compassion for the creature in the entire passage. MR's Victor does not attribute any positive characteristics to the creature. This Victor is also less **cautious** than the previous ones. Whilst he does question whether the creature can truly become harmless, he does so very briefly and drops the argument very quickly. In the previous two versions, however, Victor voices his doubts concerning the creature's honesty and will to honour the deal repeatedly. In this version of the passage, Victor is also **reflective**, although for an entirely different reason. In this version, Victor takes the blame for the creature's behaviour, as can be seen in the following statement: "My wickedness has brought terror and unhappiness to the world. I made you. Now I must find the strength to kill you" (Shelley 2005, 32). Whereas in the other two versions Victor was reflective, because he carefully weighed the advantages and disadvantages of granting the creature's request, in this one Victor seems to understand that his behaviour is the origin of the creature's wickedness.

SFB

This Victor is entirely different from the other versions. Solely based on the literary material, everything the reader can infer, is that Victor denies the request of the creature. This varies strongly from the previous editions. Not only do we not get any insight into why Victor makes this decision or any emotions for that matter, but in the other versions Victor initially agrees to the request. However, unlike the SFB Victor of Passage 1, this one speaks English, albeit remarkably simple one, e.g. "No more monster!" (Shelley 2021, 16). As already mentioned in chapter "3.2 Passage 2: The creature's request" this version solely focuses

on the fact that Victor refuses the request and thus largely changes the content of the original.

The creature

OR

Its looks are only explicitly mentioned briefly by Victor and still depict the creature as an ugly sight, e.g., “[...] when I saw the filthy mass that moved and talked, my heart sickened, [...]” (Shelley 1818, 121). In a stark contrast to the first passage, the creature’s character and emotions are the focus of this passage.

The creature’s **intelligence** is indirectly depicted in the creature’s speech. Though it is visually depicted as ugly, it uses an extremely broad vocabulary and complex sentences to convey its thoughts. The creature’s intelligence is further highlighted by the fact that it displays cognitive and affective empathy and is thus able to understand other people’s emotions and motifs. For example, the creature understands what Victor thinks and anticipates his actions, e.g. “You my creator, would tear me to pieces, and triumph” (Shelley 1818, 119) or “Pitiless as you have been towards me, I now see compassion in your eyes; [...]” (Shelley 1818, 120). Furthermore, it constantly tries to reason with Victor and appeal to his emotions instead of threatening him directly, which is proof that the creature does not brainlessly jump into the argument but that it came prepared and displays great control of his arguments and emotions. However, the creature does threaten Victor on occasion, in which the readers can see the creature’s **violent** side. For example, on one occasion, the creature threatens Victor with his destruction, should he not agree to its request, or it threatens to harm all humans (cf. Shelley 1818, 119).

The creature is also very **reasonable**. Instead of constantly threatening Victor, it tries to provide arguments which convince Victor to agree to its request. These arguments are also well thought out, as the creature knows exactly what it has to say to make Victor agree to the request, e.g., that it would live far away from humans. Even in moments where the creature grows frustrated with Victor, e.g., “how inconsistent are your feelings!” (Shelley 1818, 121) it still tries to stay level-headed and reason with him.

Lastly, the creature is very **lonely** and **desperate**. Throughout the entire passage, it tries to convince Victor to create a companion. We can see right in the beginning that the

creature longs to be understood and enjoy the pleasantries of companionship, e.g., “[...] with whom I can live in the interchange of those sympathies necessary for my being” (Shelley 1818, 118). The creature, in fact, reveals that it never experienced any love from another being, which is why it is so lonely and desperate for another being (cf. Shelley 1818, 119). The creature must also be very desperate to go to Victor with its request. The creature hates Victor, as it calls him its “arch-enemy” and swears “unextinguishable hatred” on him, if he does not agree to its request (cf. Shelley 1818, 119). However, the creature is also aware of the fact that Victor is the only one who can grant it its wish, e.g. “This alone you can do; and I demand it of you as a right which you must not refuse” (Shelley 1818, 118). This must be frustrating for the creature, as it is dependent on the man it hates.

The creature is especially interesting, as it combines many opposing emotions. Someone who is violent would not automatically be called reasonable as well. This paradox co-existing of contradicting emotions highlights the complexity of the creature’s character, as well as its desperation. Whilst the creature is willing to forgive Victor for abandoning it, if he accepts the request, it is also willing to become what Victor fears it to be if its only chance for happiness is not granted. The creature is smart, in the way it articulates itself but violent in what it threatens, reasonable in voicing its demands but desperate for it becoming reality.

RR

Unlike OR, RR does not discuss the creature’s physical appearance at any point. However, in terms of its character the creature is similar to the one in OR. The creature’s **intelligence** is also indirectly depicted by its speech, albeit not as much as in OR. Whilst it uses English to convey its thoughts, the words and grammar structure it chooses are not as complex as in OR. Also, just like in the original, the creature also tries to reason with Victor rather than threaten him, thus choosing a calm and smart way to convince Victor of its request. In fact, unlike in OR, the creature never directly threatens Victor, thus appearing less violent than in OR. However, the creature does briefly hint at its **violent** nature in the sentence: “I will give them reasons to fear me!” (Shelley 2012, 56). However, even though the creature is violent, it is also **reasonable** in its request. The request itself, a companion to be less lonely, as well as the arguments and promises the creature presents, e.g., leaving Europe, are reasonable and well thought out. Lastly, just like in OR, the creature is also **lonely** and

desperate. Readers also learn in this passage that the creature is unhappy because no human will love it, highlighting the creature's loneliness. In addition, the fact that the creature is agreeing to Victor's tough terms, e.g., leaving Europe for South America after receiving its companion, shows how desperate the creature is and how much it yearns for companionship. In summary, although the creature feels the same emotions, the literary elaboration of the emotions is much weaker than in the original as there are less scenes that hint towards the emotions. This could obstruct readers from finding these emotions, as they have much less literary material that alludes to them.

MR

Unlike RR, but similar to OR, this version briefly describes what the creature looks like. In fact, it directly characterises itself as "ugly" and "terrible" (Shelley 2005, 32). With regard to the creature's other characteristics, it strongly resembles the other two versions. First of all, the creature could also be called **intelligent**, as it learnt human language and can convey its thoughts in simple sentences, although this version of the creature is significantly less smart than the ones of the previous two versions, due to its simple lexis and sentence structure. Just like RR, this creature is less violent than the one in OR. In fact, it appears to be the most harmless one. In this version it never directly threatens Victor or other humans. The only hint at the creature's violent potential is when Victor refers to its past by saying: "You have brought unhappiness to the world" (Shelley 2005, 32). However, "unhappiness" is a very vague term and conceals the creature's violent nature from the original, in which the creature was blamed for actions with malicious intent. Just like in the other two versions, this creature is also **reasonable**. The request itself, a female companion to battle its loneliness is a reasonable one and throughout the entire discussion the creature does not resort to threats but remains calm and objective. The creature's **loneliness** and **desperation** are only very briefly hinted at in this version, for the creature only mentions in one sentence, that no human will love it and that it is desperate enough to agree to Victor's terms of the deal (cf. Shelley 2005, 32). However, similar to RR, even though the creature experiences the same emotions, they are much less obvious in this version, as the literary material was heavily abbreviated. Due to the grading of the graded readers, many passages that hinted towards the emotions of the creature were omitted, thus making it harder for readers to engage with the characters emotionally.

SFB

This version of the creature is vastly different. Only based on the text, the creature does not share any physical characteristics or emotions with the previous versions. In fact, in this version the reader can only learn two things about the creature. Firstly, the creature lacks any language. Whereas in the original it is able to use the English language like a very educated human being, in this version the creature can only voice sounds, e.g., “Grrr?” (Shelley 2021, 15). In fact, the entire request is summarised in this simple statement, thus leaving out any of the previously established characteristics, such as violence or desperation. The only physical description of the creature we get is by Victor, who still calls it a “monster” (Shelley 2021, 16).

4.3 Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth

The respective passages, along with the linguistic analysis, can be found in appendix “8.9 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 OR”, “8.10 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 RR” and “8.11 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 MR”.

Victor

OR

As in the previous passages, Victor’s speech reveals that he is a very **eloquent** and **observant** man. In terms of the latter, he does not only describe what he sees in detail, but also what he feels, e.g., “[...] I could feel the blood trickling in my veins [...]” (Shelley 1818, 165). The prevalent emotion that Victor experiences in this short passage is **shock**. This can be observed indirectly in various instances, for example in his speech and use of interjections, e.g. “Great God!” (Shelley 1818, 165) or that he loses consciousness after seeing Elizabeth’s lifeless body.

RR

Just like in the previous two passages, RR matches OR’s depiction of Victor very well. Victor is also very **observant** of his surroundings, as he describes Elizabeth’s body in great detail (cf. Shelley 2012, 75). However, also similar to the other passages, Victor does not use the same sophisticated vocabulary and thus appears less eloquent. In terms of

emotion, the prevalence of **shock** cannot be denied in this passage as well. Victor's shock is solely indirectly depicted, e.g., in his speech "Why did I not fall dead then?" (Shelley 2012, 75), or his actions, for example when he freezes out of shock after hearing Elizabeth's scream.

MR

Just like in OR and RR Victor is an **observant** man, albeit not as much as in the previous versions, as seen in his description of Elizabeth's body. Also, similar to the previous sub-chapters, Victor does not appear as eloquent as in OR, as his language was heavily simplified in the linguistic simplification. Regarding his emotions it can also be stated that the prevalent one which Victor experiences in this passage is **shock**, although it is difficult to make out. The only two hints there are for Victor's shock are that he classifies Elizabeth's scream as "terrible", thus indicating that something is wrong, and him rushing to her door, with "rushing" indicating that Victor must be stressed.

The creature

Throughout all three versions, the creature is depicted the same. In neither version does the creature appear physically. However, the readers do get an insight into the creature's **violent** and **vengeful** nature through the murder of Elizabeth. Elizabeth is an innocent person, and the creature brutally killed her on her wedding night. The biggest difference between the three versions is that MR specifies how the creature killed Elizabeth. The other versions mention Elizabeth's cause of death as well, though at another point in the plot.

4.4 Summary

In summary, the following points can be made after the literary analysis. The linguistic analysis has consequences for the literary meaning of the material on several levels. On the language level, it can be noted that all characters use simpler language. This is only secondary with regard to the focus on *Empathy* in the research question, but the characters all talk differently between the versions, due to the lexical and grammatical simplification of the text, which alters how smart or eloquent they are indirectly characterised as. With

respect to the focus on *Empathy*, however, the emotions of the characters are much more important. Most emotions remain the same between the different versions, with the exception of SFB, where no real emotions are present at all. With regard to the other versions, most of the emotions overlap between the different versions, although there are some differences between the original and the graded readers. For example, some emotions are dropped altogether, e.g., “disappointed” in OR disappears in MR, and others change slightly, e.g., “anxious” in OR turns into “excited” in MR. In all versions, however, it can be observed that the more similar the CEFR language level of a graded reader is to the original, the more similar the emotions occurring in them are. Of course, this may be a coincidence, which only occurs in this specific novel and these graded readers, so this is not a causal case, but an observation. Moreover, it is interesting to note that it is much more difficult to spot emotions in the graded readers. This is because the material has been abbreviated and less text can be spent on elaborating different emotions.

5 Practical transfer into a classroom project

In chapter “4.4 Summary”, it was revealed that the emotions of the characters are much less visible in graded readers than in the original. Since one of the goals of the master thesis is to teach empathy through literature, the loss of emotions must be counteracted by the classroom activities. In the following chapter, the findings from the theoretical discussion and the linguistic and literary analysis lead to the elaboration of exemplary classroom-activities. At the beginning in chapter “5.1 Task-design” the specific task design that underlines the individual activities is presented. In chapter “5.2 Classroom framework” the classroom framework, for which the tasks are designed for, is defined.

The following sub-chapters follow a fixed structure. At the beginning, the individual tasks, which have been specifically designed for this master thesis and have not been taken or adapted from another source, will be embedded in a lesson plan which spans the entire text, followed by the elaboration of concrete learning objectives. The learning objectives are formulated with regard to the competences of curriculum 21 and the second research question. After that, the designed tasks are presented in their entirety, followed by a description and commentary of the respective tasks, regarding how they support pupils in achieving the learning objectives and how they acknowledge heterogeneity and motivation.

Finally, a proposal is presented on how the specific task and pupils' learning progress can be evaluated in class.

5.1 Task-design

In chapter "2.3.2 Heterogeneity" it was mentioned that TBLT is a great teaching approach to accommodate heterogeneity. However, considering the previous theory it becomes evident that TBLT is not only a recommended teaching approach regarding heterogeneity, but it also lends itself to accommodate the needs of the competences *Reading*, *Dialogic speaking* and *Empathy*. In the following sub-chapters TBLT and *Scaffolding Reading* will be presented.

5.1.1 Task-based language teaching

What is a task?

Before going into more detail about what exactly TBLT is, the term "task" needs to be clarified. In terms of TBLT, a task is a work plan, which refers to tasks with clearly defined communicative goals (Ellis 2003, 10 – 11). Further, task-as-a-workplan follows a strict cycle, which is visualised in figure 5.

Figure 5: Task-as-a-workplan TBLT (Grimm et al. 2015, 70)

Looking at figure 5, it becomes evident that TBLT tasks, just like dialogic speaking and

reading comprehension, consist of the three phases of pre-, while- and post-activity. In this case, the pre-activity also serves to prepare learners for the while-activity, while the post-activity can be used to reflect on learning progresses or to further elaborate on the results of the while-activities.

Ellis goes on to say that tasks, as defined by the TBLT, must have five other characteristics.

These are as follows:

- Tasks must focus on meaning rather than form.
- Tasks must involve real-world processes. Ellis gives two examples: asking and answering questions and negotiating opinions (Ellis 2003, 10).
- The four language skills (speaking, listening, etc.) must be used to accomplish the task.
- Tasks must involve cognitive processes (e.g., selecting, classifying, organising, inferring, or evaluating information).
- Tasks must have a clear communicative aim.

(Ellis 2003, 9 – 10)

What is TBLT?

As already mentioned, TBLT is a teaching approach that encourages learners to use language to communicate, solve problems and achieve goals that are not primarily a linguistic one but a meaning-focused one (Grimm et al. 2015, 69). Unlike other communicative approaches (e.g., communicative language teaching) TBLT focuses more on comprehension- and meaning-focused tasks rather than tasks in which pupils have to learn specific forms (Grimm et al. 2015, 69). The pupils are thus viewed as social agents and encouraged to use language to achieve a specific communicative goal. As TBLT focuses a lot on communicative learner output, it makes sense that teamwork takes a crucial part in TBLT task-designs (Grimm et al. 2015, 70). Ellis argues in favour of teamwork in TBLT, as it offers many advantages. For example, the quantity of speech, motivation, and enjoyment increase (Ellis 2003, 267). Teachers, however, need to be aware, that open proceeding of teamwork may lead to poor results, especially if the tasks are too challenging and scaffolding is insufficient (Grimm et al. 2015, 70). The importance of scaffolding in particular is emphasised by theory. For example, Nunan describes that material and activities need to be well structured to support pupils in their learning (2004, 34). Scaffolding also includes

ensuring that tasks are meaningfully sequenced. Nunan describes that receptive language skills are to be practiced first before working on productive ones (2004, 35-36).

However, TBLT is also subject to criticism. For example, experts criticise that TBLT focuses too little on vocabulary and grammar and neglects accuracy (Grimm et al. 2015, 71). Some of the criticism can be refuted. As Ellis argues, focus on form can be integrated through consciousness-raising activities or clarifying feedback (2012, 267 – 268). In addition, relevant vocabulary or grammar can be focused on during the different phases in the TBLT task-cycle. Nunan additionally emphasises that grammar and vocabulary can be integrated into the tasks and learners must be provided with repeated practice opportunities (Nunan 2003, 36-37). However, despite all criticism, Vogt argues that TBLT is a very valuable teaching method for heterogeneous classes, as it allows for holistic, cooperative, and creative learning, due to its open-ended assignments and communicative focus (2017, 239).

Designing a TBLT task

Before designing a TBLT task, teachers need to define a specific learning objective (Nunan 2004, 41). Having a specific learning objective, however, is not only a key component of teaching with TBLT, but benefits learning in general, for example reading (Grabe and Stoller 2011, 143). As previously established, the objectives of TBLT tasks can focus on both linguistic skills as well as on meaning (Grimm et al. 2015, 69 – 70; Nunan 2003, 36 – 37). The specific tasks are then designed according to the TBLT task-cycle (see figure 5). Nunan compiled a list that classifies different possible task types for TBLT teaching into five categories: cognitive, interpersonal, linguistic, affective, and creative (Nunan 2004, 59). Figure 6 shows a selection of the strategies presented by Nunan.

Cognitive

Classifying

Putting things that are similar together in groups.

Predicting

Predicting what is to come in the learning process.
Example: Look at the unit title and objectives and predict what will be learned.

Taking notes

Writing down the important information in a text in your own words.

Discriminating

Distinguishing between the main idea and supporting information.

Interpersonal Co-operating	Sharing ideas and learning with other students.
Linguistic Conversational patterns	Using expressions to start conversations and keep them going.
Practicing	Doing controlled exercises to improve knowledge and skills.
Using context	Using the surrounding context to guess the meaning of an unknown word, phrase, or concept.
Summarising	Picking out and presenting the major points in a text in summary form.
Affective Personalising	Learners share their own opinions, feelings and ideas about a subject.
Self-evaluating	Thinking about how well you did on a learning task.
Reflecting	Thinking about ways you learn best.
Creative Brainstorming	Thinking of as many new words and ideas as one can.

Figure 6: Task types. Adapted from Nunan 2004, 59 - 61.

Ellis raises the point, that teachers also need to define, how the outcome of the pupils should be presented, e.g. oral or written (2004, 217).

Assessment in TBLT

Assessment in TBLT can focus on both the linguistic qualities of the learners' output as well as their performance. Both can be assessed summatively and formatively (Ellis 2003, 283 ff.). Ellis mentions in this context the distinction between system-referenced assessments, which focus on language proficiency in relation to the four language skills, and performance-referenced assessments, which focuses on how well the pupils fulfil a communicative goal (2003, 283 – 285). However, Ellis specifies, that linguistic proficiency also influences the results of performance-referenced tests (2003, 289). When it comes to assessing pupils' output, TBLT faces challenges. As it highly focuses on output and the subjective response of learners to a communicative problem, it is often difficult to measure objective results, e.g., the usage of correct tense (Grimm et al. 2015, 72). While objective results need to be assessed as well, the pupils' performance of the tasks also needs to be

assessed.

For this classroom project pupils will receive performance-referenced formative assessments. This is because the focus of the learning objectives (see chapter “5.3 Passage 1: The birth of the creature”, “5.4 Passage 2: The creature’s request” and “5.5 Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth”) is primarily on meaning. Also, pupils will only receive formative feedback to support them in their learning. Ellis describes that formative performance-focused assessments can be done, for example, in the form of learner self-assessments or through explicit feedback from the teacher regarding task fulfilment (2003, 312 – 313).

Why choose TBLT for this classroom project?

TBLT overlaps perfectly with the targeted competence specific methodology of *Reading*, *Dialogic Speaking*, and *Empathy*. First of all, TBLT focuses on meaning-focused output. The focus on meaning-focused in- and output aligns with the theory presented in chapter “2.1 Graded readers”, in which Nation and Deweerdt describe that graded readers are particularly well suited for meaning-focused approaches (Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 49 ff.). Moreover, it was also mentioned in chapter “2.2.3 Dialogic Speaking” that the focus of pupils' speech production should be on meaning and not on accuracy (Grimm et al. 2015, 130 - 131), thus TBLT's focus on meaning synergises well with the already presented theory. Secondly, teamwork plays an influential role in TBLT (Grimm et al. 2015, 70). Teamwork also plays a key role in reading methodology, as can be seen in the multi-level model of reading (see figure 1) and dialogic speaking methodology (see chapter "2.2.3 Dialogic speaking"), which is why TBLT also synergises well with the different language skill specific methodology here. Thirdly, TBLT is a great teaching approach for heterogeneous classes. As described by Vogt, TBLT is especially well suited for heterogeneous classes, as it allows for holistic and open-ended learning, as well as teamwork (2017, 239), thus matching with the focus in chapter “2.3.2 Heterogeneity”. Lastly, TBLT is also suitable for fostering empathy skills. Since TBLT supports holistic learning (Vogt 2017, 239), not only the four language skills are promoted, but the pupils can also work on their personal and social competences. Furthermore, figure 6 effectively suggests affective learning as a task type alongside traditional types such as linguistic ones for TBLT. Furthermore, since TBLT tasks can also be open-ended (Vogt 2017, 239) it allows pupils flexibility in their answers. This flexibility is needed when pupils are expected to share their opinions on the characters in

Frankenstein.

5.1.2 Scaffolding reading

In the previous chapters it was mentioned how important the *Scaffolding of reading* is. Neugebauer (2008) provides concrete guidance on how this can be implemented in practice. She describes that readers can be supported in their reading by receiving concrete work assignments which help them to understand the text (Neugebauer 2008, 2). She divides these tasks into three phases 1) pre-reading texts, 2) comprehending texts, and 3) interpreting texts (Neugebauer 2008, 3), which is strongly reminiscent of the pre-, while-, and post-reading activities from chapter "2.2.1 Reading".

The first phase, 1) Pre-reading texts, suggests content-based pre-reading (e.g., talking about pictures of the text or collecting information about the topic) and lexical pre-reading (e.g., looking up unknown words) (Neugebauer 2008, 5). Phase 2) Understanding texts, suggests different types of tasks to support *Reading for gist*, *Scanning*, and *Reading for detailed understanding* (Neugebauer 2008, 5). The last phase 3) Interpreting texts, suggests, for example, interpreting texts and formulating own opinions (Neugebauer 2008, 5). The exact list of assignments can be found in appendix "8.12 Scaffolding of reading".

5.1.3 Pre-, while- and post-activity

In the previous chapters "2.2.2 Reading", "2.2.3 Dialogic speaking", as well as in "5.1.1 TBLT" and "5.1.2 Scaffolding of reading", pre-, while- and post-activities were repeatedly mentioned. It is important to specify here that the distinct phases, regarding the individual language skills or the TBLT task-cycle in general, can complement or be combined with each other. For example, a pre-speaking activity can be a post-reading activity. In a post-reading activity pupils can interpret a text and write down their ideas. This can also be a pre-speaking activity, as pupils prepare what they are going to talk about, in which case it is equivalent to Bygate's conceptualising phase (cf. Bygate 2011, 419 - 420). The pre-, while-, and post-activities of the TBLT task-cycle can also frame the phases of the individual language skills. For example, in the pre-activity of the TBLT task-cycle, the learning goals can be introduced. This has nothing directly to do with the work on the language skills, but frames the activities by giving them context.

5.2 Classroom framework

The following tasks were designed for a secondary school 2 A/B/C class. The decision was made in order to present the potential of graded readers especially in heterogeneous teaching and learning settings. The pupils' learning is strongly driven by the tasks. This decision stems from the fact that this is a TBLT project.

With regard to the aspect of "accessibility", two points can already be established that overarch the entire classroom project. In order for the pupils to access the text at all, the text must appeal to them. This is accomplished by making the text linguistically manageable and topically interesting (Grimm et al. 2015, 190). Due to the popularity of *Frankenstein* to this day, it is assumed that the material is exciting to young people, thus appealing to their intrinsic motivation to engage with the text. The popularity of the characters, however, does not only aid pupils in accessing the material, but also assists them in developing empathy, as Döring argues that interesting and likeable characters are crucial for experiencing empathy (2013, 297). Regarding the accommodation of the Linguistic Threshold graded readers are a valuable resource. As established in chapter "2.2.2 Reading", pupils face additional challenges when engaging with foreign language material, as they are presented with foreign language related lexical and syntactical challenges (Grimm et al. 2015, 123). In this regard the choice of material already supports the pupils in overcoming these challenges. Graded readers are already simplified in terms of levels 5) amount of material and 6) difficulty by Luder (2019, 21), thus enabling pupils to engage with material that aligns with their language proficiency. Additionally, graded readers are a good choice for fostering the selected competences. As discussed by Nation and Deweerdt, graded readers are a valuable teaching resource for meaning-focused approaches (2001, 49 ff.). The learning objectives for this classroom project all revolve around meaning-focused output by the pupils, hence why the choice of material is suitable. In addition, the competences *Reading* and *Dialogic speaking* also value comprehension-focused teaching approaches (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 130 – 131; Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 15 ff.), which aligns great with the advantages of language learning with graded readers (cf. Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 56 – 57).

In the classroom project, the pupils work with the versions of RR and MR. As shown in chapter "3 Linguistic analysis," the RR version is more difficult than the MR version

linguistically. This also corresponds with the CEFR levels given by the publishers. In the linguistic analysis it was shown that the sentence structure and vocabulary in MR are simpler, which is why this version is more suitable to pupils who experience greater linguistic difficulties. The SFB version is much too simple for the designated class, and the pupils do not really get to know the story, nor can they work on their linguistic competences.

5.3 Worksheets for Passage 1: The birth of the creature

The corresponding passages can be found in appendix “8.13 Passage 1 RR” and “8.14 Passage 1 MR”.

Embedment in the lesson plan

Before the pupils encounter this passage, they have already read the graded readers up to this point. Therefore, pupils already know who Victor is and what his goal is. In addition, the pupils have also worked out how much time Victor has spent on the creature and how important the creature’s animation is to him, so that they can understand his reaction to the creature better.

Learning Objectives

In the literary analysis it was discussed that this scene is important for several reasons for the further course of the story. On the one hand, the creature comes to life in the scene, and on the other hand, moreover, Victor's fear, shame, and hatred of the creature begin at this moment. The following learning objectives were formulated with this in mind. The learning objectives for this passage are rather easy and focus on aspects of the story that the pupils can directly observe. LO1, LO2, LO3 and LO5 focus on the pupils’ reading skills, as they have to use the different reading strategies *Reading for gist* and *Scanning*. At this point of the classroom project the reading skills of the pupils are heavily focused on and fostered to prepare them for more difficult tasks in the upcoming passages, where they have to use the information in the text more creatively. LO4 focuses on the pupils’ speaking skills, and lastly LO5 and LO6* foster the pupils’ affective empathy. The complete list of learning objectives can be found in table 5 below.

The pupils can...		
basal	LO1	...determine what the creature looks like by highlighting the respective passage in the book.
	LO2	... answer general questions about the content in writing simple sentences.
	LO3	... summarise the entire passage using full sentences.
	LO4	... verbally share their personal opinion on why they think Victor reacted towards the creature so negatively.
	LO5	... identify text passages that hints at one of Victor's emotions (affective empathy) and copy it onto a padlet.
advanced	LO6*	...take on the perspective of the creature (affective empathy) and demonstrate this by verbally discussing their ideas with a partner.

Table 5: Learning objectives of Passage 1

Tasks

The worksheets for RR and MR are almost identical. The only differences are the page numbers, as well as task 3, for which pupils have to translate words which appear in their respective editions. The worksheets can be found in figure 7 and figure 8.

Richmond Reader

The birth of the creature

For the following passage you have to follow the worksheet very closely. It tells you exactly what to do and when to do it.

The icons on the lefthand side help you navigate through the worksheet.

= information

 = reading

= writing

= thinking

 = speaking

Follow the instructions on the worksheet as you read the passage. All * exercises are mandatory, ** exercises are optional.

Learning objectives:

- I can read the passage and use the information to answer questions.
- I can understand Victor's emotions.
- I can imagine what the creature feels like. **

1.* Have a look at the picture on page 20. What do you think is going to happen in the chapter? Write down your assumptions in 1 – 2 sentences.

2.* Circle the 3 adjectives that you think describe Victor's reaction the best.

happy confused

sad angry mad

scared excited

horrified anxious

disappointed desperate

disgusted

3.* Look the following words up online and write down the translation.

Lifeless (adj):

Wildly (adv):

Enormous (adj):

Horrible (adj):

Suddenly (adv):

7.* What do you think Victor feels like after that you have read the passage? Go back to task 2 and circle Victor's emotions in a different colour.

8.** Why does Victor feel that way? Write your ideas onto the following lines using key words.

9.* If you were Victor, would you have reacted the same way?

Yes

No

10.** Explain your decision on the following lines using full sentences.

11.* If you were the creature, how would you have felt when Victor ran away? Write suitable adjectives in the bubbles.

12.** Why do you think the creature would feel that way? Write your answers on the following lines using full sentences.

13.* Share your answers from task 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 with your partner. Use the sentence starters in the box below.

Helpful language:

“What is your answer for task...?”

“Why do you think that...?”

“I think that, because...”

“Can you explain your answer to me?”

“Do you agree/disagree with me?”

14.* In pairs, focus on one emotion that Victor feels (see task 7) and write it on a new note on the online padlet. Go back to the graded reader and copy the sentence that supports your answer onto the note as well and post it online.

15.* Look at your classmates notes on the padlet. Do you agree with their contributions? Discuss your opinions with your partner.

Figure 7: Worksheet Passage 1, RR

Macmillan Reader

The birth of the creature

For the following passage you have to follow the worksheet very closely. It tells you exactly what to do and when to do it.

The icons on the lefthand side help you navigate through the worksheet.

= information

 = reading

 = writing

= thinking

 = speaking

Follow the instructions on the worksheet as you read the passage. All * exercises are mandatory, ** exercises are optional.

Learning objectives:

- I can read the passage and use the information to answer questions.
- I can understand Victor's emotions.
- I can imagine what the creature feels like. **

1.* Have a look at the picture on page 16 - 17. What do you think is going to happen in the chapter? Write down your assumptions in 1 – 2 sentences.

2.* Circle the 3 adjectives that you think describe Victor's reaction the best.

happy confused

sad angry mad

scared excited

 horrified anxious

disappointed desperate

 disgusted

3.* Look the following words up online and write down the translation.

Alive (adj):

Wrinkled (adj):

Terrible (adj):

7.* What do you think Victor feels like after that you have read the passage? Go back to task 2 and circle Victor's emotions in a different colour.

8.** Why does Victor feel that way? Write your ideas onto the following lines using key words.

9.* If you were Victor, would you have reacted the same way?

Yes

No

10.** Explain your decision on the following lines using full sentences.

11.* If you were the creature, how would you have felt when Victor ran away? Write suitable adjectives in the bubbles.

12.** Why do you think the creature would feel that way? Write your answers on the following lines using full sentences.

13.* Share your answers from task 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 with your partner. Use the sentence starters in the box below.

Helpful language:

“What is your answer for task...?”

“Why do you think that...?”

“I think that, because...”

“Can you explain your answer to me?”

“Do you agree/disagree with me?”

14.* In pairs, focus on one emotion that Victor feels (see task 7) and write it on a new note on the online padlet. Go back to the graded reader and copy the sentence that supports your answer onto the note as well and post it online.

15.* Look at your classmates notes on the padlet. Do you agree with their contributions? Discuss your opinions with your partner.

Figure 8: Worksheet Passage 1, MR

Commenting on tasks

TBLT and Scaffolding

The worksheet incorporates the theory of TBLT in many ways. First of all, the learning objectives are meaning-focused. With this regard, pupils have to use language to communicate with each other (e.g., task 13) or to solve problems (e.g., task 12), hence the basic idea of TBLT, namely that one should use language to achieve a communicative goal and focus on meaning rather than on accuracy, is taken into account (Grimm et al. 2015, 69). Moreover, the learning objectives are clearly defined and transparent to the pupils.

This allows them to understand their own learning which makes it more meaningful and frames the upcoming activities (Nunan 2004, 41; Dörnyei 2001, 81 – 82; Grimm et al. 2015, 70). In terms of the structure, the worksheet provides pupils with many scaffolds and clear instructions which according to Nunan is indispensable for TBLT (2004, 34). With regard to scaffolds, the whole reading process is clearly structured in the pre-, while-, and post-reading phases by means of Neugebauer's (2008) *Scaffolding of reading*. Furthermore, regarding the clarity of the instructions the pupils receive visual support, e.g., in the form of pictograms. Pupils also receive clear assignments that tell them exactly what and how to do it (e.g., “highlight the passages” or “write down your answer using full sentences”). The scaffolding that accompanies each task ensures the quality of the pupils' output, as open-ended assignments and teamwork without sufficient scaffolding may lead to poor results (Grimm et a. 2015, 70).

With regard to teamwork, which is fundamental for TBLT, pupils are encouraged to cooperate with each other by means of dialogic speaking (Grimm et al. 2015, 70). The internal sequencing of the tasks is also based on the theory of TBLT. Nunan recommends that receptive skills need to be practiced first before pupils can work on their productive ones (2004, 35 - 36). This approach can be seen in the worksheet, as the pupils first work on the text thoroughly before they use their insights to cooperate verbally. Despite the criticism that TBLT focuses too little on form, the worksheet promotes lexical learning, even if only marginally. In this regard, pupils encounter vocabulary and language chunks in task 3 and 13, which they need use for task completion. The worksheet also uses many different task types, as defined by Nunan (see figure 6), as the pupils work with the strategies *Predicting*, *Taking notes*, *Discriminating*, *Co-operating*, *Summarising*, *Conversational patterns*, and *Personalising* (Nunan 2004, 59 - 61).

Overall, the individual tasks are framed by the task-cycle of TBLT (see figure 5). In the pre-phase the task is framed, e.g., through the learning objectives. In the while-phase the pupils read and analyse the text, followed by the post-phase, in which the pupils share their answers on the padlet. This allows pupils to evaluate their own answers and assess their own learning.

Accessibility

The choice of the TBLT approach already simplifies the access to the text with regard to

the dimensions of motivation and heterogeneity. For example, Ellis argues that the higher number of communicative activities in TBLT, e.g., tasks 13 and 15, already increases motivation (2003, 267), and, Brandt adds, that clear instructions and scaffolds facilitate access to the learning material (2002, 293). The tasks were also created in a way that they are solvable for the pupils, since unsolvable tasks strongly lower motivation (Dörnyei 2001, 75). This is achieved by a mixture of different methods. On the one hand, the assignments are clearly formulated because of Neugebauer's (2008) *Scaffolding of reading*, which enables pupils better access to the material and thus makes the tasks more solvable on an instructional level. In addition, the pupils receive support for more difficult tasks in order to lower the linguistic hurdles, e.g., in tasks 2 and 13. In task 2 pupils do not have to search for adjectives because of the lexical support and can therefore concentrate on the content, and thus the meaning. This lowers the Linguistic Threshold of the task (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 123). This linguistic relief is especially important, as Berger and Pfiffner argue for the language proficiency of the readers to be especially influential on their learning and must be accommodated (2018, 13 – 15). If the linguistic requirements are too big, pupils cannot access the material and therefore cannot learn. However, the tasks cannot be too easy and still need to be challenging, as too easy tasks also have a negative impact on motivation (Dörnyei 2001, 76).

Figure 9: Bloom's Taxonomy (adapted from Bloom 1973, 24 ff.)

In this worksheet, this is achieved by having the tasks accommodate various levels of Bloom's Taxonomy (see figure 9). Task 6, for example, is hierarchically low, since the

pupils only have to summarise information, which corresponds to the level *Understand*. In contrast, in task 12 the pupils have to justify their answer, which is why it is hierarchically placed on a higher level, *Evaluate*. Literature, in fact, lends itself to work on hierarchically more challenging tasks, as the material offers opportunities to think critically about the material and oneself, e.g., by analysing and questioning characters (cf. Naji et al. 2019, 7; Okyar 2021, 333).

Dörnyei further reveals that a high variety of task types, language skills and organisational forms increases motivation (2001, 74). The variety is omnipresent in the worksheet. For example, the task types keep changing (e.g., task 1 interpreting pictures, task 3 translating words, task 5 evaluating statements, task 8 interpreting information, etc.), as do the language skills, as the pupils switch back and forth between reading, speaking, and writing. Only the variety of organisational forms is little represented in this worksheet, since the pupils almost exclusively work individually and switch to pair work only towards the end. Some tasks also meet Dörnyei's requirement that motivating tasks must be open-ended and allow for multiple possible answers (2001, 76). Task 12, for example, has no correct answer. Pupils can write down their personal rationale and as long as it is coherent, it is correct.

Regarding the dimension of heterogeneity, the worksheet considers the differentiation of learning goals, amount of material, support, and difficulty (cf. Luder 2019, 21). For example, there are basal and advanced learning objectives, mandatory and optional tasks, sentence starters for assistance, and the graded readers are already a differentiation on material.

Reading

As recommended by Grimm et al., reading acquisition takes place in three phases: pre-, while-, and post-reading (2015, 123). Tasks 1, 2, and 3 correspond to the pre-reading phase and offer both lexical- and content-based pre-reading activities (cf. Neugebauer 2008, 5). As recommended by Grabe and Stoller, the pupils prepare themselves for the text and do not yet interact with it directly (cf. Grabe and Stoller 2011, 133). In the worksheet, this is implemented by having the pupils make assumptions about the text based on pictures. In addition, some important but difficult words are clarified in task 3, e.g., “wildly” or “horrible”. The choice of words is based on their CEFR difficulty (see chapter “3.1

Passage 1: The birth of the creature”) and whether they are important for understanding the text and developing affective empathy. Clarifying words also lowers the Linguistic Threshold, which is a particular difficulty for reading in the EFL classroom (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 123). This also relieves the pupils on the process level of the multi-level model of reading (see figure 1). Tasks 4 - 8 are assigned to the while-phase of reading, as the pupils engage with the text directly. During the reading process, the pupils use the reading strategy of *Scanning*, because the pupils have to filter out specific information to achieve the learning goals (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 122). Tasks 9 - 15 are assigned to the post-reading phase. In this phase, primarily the method of collaborative reading by Grabe and Stoller is used (2011, 157). After reading, the pupils discuss the text in order to gain a deeper understanding of it. This also takes the social level of Rosebrock and Nix (2017, 15) into account, which states that communicating with others about what has been read is an important part of the reading process (2017, 15). The collaborative aspect is further amplified, as the pupils also contribute their ideas to the class and compare their own ideas to the others, thus engaging with many different interpretations of the same question. During the reading process, pupils also work on the reading strategies of good readers as defined by Amin (cf. Amin 2019, 37). Thus, in the pre-phase, pupils practice the strategy *Predicting*, and in the while-phase they practice the strategies *Making connections* and *Summarising*.

Dialogic speaking

In this worksheet, dialogic speaking takes place especially in the post-reading phase and is solely transactional. Based on the collaborative reading method, the pupils talk about their insights into the text during the social level of the multi-level model of reading (cf. Rosebrock and Nix 2017, 15). As described in chapter "2.2.3 Dialogic speaking" the speaking process can also be divided into pre-, while, and post-speaking phases. Bygate specifies these phases by calling them conceptualising (planning what they want to say), formulating (using lexical and grammatical knowledge to formulate the message), articulating (externalising the inner speech) and repairing (monitoring one's speech) (Bygate 2011, 419 - 420). During tasks 8 - 12, pupils prepare what they want to say regarding certain points and plan their speech which can be assigned to Bygate's conceptualising phase. During these pre-speaking activities, pupils are not only being offered support on the

conceptualising phase, but the formulating phase as well. Since the pupils have already answered the questions in writing, they have already activated the necessary linguistic knowledge to voice their thoughts. The articulating phase will not be monitored in this worksheet, as this concerns the externalisation of (accurate) speech. The focus of this worksheet is not on accuracy but on meaning. This is in accordance with Grimm et al.'s emphasis, that speaking activities should focus on meaning and fluency and not accuracy (2015, 132). The post-speaking phase of repairing is done by the pupils' themselves and their peers. If the meaning of the statements is not clear, the partners are urged to ask the speakers to elaborate. For this the pupils receive language chunks in task 13.

Regarding the task design, Grimm et al. emphasises that the pupils should receive language support and that they should talk about relevant topics (2015, 132). This is both the case in this worksheet. Regarding support, two points are considered in the worksheet. On the one hand, in task 13 the pupils are given language chunks to support them in the conversation. This does not only support them linguistically, but also in their discourse features as described by Bygate, as they learn how to properly take turns and maintain a conversation (2009, 415). On the other hand, the assignments are very clearly formulated, which helps the pupils to work on them. The topic of conversation is also accessible to the pupils. This is achieved through three aspects. Firstly, the conversation revolves around the pupils own learning, their interpretations and the characters they like which makes the topics interesting. Secondly, the speaking activities are crucial for understanding the text more thoroughly which gives the speaking activities more meaning in the context of text comprehension. Thirdly, the dialogic speaking activities involve real-world processes as described by Ellis as the pupils have to negotiate their opinions in the speaking activities (cf. Ellis 2003, 10).

Empathy

In the development of empathy skills, the pupils are supported by a variety of tasks. As recommended by Jamieson, the tasks motivate pupils to actively engage with the characters and their emotions (2015, 234 - 235). However, access to empathy can only succeed if the pupils understand the text (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 123). Linguistic difficulties are minimised, besides the choice of the graded reader, in the pre-reading activity in task 3, where difficult words are clarified. However, the choice of words is not only based on difficulty,

but they also (almost) all describe the creature. The pupils are thus already confronted with the characterisation of the creature without having read the text. In addition, pupils receive linguistic support in task 2 in the form of a word list. This list enables the pupils to concentrate on the emotions that are visible in the passage and are not hindered in their discovery of emotions by limited vocabulary. The list of words includes the emotions that were analysed in chapter "4.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature". Even if the emotions are not explicitly stated in the graded reader, the pupils can be made aware of them through the word list, which increases the likelihood that they will find them, thus counteracting the literary loss because of the linguistic simplification. The worksheet focuses primarily on teaching affective empathy. This is evident in tasks 2, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12. Here, the pupils have to put themselves in Victor's or the creature's proverbial shoes. This active engagement with the characters' emotions enhances the pupils' sense of empathy (Jamieson 2015, 234 - 235). However, in the literary analysis it was established that the emotions of the characters are difficult to discover, and that the difficulty varies depending on the graded reader. In RR, emotions are more clearly named, e.g., "Fear filled my heart" (Shelley 2012, 21). In MR, on the other hand, emotions have to be inferred much more from the text. In order to further simplify the access to the emotions, the pupils analyse the illustrations in the graded readers in the beginning in task 1. Because of the illustrations, pupils can already recognise many emotions and use this prior knowledge to discover the emotions in the text later on. This engagement with the illustrations also helps counteract the loss of literary meaning in the graded readers, as the pupils can use the pictures as visual support to spot the emotions. Overall, the high involvement of the pupils in the story also assists empathy development (cf. Döring 2013, 298). This high involvement is achieved by repeatedly asking pupils to analyse the characters, as well as form personal connections with them.

Evaluation

The assessment of the pupils' progress takes place in two steps.

To assess the pupils' reading skills, the worksheet is collected at the end of class. With this regard, task 5 will be corrected, because it shows whether the pupils are able to use the reading strategy *Scanning* correctly.

To assess their progress with regard to their empathy skills, the notes on the padlet are

used. Pupils write down one of the emotions that they believe Victor feels, as well as link the emotion to a passage from the text. This allows teachers to determine two things: 1) do the pupils identify relevant emotions?, and 2) how do they use the text to access the emotion? The assessment of the notes on the padlet is a performance-referenced assessment, since the focus is on whether the pupils found important information from the text and thus were able to correctly interpret the meaning-focused input and not on whether their answer on the padlet is linguistically correct (cf. Ellis 2003, 283 - 285). The padlet can also be used by the pupils for their self-assessment. Because the pupils only have to write down one emotion, it is highly likely that several pupils choose to contribute their answers on the same emotion. Through the contributions of the others, pupils can also directly check for themselves how others interpreted the passage and evaluate their own answer in comparison to the other contributions. At this point it is also advised that the teacher discusses the answers on the padlet with the pupils. This is done to value the pupils' efforts and contributions, as well as enable the teacher to offer formative feedback and address errors.

5.4 Worksheets for Passage 2: The creature's request

The corresponding passages can be found in appendix "8.15 Passage 2 RR" and "8.16 Passage 2 MR".

Embedment in the lesson plan

Before engaging with this passage, the pupils must have already read the previous chapters. Special attention should be paid to the creature's life, as it is very tragic. The plots of the previous chapters help pupils to better identify the emotions of the creature and Victor in this passage, as they approach the scene with prior knowledge. In addition, the pupils should have further worked on their reading and dialogic speaking skills. Their progress in their reading skills enables the pupils to concentrate on inexplicitly stated meaning, e.g., the emotions of the characters. In addition, pupils will receive less scaffolds for dialogic speaking (e.g., no support for task 15) and are expected to conduct their discussions more independently.

Learning Objectives

As the pupils have improved their reading skills in between the passages, the learning objectives focus more on the other skills, namely empathy, and dialogic speaking. The learning objectives for reading (LO1 and LO2) serve as preparation for the pupils' work on their empathy skills, as they need to be able to infer meaning which is not explicitly stated (LO2) and to differentiate between main ideas and secondary information (LO1). Since the pupils have already gained experience in identifying explicit information, it makes sense to increase the difficulty of the learning objective by letting pupils look for inexplicitly stated information and infer meaning. The majority of the learning objectives focus on Victor's and the creature's emotions (LO2, LO3, LO4 and LO5*). Now, in addition to affective empathy, pupils also have to practice their cognitive empathy (e.g., LO5*). In terms of speaking the pupils need to be able to negotiate their ideas with each other, in addition to acting out their ideas in front of each other and the class (LO3 and LO4). The complete list of learning objectives can be found in table 6 below.

		The pupils can...
basal	LO1	...identify the main message of a passage and demonstrate this by summarising it in their own words.
	LO2	... identify the emotions of the creature and Victor by assigning matching adjectives to their dialogue (affective empathy).
	LO3	... verbally negotiate their ideas and agree on one solution.
	LO4	... verbally perform the emotions of the creature and Victor (affective empathy).
advanced	LO5*	...take on the perspective of the creature or Victor and argue what they would have done in their position in writing (cognitive empathy).

Table 6: Learning objectives of Passage 2

Tasks

As for the worksheet in chapter "5.3 Worksheet for Passage 1: The birth of the creature" the worksheet for RR and MR are almost identical. The only differences in this passage

are the page numbers, as well as task 3, for which pupils have to translate words which appear in their respective editions. The worksheet can be found in figure 10 and figure 11.

Richmond Reader

The creature's request

Follow the instructions on the worksheet as you read the passage. All * tasks are mandatory, ** tasks are optional.

Learning objectives:

- I can understand what the creature wants.
- I can understand how the creature feels.
- I can understand how Victor's emotions change in the passage.
- I can argue what I would feel like if I were the creature or Victor. **

 1.* Read the title of the chapter on page 55. What do you think is going to happen in this chapter? Write down your assumptions in 1 – 2 sentences.

 2.** Did the previous chapters help you make your assumptions? If so, quickly write down how the previous chapters influenced your decision.

 3.* Discuss your answers of task 1 and 2 with your partner.

4.* Look the following words up online and write down the translation.

Destroy (verb):

Reasonable (adv):

Sensitive (adj):

Horrible (adj):

Peacefully (adv):

5.* Read the passage in the graded reader (p. 55 - 56) in one go.

6.* In one sentence, what does the creature want?

7.* Compare your answer with your partner. Do you have the same answer?
If not, discuss the differences with your partner.

In the following tasks you will focus on the emotions of the creature and Victor.

8.* Go back to the graded reader (p. 55 – 56) and underline every sentence in which the creature talks about **why** it wants a companion.

9.* If you had one emotion to describe why the creature wants a companion, which one would you use? Write it down.

- 10.*Victor does not immediately agree to the request. Underline the following three passages in the graded reader.
- 1) Victor does not want to help the creature.
 - 2) Victor starts to feel compassionate towards the creature.
 - 3) Victor agrees to the request.

- 11.*Go back to the graded reader (p. 55 – 56) and highlight everything the creature says in one colour.

- 12.*Assign at least **one** of the following emotions to every sentence that you highlighted. If you do not understand a word, look it up online.

happy *lonely* *confused* *hostile*

sad *reasonable* *mad* *compassionate*

scared *excited* *horrified* *reflected*

desperate *violent* *angry* *cautious*

- 13.*Repeat tasks 11 and 12 for Victor in another colour.

- 14.*Compare your results with your partner. Do you agree on the emotions? If not, discuss the differences with your partner and agree on the emotions. Use the sentence starters in the box below if you need help.

Helpful language:

“Why do you think that...?”

“I think that, because...”

“I disagree with you, because.... “

“Can you explain your answer to me?”

“Do you agree/disagree with me?”

 15.* In pairs, decide who is A and B. A reads out the dialogue for Victor, B will read out the dialogue for the creature. When reading the dialogue to each other, try to act out the emotions of tasks 12 and 13.

 16.* Present your performance to the class.

 17.** If you had been alone like the creature, what would you feel like? Use adjectives to describe your emotions. If you need help, look at the box in task 12.

 18.** Do you think the creature's request is reasonable? Why? Write your answer on the lines using full sentences.

 19.** Would you have agreed to the creature's request if you were Victor? Why yes/not? Write down your answer using full sentences.

Figure 10: Worksheet Passage 2, RR

Macmillan Reader

The creature's request

Follow the instructions on the worksheet as you read the passage. All * tasks are mandatory, ** tasks are optional.

Learning objectives:

- I can understand what the creature wants.
- I can understand how the creature feels.
- I can understand how Victor's emotions change in the passage.
- I can argue what I would feel like if I were the creature or Victor. **

- 1.* Read the title of the chapter on page 32. What do you think is going to happen in this chapter? Write down your assumptions in 1 – 2 sentences.

- 2.** Did the previous chapters help you make your assumptions? If so, quickly write down how the previous chapters influenced your decision.

- 3.* Discuss your answers of task 1 and 2 with your partner.

- 4.* Look the following words up online and write down the translation.

Wickedness (noun):

Lonely (adj):

- 5.* Read the passage in the graded reader (p. 32) in one go.

6.* In one sentence, what does the creature want?

7.* Compare your answer with your partner. Do you have the same answer?
If not, discuss the differences with your partner.

In the following tasks you will focus on the emotions of the creature and Victor.

8.* Go back to the graded reader (p. 32) and underline every sentence in which the creature talks about **why** it wants a companion.

9.* If you had one emotion to describe why the creature wants a companion, which one would you use? Write it down.

10.* Victor does not immediately agree to the request. Underline the following three passages in the graded reader.

- 1) Victor does not want to help the creature.
- 2) Victor starts to feel compassionate towards the creature.
- 3) Victor agrees to the request.

11.* Go back to the graded reader (p. 55 – 56) and highlight everything the creature says in one colour.

12.* Assign at least **one** of the following emotions to every sentence that you highlighted. If you do not understand a word, look it up online.

happy *lonely* *confused* *hostile*

sad *reasonable* *mad* *compassionate*

scared *excited* *horrified* *reflected*

desperate *violent* *angry* *cautious*

13.* Repeat tasks 11 and 12 for Victor in another colour.

14.* Compare your results with your partner. Do you agree on the emotions? If not, discuss the differences with your partner and agree on the emotions. Use the sentence starters in the box below if you need help.

Helpful language:

“Why do you think that...?”

“I think that, because...”

“I disagree with you, because.... “

“Can you explain your answer to me?”

“Do you agree/disagree with me?”

15.* In pairs, decide who is A and B. A reads out the dialogue for Victor, B will read out the dialogue for the creature. When reading the dialogue to each other, try to act out the emotions of tasks 12 and 13.

16.* Present your performance to the class.

17.** If you had been alone like the creature, what would you feel like? Use adjectives to describe your emotions. If you need help, look at the box in task 12.

18.**Do you think the creature's request is reasonable? Why? Write your answer on the lines using full sentences.

19.**Would you have agreed to the creature's request if you were Victor? Why yes/not? Write down your answer using full sentences.

Figure 11: Worksheet 2, MR

Commenting on tasks

TBLT and Scaffolding

Regarding the aspects TBLT and Scaffolding of reading, a large part overlaps with the descriptions in chapter "5.3 Worksheet for Passage 1: The birth of the creature". For this passage, only the points that differ from the worksheet in passage 1 are highlighted. In this passage, there are slight changes to the task types that the pupils work on. The pupils still have to practice the strategy of *Conversational patterns, Personalising and Co-operating* (see figure 6), but for *Conversational patterns* they receive less support than in passage 1. This worksheet heavily focuses on the skills of *Co-operating* and *Personalising*, as pupils have to collaborate with others to achieve the learning goals and personally engage with the material.

Accessibility

This subsection also shows similarities with the chapter "5.3 Worksheet for Passage 1: The birth of the creature". In this worksheet, the TBLT approach, with its many communicative tasks, e.g., tasks 3 and 7, creates positive conditions for easier access to the text, as it is motivating for pupils to work collaboratively (cf. Ellis 2003, 267). In addition, the structure of the tasks remains very clear, which makes it easier for the pupils to access the

text and work on the assignments (Brandt 2002, 293). In this worksheet, too, care was taken to ensure that the tasks are solvable but not too easy, in order to optimally support the pupils' motivation (Dörnyei 2001, 75 - 76). This was again achieved by language support, e.g., in tasks 4 and 12, so that the pupils receive support for their linguistic difficulties and can concentrate on the meaning-focused output. In addition, the tasks can be assigned to different levels in Bloom's Taxonomy (see figure 9), in which it can be seen that both easy and challenging tasks are offered. Task 6, for example, is assigned to the *Understand* level, and thus easy, whereas tasks 11, 12 and 13 are assigned to the *Analysis* level, and are thus much more difficult. As for the worksheet for passage 1, literature is a great resource for teaching hierarchically more challenging tasks, as it offers many authentic opportunities to think critically and creatively (cf. Naji et al. 2019, 7). In this passage this is achieved, for example, by inferring emotions that are not explicitly stated (tasks 12 and 13) or by evaluating the creature's request and Victor's reaction to it (tasks 17, 18 and 19) which allows for many possible answers, creative solutions, and critical engagement with the material (cf. Okyar 2021, 333).

The pupils also receive language support to accommodate and balance the heterogeneity feature "language proficiency" (cf. Berger and Pfiffner 2018, 13 – 15), e.g., in task 14 through the help of sentence starters. Regarding the necessity of variety in task design, language skills and organisational forms for a motivating teaching, the worksheet fulfils all of Dörnyei's requirements (cf. Dörnyei 2001, 74). In this worksheet the task type changes repeatedly (e.g., task 1 predicting, task 4 translating, task 6 summarising, task 7 comparing, etc.), as well as the language skills, even more so than in the worksheet for passage 1. Nevertheless, a productive task is always preceded by a receptive one, which is the recommended sequencing of language skills (cf. Nunan 2004, 35 - 36). In this worksheet, there is also a variety of organisational forms. The phases of individual work are repeatedly followed by cooperative learning forms, e.g., in tasks 3 and 7. In addition to the motivational components already mentioned, for this worksheet the pupils can also present and celebrate their results in front of the class, which according to Dörnyei is strongly motivational (2001, 76). By showing off their results in task 16, pupils receive external recognition and creates an opportunity for them to celebrate their efforts, which further increases their intrinsic motivation (Grimm et al. 2015, 132).

Like the worksheet for passage 1, this worksheet accommodates heterogeneity in the

classroom by considering learning goals (basal and advanced), amount of material (mandatory and optional tasks), support (helpful language chunks for assistance) and difficulty (choice of graded reader) (cf. Luder 2019, 21).

Reading

In this worksheet, too, reading takes place in three phases: pre-, while-, and post-reading (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 123). Tasks 1 - 4 are assigned to the pre-reading phase. Here, pupils find access to the text through the title and their prior knowledge of the novel. In addition, important words are clarified in advance. The choice of words in this case is based on their CEFR rating to lower the Linguistic Threshold (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 123), as well as on their relevance for the development of affective empathy skills. More on this will be clarified in the Empathy subsection. The pupils thus receive lexical- and content-based pre-reading activities (cf. Neugebauer 2008, 5). Tasks 5 - 13 refer to the while-reading phase. In this phase, pupils work on the reading strategies *Reading for gist* (task 6), *Scanning* (task 10), and *Reading for detailed understanding* (e.g., task 12). Tasks 14 - 19 are assigned to the post-reading phase. The pupils no longer work with the material directly but use it to find a more personal approach to the text through affective and cognitive empathy. The approach of collaborative reading is considered in this passage during all three phases (cf. Grabe and Stoller 2011, 157). The pupils discuss their assumptions in the pre-phase, compare their results in the while-phase and work out the characters' emotions collaboratively in the post-phase. In contrast to the worksheet in passage 1, the receptive skill reading, and the productive skill dialogic speaking are much more interrelated and therefore accommodate collaborative reading well.

Regarding the reading strategies that good readers use, in addition to the strategies in the worksheet for passage 1 (*Predicting*, *Making connections* and *Summarising*), the pupils now practice *Inferring* as well (cf. Amin 2019, 37). The emotions are not explicitly mentioned in many cases, and pupils must use their prior knowledge and literary skills to identify them.

Dialogic speaking

In this worksheet, dialogic speaking is used to a much greater extent than in the worksheet for passage 1 but remains transactional. It is used during the pre-, while-, and post-reading

phases to support the reading process through the method of collaborative reading (cf. Grabe and Stoller 2011, 157). Similar to the worksheet for passage 1, speaking activities are scaffolded to accommodate the four phases of the speaking process (cf. Bygate 2011, 419 – 420). Since the focus in this case is also primarily on what is said rather than how it is said, the assignments focus primarily on Bygate's conceptualising phase.

For example, the speaking activity in task 3 is supported by two pre-reading activities (tasks 1 and 2) in which the pupils already plan what they will say later, both in terms of content and language. The same structure can be found in task 7, for which tasks 5 and 6 function as preparation, or in task 14, where tasks 11, 12 and 13 function as preparation. The pupils thus receive a lot of support during their conceptualising phase. The formulating phase of the pupils is also supported similarly as in the worksheet for passage 1. Since the pupils write down most of their answers, they already activate the lexical and grammatical knowledge that they will need later for the formulating phase. The articulating and repairing phase is managed individually by the pupils. The pupils, or their peers, can determine whether the statement has the desired meaning and adjust their statement if necessary.

In this worksheet, the pupils also receive linguistic support in the form of sentence starters, which is recommended by Grimm et al. especially in discursive settings (2015, 132). The sentence starters also support pupils in improving their discourse features, as they are supported in structuring and continuing a conversation (cf. Bygate 2009, 415). In addition, they also support the pupils in their formulating phase, as they are provided with fixed and already prepared language structures that help them formulate their thoughts. Furthermore, the pupils are again supported by the logical internal structure of the worksheet in terms of sequencing between productive and receptive language skills and the clear assignments (cf. Nunan 2004, 35 - 36). The topic of conversation is also interesting for the pupils. The pupils have to put themselves in the shoes of the characters and recognise emotions, which they have to infer from implicit information from the text. According to Dörnyei, this openness and ambiguity of possible answers is particularly exciting and motivating for pupils (2001, 76). In addition, the topic of the conversation, the characters' emotions, is sensibly chosen in view of the topic of the lesson. Since the characters are exciting to the pupils, it is also interesting for them to talk about the characters, thus proving to be a meaningful speaking activity and enabling pupils to develop a deeper understanding of the text (cf. Grimm et al. 123; Jamieson 2005, 236 - 238). Additionally, the tasks

involve real-world processes, such as negotiating opinions, which are crucial for meaningful TBLT activities (Ellis 2003, 10).

Empathy

As suggested by Jamieson, the pupils are asked to repeatedly directly engage with the characters' emotions (2015, 234 – 235). In order to achieve this, the pupils are given different tasks. The first confrontation with the characters' emotions takes place in task 4. This confrontation does not explicitly ask the pupils to engage with any characters' emotions but lowers the Linguistic Threshold (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 123). However, the words were chosen to revolve around the creature's and Victor's emotions. Thus, the pupils receive linguistic support and are sure to understand important words for accessing the different emotions in the text. In addition, the words offered to the pupils in task 12 also support the pupils both linguistically as well as in working out the emotions of the characters. In the literary analysis (see chapter "3.2 Passage 2: The creature's request") it turned out that especially in this scene many emotions are either missing or difficult to make out. Therefore, the emotions offered in the linguistic support were chosen to include and acknowledge the emotions that were discussed in the literary analysis. Since the emotions are not easily recognisable in the graded readers, as they are much less elaborated due to the abbreviated text, the list helps pupils to become aware of certain emotions, which counteracts the loss of literary material due to the linguistic simplification and assist readers in engaging with Victor's and the creature's original character. Since the pupils are primarily concerned with the emotions of the characters, they mainly practice affective empathy. Tasks 18 and 19, however, allow pupils to work on their cognitive empathy skills. In these tasks, pupils must not only empathise with the emotions, but also actively change perspectives mentally. The mental change of perspectives is necessary for pupils to understand the characters' decisions as well as for them to imagine and argue how they would react in the same situation. This high level of involvement and personalisation favours empathy development (cf. Döring 2013, 298).

Evaluation

Whether or not the basal learning objectives have been achieved can be assessed in class through a formative performance-referenced assessment (cf. Ellis 2003, 283 - 285). As the

pupils have to act out the emotions, which they assign to the dialogue between Victor and the creature, teachers can base on the pupils' performance, whether or not the pupils managed to identify matching emotions. With this regard it is important that teachers should not focus on fluency or pronunciation, as the pupils did not directly work on these skills. The focus should solely rely on whether or not the emotions are 1) identifiable, and 2) matching. With regard to the advanced learning objective teachers need to collect the worksheet of the pupils and assess, whether or not the pupils were able to cognitively empathise with the characters. Just like with the assessment of the performance, teachers should focus on the meaning of the pupils' output and not their linguistic accuracy, as they do neither receive enough support to work on their accuracy, nor are they made aware of it being assessed.

5.5 Worksheets for Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth

The corresponding passages can be found in appendix "8.17 Passage 3 RR" and "8.18 Passage 3 MR".

Embedment in the lesson plan

Just like for the previous two passages, the pupils have read the novel up to this passage. In addition, the teacher should pay special attention to the chapter, in which Victor decided to destroy the female companion and the creature's reaction to it. This scene sets the stage for this passage. The pupils have also continued to work on their dialogic speaking skills as well as on the identification of emotions. That is why the scaffolds in this worksheet have been massively reduced with regard to these two skills.

Learning Objectives

The learning objectives of this passage focus almost exclusively on the pupils' empathy skills. Reading skills are no longer worked on specifically but are a prerequisite for the development of the learning objectives. LO1, LO2, and LO4 focus on pupils' empathy skills. Similar to passage 2, pupils must primarily comprehend indirectly inferred emotions of the characters which can only succeed if pupils empathise affectively with the characters. In addition, there is now a greater focus on cognitive empathy, as pupils actively need to take on Victor's role and argue what they would do in his position. LO3 focuses on the pupils'

dialogic speaking skills. This learning goal has also become more difficult, as they no longer have to just present their ideas to each other but must actively convince each other of their opinions. Their opinions must therefore be supported by arguments in addition to discourse skills (cf. Brown 2001, 276). The complete list of learning objectives can be found in table 7 below.

		The pupils can...
basal	LO1	...identify implicitly inferred emotions (affective empathy) and demonstrate this by highlighting sentences that hint towards the emotions.
	LO2	...draw connections between the previous chapters and specific statements of this chapter and infer implicitly stated meaning (affective and cognitive empathy).
	LO3	... verbally share their opinion with a partner and defend it if necessary.
	LO4	... suspect how the story is going to continue by taking on Victor's perspective (affective and cognitive empathy).
ad- vanced	LO4*	...use the literary material to justify their decision as to why they think a hypothetical continuation is plausible.

Table 7: Learning objectives of Passage 3

Tasks

For this passage, the worksheets for RR and MR differ in the first two tasks in what the pupils are expected to do. However, the structure between the two worksheet is identical. The differences between the two worksheets will be discussed in the subsection Reading. The worksheet can be found in figure 12 and figure 13.

Richmond Reader

The death of Elizabeth

Follow the instructions on the worksheet as you read the passage. All * tasks are mandatory, ** tasks are optional.

Learning objectives:

- I can understand what emotions Victor feels.
- I can infer why the creature killed Elizabeth.
- I can suspect what Victor's next steps are.
- I can justify my decision with the help of the text.**

1.* The previous chapter concludes with the sentence "*Those were the last happy moments of my life.*" Based on the previous chapters, what horrible things could happen to Victor? Write your assumptions down in 1 – 2 sentences.

2.** The title of the chapter is "A Promise Kept". What "Promise" could they talk about? Write your assumptions down using full sentences.

3.* Read the passage (p.75 – 76) in one go.

4.* What emotion do you think is Victor feeling at the moment? Write your answer down using key words or full sentences.

5.* Go back to the graded reader and highlight every passage that supports your answer from task 5.

6.* Why do you think the creature killed Elizabeth? Write down your idea using at least one full sentence.

7.* Discuss your assumption on task 6 with your partner. If you disagree, try to convince your partner of your idea.

 8.* How do you think the story is going to continue? Discuss your ideas with your partner.

 9.* Agree on how the story could continue. Write your answer on a note on the online padlet using full sentences and publish it.

 10.* Read through all the answers of your classmates.

 11.* In pairs, decide which possible continuation is the most plausible one. Copy the answer of the padlet onto the worksheet.

 12.** Why did you choose this possible continuation? Justify your answer on the following lines.

Figure 12: Worksheet Passage 3, RR

Macmillan Reader

The death of Elizabeth

 = writing

 = speaking

Follow the instructions on the worksheet as you read the passage. All * tasks are mandatory, ** tasks are optional.

Learning objectives:

- I can understand what emotions Victor feels.
- I can infer why the creature killed Elizabeth.
- I can suspect what Victor's next steps are.
- I can justify my decision with the help of the text.**

1.* The title of this chapter is "My Wedding-night". What emotions do you associate with a wedding? Write your answers down using key words or sentences.

2.** Have a look at the picture on page 47. What do you think happened? Write your assumptions down using full sentences.

3.* Read the passage (p.46 - 48) in one go.

4.* What emotion do you think is Victor feeling at the moment? Write your answer down using key words or full sentences.

5.* Go back to the graded reader and highlight every passage that supports your answer from task 5.

6.* Why do you think the creature killed Elizabeth? Write down your idea using at least one full sentence.

7.* Discuss your assumption on task 6 with your partner. If you disagree, try to convince your partner of your idea.

8.* How do you think the story is going to continue? Discuss your ideas with your partner.

9.* Agree on how the story could continue. Write your answer on a note on the online padlet using full sentences and publish it.

10.* Read through all the answers of your classmates.

 11.* In pairs, decide which possible continuation is the most plausible one. Copy the answer of the padlet onto the worksheet.

 12.* Why did you choose this possible continuation? Justify your answer on the following lines.

Figure 13: Worksheet Passage 3, MR

Commenting on tasks

TBLT and Scaffolding

Similar to chapter “5.4 Worksheet for Passage 2: The creature’s request” many of the accommodations made for the worksheet to fit TBLT criteria overlap with the descriptions in chapter “5.3 Worksheet for Passage 1: The birth of the creature”. Thus, only the points that differ from the worksheet in passage 1 will be discussed. Regarding the task types, changes between the worksheets can be observed. This worksheet heavily focuses on the two strategies *Personalising* and *Predicting* (cf. Amin 2019, 37).

Accessibility

There are similarities to the previous chapters in this subsection as well. Also in these tasks, care was taken that they are clear and offer many opportunities for cooperative learning, so that intrinsic motivation is as high as possible (cf. Ellis 2003, 267; Brandt 2002, 293). Similar to the previous worksheets, tasks were also designed to be solvable, but challenging (cf. Dörnyei 2001, 75 - 76). In contrast to the other worksheets, however, the pupils do not receive linguistic support as the linguistic demands in this passage are consistently easy. Rather, the tasks address various levels of Bloom's Taxonomy (see figure 9). For example, task 6 can be assigned to the *Evaluate* level, since the pupils must justify

their answer. Even though this is already a hierarchically challenging task, other tasks are even more challenging. Task 8, for example, requires the pupils to actively create a hypothetical continuation of the story and can therefore be assigned to the level *Create*. These highly creative and open-ended assignments allow for pupils to improve highly cognitive challenging skills, whilst also allowing for a lot of flexibility and creativity for the pupils (cf. Okyar 2021, 333). In this worksheet, however, it can be stated that almost all tasks can be assigned to the upper three levels of the taxonomy and that the entire worksheet is difficult. This can be justified by the fact that the pupils are approaching the end of the classroom project and had enough time to practice the competences. Tasks that are too easy at this point would lower motivation (cf. Dörnyei 2001, 75). This worksheet also considers the variety of tasks and language skills (cf. Dörnyei 2001, 74). The task type (e.g., task 2 interpreting, task 3 discriminating, task 8 predicting, etc.) and the language skill are constantly changing. Regarding heterogeneity, the worksheet is differentiated on three levels, namely learning goals (basal and advanced), amount of material (mandatory and optional tasks) and difficulty (choice of graded reader) (cf. Luder 2019, 21).

Reading

Tasks 1 and task 2 are assigned to the pre-phase of reading. Depending on the worksheet, however, the pupils work on different tasks. In RR's worksheet, pupils use information from the previous chapters, as well as their own prior knowledge, to access the passage. This pre-phase is relatively difficult because pupils must use the reading strategies of *Predicting*, *Making connections*, and *Inferring* (cf. Amin 2019, 37). MR's worksheet pre-activity proceeds through the chapter title and illustrations and requires only *Predicting* from the pupils. However, RR's more difficult pre-activity can be justified by the fact that it is also the more difficult edition in terms of CEFR language level and a more challenging task is therefore reasonable. For either worksheet the pre-activities aim to offer a content-based access to the material rather than a lexical one (cf. Neugebauer 2008, 5). Tasks 3 - 7 are assigned to the while-phase. In this phase, the pupils use the reading strategy *Scanning* to identify relevant parts of the text. In RR's case, the pupils also use the reading strategy *Inferring*, since the motif behind Elizabeth's murder is not explicitly stated and the pupils have to infer it using their prior knowledge of the story. Tasks 8 - 12 are assigned to the post-phase of the reading process. Following the reading, pupils talk about the content on

the one hand, and on the other hand, they hypothesise about how the story will continue. They do so in pairs and are thus engaging in the method of collaborative reading. The collaborative aspect is further highlighted by the pupils seeing and evaluating the results of the others on the padlet.

Dialogic speaking

Similar to the worksheet for passage 1, the dialogic speaking takes place in the post-reading phase and is transactional. Situated in the social level of Rosebrock and Nix multi-level model of reading (see figure 1), the pupils talk about their interpretations with each other. In this worksheet, however, the pupils receive the least support in their speech production. This is because the classroom project nears its end, and the pupils should have improved their dialogic speaking competences and not be as dependent on the scaffolds anymore. With regard to the four phases of speech production by Bygate (2011, 419 – 420) they are only really supported with regard to the conceptualising phase. In task 7 they are expected to share their ideas to their partners, however, task 6 briefly assists them on preparing their statement. In contrast, in task 8 they do not receive any support, neither linguistically nor discursively anymore from the worksheet with regard to Bygate's phases. The pupils are therefore expected to be able to monitor the four phases independently. As this is the last speaking activity of the worksheet, the challenge is reasonable as pupils should have acquired the competences to navigate the stages independently. In addition, task 8 is open-ended and allows pupils to find a personal and creative way to answer it. As Dörnyei argues, activities that allow for flexibility and creativity are especially motivating for pupils and should thus encourage them to work on them (2001, 76).

With regard to Grimm et al.'s general suggestions to designing communicative tasks, the worksheet acknowledges the pupils' intrinsic motivation, the focus on meaning, as well as the relevance of the topics (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 132). Firstly, with regard to the pupils' intrinsic motivation, Victor and the creature are interesting characters, which already increases the pupils' intrinsic motivation to engage with them (cf. Döring 2013, 297). The focus on meaning is evident in that the pupils are not assessed on the linguistic accuracy of their speech production but rather on whether they fulfil the communicative goal of the task. Lastly, task 8 offers pupils relevant topics to discuss. According to Vogt, as soon as pupils can engage with a material on a personal level (e.g. "How do you think the story is

going to continue?" in task 8), the task is more enjoyable and interesting (2017, 239).

Empathy

This worksheet focuses on promoting the pupils' affective and cognitive empathy skills. Once again, in accordance with Jamieson's suggestion to directly ask the pupils to look into the characters' emotions, as well as their mind, the tasks designed explicitly state, how the pupils should engage with the characters (cf. Jamieson 2015, 236 – 238). Task 4 does so, by asking pupils to infer Victor's emotions to Elizabeth's death. His emotions are never explicitly stated but the pupils need to be able to infer it on the base of the text. To recognise Victor's emotions the pupils therefore need to be able to affectively empathise with him, which in turns promotes their affective empathy skills. Tasks 6 and 8 focus more on the pupils' cognitive empathy. In task 6 pupils need to take on the creature's perspective and try to understand, why it decided to kill Elizabeth. As the pupils need to be able to comprehend the creature's reasoning, they need to understand his thinking process and mentally change perspectives, which according to Döring can be attributed to cognitive empathy (2013, 297). Task 8 elaborates on the skills required in task 6. In this case, the pupils receive neither textual nor structural support for developing empathy. Quite the opposite, the pupils' cognitive and affective empathy skills must be strong enough to experience empathy without any textual or structural support. The pupils need to cognitively and affectively synchronise with the characters to understand and anticipate the characters' perspectives in an imaginative scenario and invent a hypothetical continuation based on their perspective-taking. Just like it was the case for reading and speaking, the empathy tasks in this worksheet are also the most difficult among the worksheets, as pupils need to be able to empathise with characters without the help of any textual hints. This requires a very high personal involvement with the story, as the pupils actively need to put themselves in the proverbial affective and cognitive shoes of someone else, which fosters empathy development (cf. Döring 2013, 298). However, as it was the case for the language skills, as this is the last task for the classroom project the challenge can be warranted, as the pupils have already had many opportunities to work on their affective and cognitive empathy skills.

Evaluation

The learning objectives heavily focus on the pupils' empathy skills. However, the pupils' reading and dialogic speaking skills are required for the development of the empathy skills. In the assessment only their empathetic performance will be assessed and is based on the performance-referenced assessment by Ellis (2003, 283 – 285). The pupils' achievement of LO1, LO2, LO3 and LO4 can be assessed through their answer on the padlet. Depending on what emotions they assign to Victor (LO1 and LO2) and what motif they assign to Elizabeth's murder (LO3) alters their answer for LO4. As the padlet is visible online, the teacher can very easily and quickly assess, whether or not the pupils have been able to change perspectives with the characters, both affectively and cognitively. As the answers are visible online, the teacher should also use this opportunity to comment on some answers to provide formative feedback. The teacher can, for example, ask pairs how they came up with their possible continuation and, if necessary, assist them in arguing for it. LO4* can be assessed in writing when the teacher collects the worksheet. As with the previous assessments, due to the nature of the task-design, teachers should only pay attention to the meaning of the pupils' output and not the linguistic accuracy.

6 Discussion and outlook

In this master thesis, two research questions were investigated. In the following, the questions are revisited and answered with the theoretical and practical background.

The first research question was as follows:

1. How do the linguistic simplifications in graded reader versions of *Mary Shelley's Frankenstein, or the Modern Prometheus 1818 Text* change the literary meaning of the material in comparison to the original text?

In chapter "3 Linguistic analysis" it was revealed that the texts were linguistically adapted especially with regard to their sentence structure and the difficulty of words. This finding is consistent with the theoretical background. For example, Claridge argues that one of the most important grading scales is the lexis of the texts (2012, 12). Among the texts analysed

(OR, RR, MR, and SFB), OR consistently has the most difficult words. RR and MR both displayed a severely simplified vocabulary in comparison to OR but the lexical difficulty between the two versions is comparable. In contrast, SFB uses a very simplified language, which is reflected in the easy CEFR language level for the graded reader. Moreover, Lucas' levels of lexical simplification 1) replacement and 2) omission could also be observed in the linguistic simplification among all three graded readers (cf. Lucas 1991, 243). For example, in all graded readers some descriptions were missing (e.g., "flowing" in passage 1 in OR does not have a counterpart in RR, MR or SFB), corresponding to level 2) omission. Additionally, difficult words were replaced by simpler ones (e.g., passage 2 "malicious" (C2) from OR becomes "evil" (B2) in RR), which corresponds with level 1) replacement. Regarding sentence structure, the results of the linguistic analysis confirm Dirks' (2004, 36 ff.) assumptions that the relative number of main and subordinate clauses increases to the relative number of sentences with increasing language level, and that sentence length decreases with CEFR level. In addition, Hill's (2008, 196) finding that easier graded readers use more dialogues was confirmed. With this regard, OR has both the most difficult sentence structure and the longest sentences. Both categories consistently changed in relation to CEFR language level in this analysis. Only my hypothesis that linguistic simplification targets a certain part of speech, especially adjectives and adverbs, could not be confirmed, whereas the hypothesis that graded readers commonly use more verbs to drive the narrative forward could be confirmed on the basis of the four texts.

These linguistic changes had an enormous influence on the literary material. In this regard, the indirect and direct characterisation of the main characters was analysed, focusing on the emotions of the characters. The analysis showed that the emotions of the characters in the graded readers are much less prominent in comparison to the original. This can be attributed to two reasons. Firstly, the reduction of content in general consequently prompts that there is less text to elaborate the individual emotions (cf. Macmillan 2014, 2). Characters have fewer opportunities to show their emotions and whole sections, where emotions can be explicitly and implicitly observed, are omitted. For example, Victor in chapter "4.2 Passage 2: The creature's request" is "cautious", among other things, in the original, but this emotion is lost in MR's versions, as the passages that allude to these emotions are omitted. The second reason is the level 1) replacement of Lucas (1991, 243). For example, in chapter "4.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature," the creature in OR is described

neutrally as a “being” by Victor, whereas in the graded readers it is directly described as a “monster.” Victor thus appears more negative from the beginning in the graded readers than in the original.

In summary, the first research question can be answered as follows. Linguistic simplification strongly alters how characters are characterised indirectly and directly, eliminating some emotions altogether and changing others, e.g., the switch from “anxious” in the original to “excited” in MR (see “4.1 Passage 1: The birth of the creature”). The similarity of emotions between the original and graded readers also depends on the CEFR language level. For this analysis, the more similar the CEFR language level of the graded reader was to the original, the more similar were the emotions that could be directly and indirectly observed. Whether this observation is a coincidence or whether there really is a causal relationship between language level and emotional similarity would need further investigation.

The second research question was as follows:

2. How can task-based language teaching introduce secondary school pupils to literature and improve their *Reading*, *Dialogic speaking*, and *Empathy* skills and help them work out literary meaning that was changed or lost during the simplification process between the original and graded readers?

The linguistic and literary analysis revealed that emotions are heavily impacted by the editing process. However, the emotions of the characters are an integral part for the pupils’ development of affective empathy, which is why the lesson plan focused particularly on the reappraisal of the characters’ emotions (cf. Döring 2013, 289 ff.). Thus, the lesson plan focuses on developing the pupils’ linguistic competences of *Reading* and *Dialogic speaking*, as well as recovering the loss of the characters’ emotions in the graded readers as a result of the linguistic simplification through suitable tasks.

The worksheets can be seen in the chapters “5.3 Worksheet for Passage 1: The birth of the creature”, “5.4 Worksheet for Passage 2: The creature’s request” and “5.5 Worksheet for Passage 3: The death of Elizabeth”.

The approach of TBLT, in addition to language skill specific methods, has proven to be an excellent way to work on the subject specific competences and transversal competences.

On the one hand, TBLT focuses on a meaning-focused in- and output (Grimm et al. 2015, 70). Thus, the focus is on the individual processing of the material and the meaning of pupils' output and not on linguistic accuracy. Since the lesson did not aim to teach grammatical or lexical structures, but rather to encourage the pupils to actively use the language to solve problems, the choice of the approach was correct. The focus on meaning also aligns with the research on graded readers, which suggests that they are a valuable learning resource for comprehension- and meaning-based projects (Nation and Deewerdt 2001, 57). TBLT also allows for a lot of flexibility in how questions are answered (Vogt 2017, 239). With this regard TBLT also advocates for designing assignments where the answer is open-ended and can be solved creatively by the pupils. This flexibility is particularly important in the development of cognitive and affective empathy. For example, in the case of cognitive empathy related questions such as "What would you have done in Victor's place?", the pupils need to have the freedom to engage with the material personally. There are also no correct or incorrect answers to these questions, which allows the pupils to properly access the text personally without having to fear whether or not their answer is correct. These open-ended questions also enable pupils to engage with the material more thoroughly and individually (cf. Okyar 2021, 333; Dörnyei 2001, 76). Personal engagement with the figures also increases pupils' engagement with the text overall, which in turn has a positive effect on the pupils' intrinsic motivation and thus accessibility to the text (Dörnyei 2013, 299; Grimm et al. 2015, 177). From a methodological perspective, the basic framework of the TBLT approach also overlaps with language skill specific methods. The individual phases pre-, while-, and post-activity of the individual language skills reading, and dialogic speaking can be embedded in the overarching phases of the TBLT task-cycle (cf. Grimm et al. 2015, 70). Thus, the different methods complement each other excellently and the language skills reading, and dialogic speaking can be optimally promoted with the right tasks.

With regard to the empathy skills, the lesson plan manages to draw the pupils' attention to the emotions and thoughts of the characters. This is done through a variety of tasks, that explicitly encourage pupils to analyse the characters as well as try to take on their perspective. These methods align with the theory of Jamieson, who suggests that for pupils to be able to develop empathy they must repeatedly be encouraged to actively engage with the characters (2015, 236 – 238). The holistic language learning in this classroom

project is also highly encouraged by theory. For example, Ghosn argues that literature is a great teaching tool to teach pupils language, as well as foster transversal skills, such as empathy (2002, 176). As shown in chapter “5 Practical transfer into a classroom project” the potential for holistic language learning is not just limited to theoretical ideas but can be transferred into practice with the right tasks.

However, the lesson plan also has its limitations. For example, the curriculum competence *Languages in focus* is hardly promoted. This competence, however, can be included in an extension of the classroom project. Also, the pupils do not receive any feedback on the accuracy of their verbal and written contributions. This could lead to the fossilisation of errors, as pupils pronounce words wrongly or use wrong grammar structures (Grimm et al. 2015, 131). Adding accuracy- and language-focused exercises would counteract this issue. Lastly, the classroom project was only developed theoretically and was not tested practically. As promising the classroom project appears to be in fostering the targeted competences, it has yet to be tested on how well the worksheets work in practice.

With regard to the material, the use of graded readers in the classroom is both encouraged and discouraged depending on the instructional goal after this master thesis. Graded readers, especially at a simple level, do not lend themselves to learning "authentic" language. As seen in MR's linguistic analysis, it could be observed that the novel was practically told only in simple sentences, which seems very artificial. This criticism was already mentioned by experts, such as Hill and must be confirmed after the linguistic analysis (cf. Hill 1997, 57). If teachers aim to teach languages mainly through graded readers, they must be part of an extensive reading project (cf. Nation and Ming-Tzu 1999, 375). In the case of an instructed teaching approach, as it was the case for this classroom project, pupils encounter artificial language forms for a very long time, which could prevent them from learning "authentic" language. This problem is confirmed by Yano et al. (1994, 191 ff.). Language learning with graded readers in instructed teaching approaches should therefore be treated with caution and must be supported with very good tasks. However, if the focus is on meaning-based and comprehension-based learning objectives, graded readers are an excellent resource (cf. Nation and Deweerdt 2001, 56 – 57). Because of the linguistically simplified material, pupils can interact with material that would be too difficult in the original and engage with interesting topics that would be inaccessible otherwise. Also, the graded readers draw the readers' attention to key passages and elements of the story (Macmillan

2014, 2). This, in relation to the simpler language, facilitates reading comprehension which accommodates a meaning-focused input approach. Therefore, if the learning objective revolves around meaning, the artificial and unauthentic language can be accepted. However, teachers must also be aware that the pupils will engage with a modified version of the material and teachers thus need to check in advance, whether the meaning-based learning objectives, which were originally intended, are still feasible with the graded readers.

In conclusion, I see great potential in holistic language learning with graded readers, but little potential for learning a language exclusively through engaging with graded readers. Although I have learnt English almost exclusively through reading books, this approach is not appropriate in the EFL classroom, since important factors such as accuracy and the engagement with "authentic" language clearly fall short, especially when the focus is solely on meaning as it was in this classroom project. However, after this master thesis I believe that literature should be used as a supplementary learning resource in the EFL classroom, as it is very motivating, highly engaging, and offers learning opportunities which are otherwise difficult to access, e.g., learning empathy.

7 Bibliography

- Amin, Ruhul. 2019. "Developing Reading Skills through Effective Reading Approaches." *International Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities* 4 (1): 35 – 40.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2557919>
- Alyousef, Hesham Suleiman. 2006. "Teaching Reading Comprehension to EFL/EFL Learners." *Journal of Language and Learning* 5 (1): 63 – 73.
ISSN 1475 – 8989
- Berger, Martin and Manfred Pfiffner. 2018. *Umgang mit Heterogenität an Berufsfachschulen. Didaktische Hausapotheke Band 12*, published by Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich. Bern: hep Verlag.
- Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich. 2016. *Grundlagen*. Zürich: Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich.
- Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich. 2017. *Lehrplan Volksschule. Sprachen*. Zürich: Bildungsdirektion des Kanton Zürich.
- Bloom, Benjamin Samuel. 1973. *Taxonomie von Lernzielen im kognitiven Bereich*. Weinheim: Beltz.
- Blum, Shoshana and Edward A. Leventson. 1978. "Universals of Lexical Simplification." *Language Learning* 28 (2): 399-415.
[doi:10.1111/J.1467-1770.1978.TB00143.X](https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1467-1770.1978.TB00143.X)
- Brandt, Hanne. 2020. "Sprachliche Heterogenität im Fachunterricht. Erfahrungen und Überzeugungen von Gesellschaftslehrkräften in der Sekundarstufe I." In *Handbuch Mehrsprachigkeit und Bildung*, published by Ingrid Gogolin, Antje Hansen, Saraha McMonagle, Dominique Rauch, 293 – 299. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien.
- Brown, H. Douglas. 2001. *Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy*. 2nd ed. Harlow: Longman.
- Bygate, Martin. 2009. "Teaching and Researching Speaking." In *The Handbook of Language Teaching*, edited by Michael H. Long and Catherine Doughty, 412–440. New Jersey: Blackwell publishing.
- Byrde, Penelope. 1992. *Nineteenth Century Fashion*. London: Batsford.
- Claridge, Gillian. 2012. "Graded readers: How the publishers make the grade." *Reading in*

a Foreign Language 24 (1): 106 – 119.

ISSN: ISSN 1539-0578

- Council of Europe Portal. n.d. "Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR)." Accessed August 8, 2022. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/common-european-framework-reference-languages>
- Deci, Edward L. and Richard M. Ryan. 1985. *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior*. New York: Plenum.
- Dirks, Ines. 2004. *Graded Readers: Text Structure, Use and Perception*. Lizentiatsarbeit. Zürich: Universität Zürich.
- Döring, Nicola. 2013. "Wie Medienpersonen Emotionen und Selbstkonzept der Mediennutzer beeinflussen. Empathie, sozialer Vergleich, parasoziale Beziehung und Identifikation." In *Handbuch Medienwirkungsforschung*, published by Wolfgang Schweiger and Andreas Fahr, 295-310. Wiesbaden: Springer.
- Dörnyei, Zoltán. 2001. *Motivational Strategies in the Language Classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ellis, Rod. 2003. *Task-based Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ellis, Rod. 2012. *Language Teaching Research and Language Pedagogy*. New Jersey: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Ghosn, I. K. 2002. "Four good reasons to use literature in primary school ELT." *ELT Journal* 56 (2): 172-179.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/56.2.172>
- Grabe, William and Fredricka L. Stoller. 2011. *Teaching and Researching Reading*. 2nd ed. Edinburgh: Pearson Education Limited.
- Grimm, Nancy, Michael Meyer and Laurenz Volkmann. 2015. *Teaching English*. Tübingen: Narr Francke Attempto.
- Hermes, Liesel. 1994. "Romanerarbeitung im fremdsprachlichen Unterricht." *Fremdsprachenunterricht* 38 (47): 37 – 52.
ISSN: 0016-0989
- Hesse, Mechthild. 2009. *The English Teacher's Handbook of Youth Literature*. Stuttgart: Klett Lerntraining.
- Hill, David R. 1997. "Survey Review: Graded Readers." *ELT Journal* 51 (1): 57 – 81.

ISSN: 0951-0893

Hill, David R. 2008. "Survey Review: Graded Readers in English." *ELT Journal* 62 (2): 184 – 204.

doi:10.1093/elt/ccn006

Jamieson, Alanna. 2015. "Empathy in the English Classroom: Broadening Perspectives Through Literature." *LEARNing Landscapes* 8 (2): 229 – 244.
<https://doi.org/10.36510/learnland.v8i2.706>

Klippert, Heinz. 2010. *Heterogenität im Klassenzimmer. Wie Lehrkräfte effektiv und zeit-sparend damit umgehen können*. Weinheim und Basel: Beltz.

Kuty, Margitta. 2015. "Literatur für alle: Lesemotivation und Leseerziehung." In *Literatur-kompetenzen Englisch. Modellierung – Curriculum – Unterrichtsbeispiele*, published by Wolfgang Hallet, Carola Surkamp and Ulrich Krämer, 56 – 66. Hannover: Erhard Friedrich.

Laurence, Rebecca. "Why Frankenstein is the story that defines our fears." 2018. BBC, June 13, 2018, <https://www.bbc.com/culture/article/20180611-why-frankenstein-is-the-story-that-defined-our-fears> .

le Bourhis, Katell, 1989. *The Age of Napoleon: Costume from Revolution to Empire 1789-1815*, published by H.N. Abrams. New York: The Metropolitan Museum of Art.

Long, M. 1986. "A feeling for Language: The multiple Values of Teaching Literature." In *Literature and Language Teaching*, published by Christopher Brumfir and Ronald Carter, 42 – 59. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Lucas, Michael A. 1991. "Systematic Grammatical simplification." *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching (IRAL)* 29 (3): 241-248.

ISSN-0019-042X

Luder, Reto. 2009. *Heterogenität als Herausforderung. Inklusiver Unterricht als Antwort*. Zürich: Pädagogische Hochschule Zürich. Publicly available PowerPoint-Presentation.

Macmillan Readers. 2014. *Using Graded Readers in the Classroom*. London: Macmillan Education.

Naji, Jeneem Ganakumaran Subramaniam and Goodith White. 2019. *New approaches to literature for language learning*. London Borough of Camden: Palgrave Macmillan.

Nation, Paul and Karen Wang Ming-Tzu. 1999. "Graded readers and Vocabulary." *Reading*

- in a Foreign Language* 12 (2): 355 – 379.
- Nation, Paul and Jean Paul Deweerdt. 2001. "A Defence on Simplification." *Prospect* 16 (3): 55 – 67.
- Neugebauer, Claudia. 2008. *Didaktisierte Lesetexte – was ist das?*. Zürich: Institut für Interkulturelle Kommunikation.
- Neugebauer, Claudia and Claudio Nodari. 2012. *Förderung der Schulsprache in allen Fächern. Praxisvorschläge für Schulen in einem mehrsprachigen Umfeld*. Zürich: Schulverlag plus.
- Neumann, Birgit and Ansgar Nünning. 2008. *An Introduction to the Study of Narrative Fiction*. Stuttgart: Klett.
- Nunan, David. 2004. *Task-based Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Nünning, Ansgar and Carola Surkamp. 2006. *Englische Literatur Unterrichten. Grundlagen und Methoden*. Hannover: Erhard Friedrich Verlag.
- Okyar, Hatice. 2021. "Contribution of Literature to Language and Learning." *Cumhuriyet International Journal of Education* 10 (1): 330, 343.
<https://doi.org/10.30703/cije.719796>
- Paran, Amos. 1996. "Reading in EFL: Facts and Fictions." *ELT Journal* 50 (1): 25 – 34.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/50.1.25>
- Penguin Reader. N.d. *What is a Penguin Reader?*. London: Pearson.
- Richards, Jack. C. and Richard Schmidt. 2002. *Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics*. 3rd ed. London: Longman, Pearson Education.
- Rosebrock, Cornelia und Daniel Nix. 2017. *Grundlagen der Lesedidaktik*. Baltmansweiler: Schneider Verlag Hohengehren.
- Shelley, Mary. 1993. *Frankenstein or The Modern Prometheus. The 1818 Text*. Ed. Marilyn Butler. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Shelley, Mary. 2005. *Frankenstein*. Adapted by Margaret Turner. London: Macmillan Readers.
- Shelley, Mary. 2012. *Frankenstein*. Adapted by Pam Davies. Oxford: Richmond Readers.
- Shelley, Mary. 2021. *Frankenstein*. Adapted by A.H. Hill. New York: Starry Forest Books.
- Shumin, Kang. 2002. "Facts to Consider: Developing EFL Student's Speaking Abilities." In *Methodology in Language Teaching: An Anthology of Current Practice*, edited by

- Jack C. Richards and Willy A. Renandya, 204 – 211. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Slavin, Robert E. 1996. "Research on Cooperative Learning and Achievement: What we know, what we need to know." *Contemporary Educational Psychology* 21 (1): 43 – 69.
<https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1996.0004>
- Tortora, Phyllis G. and Keith Eubank. 2010. *Survey of Historic Costume*. New York: Fairchild Books.
- Trautmann, Matthias and Beate Wischer. 2011. *Heterogenität in der Schule. Eine kritische Einführung*. Wiesbaden: VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften | Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.
- Vogt, Karin. 2017. "Inklusion und Heterogenität im Englischunterricht der Sekundarstufe." In *Inklusion, Diversität und das Lehren und Lernen fremder Sprachen*, published by Eva Burwitz-Melzer, Frank G. Königs, Claudia Riemer, Lars Schmelter, 326 – 336. Tübingen: Narr Francke Attempto.
- Warner, Darrel. 2012. *Untitled*. Oxford: Richmond Readers.
- Woolfolk, Anita. 2014. *Pädagogische Psychologie*. Hallbergmoos: Pearson Deutschland.
- Yano, Asukata, Michael H. Long and Steven Ross. 1994. "The Effects of Simplified and Elaborated Texts on Foreign Language Reading Comprehension." *Language Learning* 44 (2): 189 – 219.
[doi:10.1111/J.1467-1770.1994.TB01100.X](https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1467-1770.1994.TB01100.X)

8 Appendix

8.1 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 OR

OR Passage 1:

N= noun

Det= determiner

Adj= adjective

V= verb

Adv= adverb

Prep= preposition

Pro= pronoun

C= conjunction

O= other

Parts of speech:

Pro. V. Prep. Det. Adj. N. Prep. N. C. Pro. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N.
It was on a dreary night of November, that I beheld the accomplishment of my toils.

Prep. Det. N. Pro. Adv. V. Prep. N. Pro. V. Det. N. Prep. N. Prep.
With an anxiety that almost amounted to agony, I collected the instruments of life around

Pro. C. Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep. N. Prep. Det. Adj. N. Pro. V. Prep. Det. N.
me, that I might infuse a spark of being into the lifeless thing that lay at my feet.

Pro. V. Adv. O. Prep. Det. N. Det. N. V. Adv. Prep. Det. N. C. Det.
It was already one in the morning; the rain pattered dismally against the panes, and my
N. V. Adv. V. Adv. C. Prep. Det. V. C. Det. Adj. N. Pro. V. Det.
candle was nearly burnt out, when, by the glimmer of the half-extinguished light, I saw the
Adj. Adj. N. Prep. Det. N. V. Pro. V. Adv. C. Det. Adj. N. V. Pro.
dull yellow eye of the creature open; it breathed hard, and a convulsive motion agitated its
N.
limbs.

Adv. V. Pro. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N. C. Adv. V. Det. N. Pro.
How can I describe my emotions at this catastrophe, or how delineate the wretch whom

Prep. Det. Adj. N. C. N. Pro. V. V. Prep. N.
with such infinite pains and care I had endeavoured to form?

Det. N. V. Prep. N. C. Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep. V.
His limbs were in proportion, and I had selected his features as beautiful.

Adj.

Beautiful!

Adj. N.

Great God!

Det. Adj. N. Adv. V. Det. N. Prep. N. C. N. Adv. Det. N. V. Prep Det.
His yellow skin scarcely covered the work of muscles and arteries beneath; his hair was of a
Adj. Adj. C. Adj. Det. N. Prep Det. Adj. N. C. Det. N. Adv.
lustrous black, and flowing; his teeth of a pearly whiteness; but these luxuriances only
V. Det. Adj. Adj. N. Prep Det. Adj. N. Pa. V. Adv. Prep Det. Det. N.
formed a more horrid contrast with his watery eyes, that seemed almost of the same colour
C. Det. Adj. Adj. N. Prep Pa. Pa. V. V. Det. Adj. N. C. Adj.
as the dull white sockets in which they were set, his shrivelled complexion, and straight
Adj. N.
black lips.

Det. Adj. N. Prep N. V. Adv. Adv. Adj. C. Det. N. Prep Adj. N.
The different accidents of life are not so changeable as the feelings of human nature.

Pro. V. V. Adv. Prep Adv. O. N. Prep Det. Adj. N. Prep U. N. Prep Det.
I had worked hard for nearly two years, for the sole purpose of infusing life into an
Adj. N.
inanimate body.

Prep. Pa. Pa. V. V. Pro. Prep N. C. N.
For this I had deprived myself of rest and health.

Pro. V. V. Pa. Prep Det. N. C. Adv. V. N. C. Adv. C. Pa. V. V.
I had desired it with an ardour that far exceeded moderation; but now that I had finished,
Det. N. Prep Det. N. V. C. Adj. N. C. N. V. Det. N.
the beauty of the dream vanished, and breathless horror and disgust filled my heart.

Adj. O. V. Det. N. Prep Det. N. Pa. V. V. Pa. V. Adv. Prep Det. U. C.
Unable to endure the aspect of the being I had created, I rushed out of the room, and
V. Det. Adj. N. V. Det. N. Adj. O. V. Det. N. O. V.
continued a long time traversing my bed-chamber, unable to compose my mind to sleep.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

It was on a dreary night of November, that I beheld the accomplishment of my toils.

With an anxiety that almost amounted to agony, I collected the instruments of life around me, that I might infuse a spark of being into the lifeless thing that lay at my feet.

It was already one in the morning; the rain pattered dismally against the panes, and my candle was nearly burnt out, when, by the glimmer of the half-extinguished light, I saw the dull yellow eye of the creature open; it breathed hard, and a convulsive motion agitated its limbs.

How can I describe my emotions at this catastrophe, or how delineate the wretch whom with such infinite pains and care I had endeavoured to form?

His limbs were in proportion, and I had selected his features as beautiful.

Beautiful!

Great God!

His yellow skin scarcely covered the work of muscles and arteries beneath; his hair was of a lustrous black, and flowing; his teeth of a pearly whiteness; but these luxuriances only formed a more horrid contrast with his watery eyes, that seemed almost of the same colour as the dun white sockets in which they were set, his shrivelled complexion, and straight black lips.

The different accidents of life are not so changeable as the feelings of human nature.

I had worked hard for nearly two years, for the sole purpose of infusing life into an inanimate body.

For this I had deprived myself of rest and health.

I had desired it with an ardour that far exceeded moderation; but now that I had finished, the beauty of the dream vanished, and breathless horror and disgust filled my heart.

Unable to endure the aspect of the being I had created, I rushed out of the room, and continued a long time traversing my bed-chamber, unable to compose my mind to sleep.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
73 types / 193 tokens	33 types / 36 tokens	19 types / 20 tokens	13 types / 13 tokens	7 types / 7 tokens	7 types / 7 tokens	34 types / 35 tokens
a (7)	accidents (1)	beauty (1)	anxiety (1)	changeabl e (1)	catastrop he (1)	accomplishm ent (1)
an (3)	against (1)	burnt (1)	aspect (1)	desired (1)	complexi on (1)	agitated (1)
and (11)	almost (2)	breathe d (1)	beneat h (1)	endeavour ed to (1)	disgust (1)	agon (1)
are (1)	already (1)	candle (1)	compos e (1)	exceeded (1)	infinite (1)	amounted (1)
as (3)	around (1)	continu ed (1)	contras t (1)	moderatio n (1)	motion (1)	ardour (1)
at (2)	by (1)	created (1)	deprive d (1)	proportion (1)	scarcely (1)	arteries (1)
beautiful l (2)	care (1)	creature (1)	emotio ns (1)	sole (1)	spark (1)	beheld (1)
bed (1)	collected (1)	dull (1)	endure (1)			breathless (1)
being (2)	covered (1)	feelings (1)	feature s (1)			chamber (1)
black (2)	describe (1)	flowing (1)	muscle s (1)			convulsive (1)
body (1)	dream (1)	formed (1)	rushed (1)			delineate (1)
but (2)	far (1)	horror (1)	vanishe d (1)			dismally (1)
can (1)	filled (1)	human (1)	whom (1)			dreary (1)
colour (1)	form (1)	lips (1)				dun (1)
differen t (1)	god (1)	purpose (1)				extinguished (1)
eye (1)	health (1)	seemed (1)				glimmer (1)
eyes (1)	heart (1)	selected (1)				horrid (1)
feet (1)	instrume nts (1)	skin (1)				inanimate (1)
finished (1)	lay (1)	unable (2)				infuse (1)
for (3)	might (1)					infusing (1)
great (1)	mind (1)					lifeless (1)
had (7)	myself (1)					limbs (2)
hair (1)	nature (1)					lustrous (1)
half (1)	nearly (2)					luxuriances (1)
hard (2)	of (1)					panes (1)
his (7)	out (2)					pattered (1)
how (2)	pains (1)					pearly (1)
i (13)	rest (1)					shrivelled (1)
in (3)	set (1)					sockets (1)
into (2)						toils (1)
it (4)						traversing (1)
						watery (1)
						whiteness (1)

its (1)	so (1)					wretch (1)
life (3)	straight					
light (1)	(1)					
long (1)	such (1)					
me (1)	were (2)					
more (1)						
morning						
(1)						
my (7)						
night (1)						
not (1)						
novemb						
er (1)						
now (1)						
of (16)						
on (1)						
one (1)						
only (1)						
open (1)						
or (1)						
rain (1)						
room						
(1)						
same (1)						
saw (1)						
sleep (1)						
teeth (1)						
that (7)						
the (22)						
these						
(1)						
they (1)						
thing (1)						
this (2)						
time (1)						
to (4)						
two (1)						
was (4)						
when						
(1)						

which (1)						
white (1)						
with (4)						
work (1)						
worked (1)						
years (1)						
yellow (2)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 1993, 38 – 39)

8.2 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 RR

RR Passage 1:

Parts of speech:

Prop. Adv. So. V. Det. N. Prop. Det. Adj. N. N.
 At last, I finished my work on a dark November night.

Det. N. V. Adv. Adv. C. Prop. V. Det. N. Prop. N. Prop. Prop.
 My heart beat painfully hard as I collected the instruments of life around me.

Adv. Prop. V. Det. Adj. N. Prop. Det. N. O. V.
 Then I caused the lifeless thing at my feet to breath.

Prop. V. Adv. O. N. Prop. Det. N. C. Det. N. V. V. Prop. Det. N.
 It was already one o'clock in the morning and the rain was beating against the windows.

Det. N. N. V. V. Adj.
 My oil lamp had burned low.

Prop. Prop. Adj. N. Prop. V. Det. N. N. V.
 By its weak light, I saw the monster's eyes open.

Prop. V. Adv. C. Prop. N. V. Adv.
 It breathed hard and its body moved wildly.

Prop. V. V. Det. N. Prop. Prop. N.
 I cannot describe my feelings at that moment.

Det. N. Prop. V. Prop. N. V. Adj. N. C. N.
 The thing that came to life had enormous arms and legs.

Det. N. V. Adj. C. Adj. C. Det. N. V. Adv. Adj.
 His hair was long and black and his teeth were very white.

Prop. V. Det. Adj. Adj. N. C. Adj. Adj. N.
 He had a horrible grey-white face and thin, black lips.

Prop. V. V. Prop. N. Prop. O. N.
 I had worked without rest for two years.

Adv. C. Prop. V. V. Det. Adj. N. Adv. V.
 Now that I had finished, my beautiful dream suddenly disappeared.

N. V. Det. N.
 Fear filled my heart.

Prop. V. Adj. O. V. Prop. Det. N. C. Prop. V. Prop. Det. N.
 I was unable to look at the monster, and I ran from the room.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

At last, I finished my work on a dark November night.

My heart beat painfully hard as I collected the instruments of life around me.

Then I caused the lifeless thing at my feet to breath.

It was already one o'clock in the morning and the rain was beating against the windows.

My oil lamp had burned low.

By its weak light, I saw the monster's eyes open.

It breathed hard and its body moved wildly.

I cannot describe my feelings at that moment.

The thing that came to life had enormous arms and legs.

His hair was long and black and his teeth were very white.

He had a horrible grey-white face and thin, black lips.

I had worked without rest for two years.

Now that I had finished, my beautiful dream suddenly disappeared.

Fear filled my heart.

I was unable to look at the monster, and I ran from the room.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
62 types / 113 tokens	20 types / 21 tokens	14 types / 15 tokens	2 types / 2 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	2 types / 2 tokens
a (2)	against (1)	beat (1)	caused (1)			lifeless (1)
and (7)	already (1)	beating (1)	wildly (1)			painfully (1)
arms (1)	around (1)	breath (1)				
as (1)	by (1)	breathed (1)				
at (4)	collected (1)	burned (1)				
beautiful (1)	describe (1)	disappeared (1)				
black (2)	dream (1)	enormous (1)				
body (1)	filled (1)	fear (1)				
cannot (1)	heart (2)	feelings (1)				
o'clock (1)	horrible (1)	lips (1)				
come (1)	instruments (1)	monster (2)				
dark (1)	lamp (1)	suddenly (1)				
eyes (1)	low (1)	unable (1)				
face (1)	moment (1)	weak (1)				
feet (1)	moved (1)					
finished (2)	oil (1)					
for (1)	rest (1)					
from (1)	thin (1)					
grey (1)	were (1)					
had (5)	without (1)					
hair (1)						
hard (2)						
he (1)						
his (2)						

i (9)						
in (1)						
it (2)						
its (2)						
last (1)						
legs (1)						
life (2)						
light (1)						
long (1)						
look (1)						
me (1)						
morning (1)						
my (7)						
night (1)						
november (1)						
now (1)						
of (1)						
one (1)						
on(1)						
open (1)						
rain (1)						
ran (1)						
room (1)						
saw (1)						
teeth (1)						
that (3)						
the (9)						
then (1)						
thing (2)						
to (3)						
two (1)						
very (1)						
was (4)						
white (2)						
windows (1)						
work (1)						
worked (1)						
years (1)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 2012, 19 – 21)

8.3 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 MR

MR Passage 1:

Parts of speech:

Det. Adj. N. Adv. N. V. Det. N.
A few days later clouds covered the sun.

Det. N. V. Adj.
The sky became dark.

Pro. V. Det. N. V. V.
I knew a storm was coming.

Pro. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N. C. V.
I opened the windows of the laboratory and waited.

N. V. O. V. C. Pro. V. N.
Lightning began to flash and I heard thunder.

Det. N. Adv. C. Adv. Det. N. V. Adj.
A flash again and now the thunder was nearer.

Adv. Det. N. V. Adv. Prep. Pro.
Then the lightning was all around me.

Pro. V. Adj. C. Adj.
It flashed blue and silver.

N. V. C. Det. N. V. C. Adj. C. N.
Thunder crashed and the room was as light as day.

Adv. Pro. V.
Suddenly it happened.

Det. N. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N.
The lightning hit the wires on the roof.

Det. N. Prep. N. V. Adv. Det. N.
The sparks of light came down the wires.

Pro. V. Prep. Det. Adj. N.
I looked at the huge body.

Det. Adj. N. V. Det. N. Det. N. C. Det. N.
The silver light reached the hands, the feet and the head.

Det. N. V. V. Prep. Det. Adj. C. Adj. N.
The body was covered with a blue and silver light.

Prep. Det. N. Pro. V. Adj.
For a moment everything was quiet.

V. Pro. V.
Was it moving?

O. O.
No, yes!

Det. N. V. C. Adv. Det. N.
An arm moved and then a leg.

Adv. Pro. V. N. O. Det. N. V. V.
Then I heard breathing, yes, the man was breathing.

Pro. V. Adj.
He was alive!

Det. N. V. C. Pro. V. Adj.
The body moved and I went nearer.

Pro. V. Adv. Det. N. C. V.
I held out my arms and smiled.

Det. N. V. Adv. C. V. Det. N.
The man sat up and turned his head.

Det. N. V. Adj.
His eyes were open.

O. H.
Oh, God.

Pro. V. Pro. V.
What had I done?

Pro. V. V. Adj.
What had gone wrong?

Det. N. N. V. Adj. C. Adj.
The man's skin was wrinkled and yellow.

Det. N. V. Adj. C. Adj.
His eyes were yellow and dry.
Det. Adj. Adj. N. V. Prop. Det. Adj. N.
His thin, black lips opened in a terrible smile.
Prop. V. Adv. V. Det. N.
I had not made a man.
Prop. V. V. Det. N.
I had made a Monster!
Prop. V. Prop. Prop. Det. N. C. Adv. Det. N.
I ran out of my laboratory and down the stairs.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

A few days later clouds covered the sun.

The sky became dark.

I knew a storm was coming.

I opened the windows of the laboratory and waited.

Lightning began to flash and I heard thunder.

A flash again and now the thunder was nearer.

Then the lightning was all around me.

It flashed blue and silver.

Thunder crashed and the room was as light as day.

Suddenly it happened.

The lightning hit the wires on the roof.

The sparks of light came down the wires.

I looked at the huge body.

The silver light reached the hands, the feet and the head.

The body was covered with a blue and silver light.

For a moment everything was quiet.

Was it moving?

No, yes!

An arm moved and then a leg.

Then I heard breathing, yes, the man was breathing.

He was alive!

The body moved and I went nearer.

I held out my arms and smiled.

The man sat up and turned his head.

His eyes were open.

Oh, God.

What had I done?

What had gone wrong?

The man's skin was wrinkled and yellow.

His eyes were yellow and dry.

His thin, black lips opened in a terrible smile.

I had not made a man.

I had made a Monster!

I ran out of my laboratory and down the stairs.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
64 types / 156 tokens	28 types / 35 tokens	15 types / 23 tokens	3 types / 4 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	3 types / 3 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens
a (9)	around (1)	alive (1)	flash (2)		roof (1)	
again (1)	became (1)	breathing (2)	flashed (1)		sparks (1)	
all (1)	clouds (1)	crashed (1)	wires (2)		wrinkled (1)	
an (1)	covered (2)					
and (14)	done (1)	huge (1)				
arm (1)	down (1)	laboratory (2)				
arms (1)	dry (1)	lightning (3)				
as (2)	everything (1)	lips (1)				
at (1)	few (1)	monster (1)				
began (1)	god (1)	nearer (2)				
black (1)	happened (1)	ran (1)				
blue (2)	held (1)	reached (1)				
body (3)	hit (1)	skin (1)				
come (1)	moment (1)	smile (1)				
coming (1)	moved (2)	smiled (1)				
dark (1)	moving (1)	suddenly (1)				
day (1)	of (1)					
days (1)	out (3)					
down (1)	quiet (1)					
eyes (2)	silver (3)					
feet (1)						

for (1) gone (1) had (4) hands (1) he (1) head (3) heard (1) his (4) i (11) in (1) it (3) knew (1) later (1) leg (1) light (4) look (1) make (2) man (4) me (1) my (2) no (1) not (1) now (1) of (2) oh (1) on (1) open (1) opened (2) room (1) sat (1) sun (1) the (23) then (3) to (1) up (1) waited (1) was (10) went (1) what (2) windows (1) with (1) yellow (2)	sky (1) stairs (1) storm (1) terrible (1) thin (1) turned (1) were (2) wrong (1)	thunder (3)				
---	---	----------------	--	--	--	--

yes (2)						
---------	--	--	--	--	--	--

(Passage taken from Shelley 2005, 14 - 15)

8.4 Linguistic analysis Passage 1 SFB

SFB Passage 1:

Parts of speech:

O. O. P. V.
 Uh- oh... it worked!
 O. V. U. U.
 "Eek!" said Dr. Frankenstein.
 Det. N.
 "A monster!"
 O. V. Det. N.
 "Grr," said the monster.
 N. N. V. Adv.
 Dr. Frankenstein ran away.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

Uh- oh... it worked!

"Eek!" said Dr. Frankenstein.

"A monster!"

"Grr," said the monster.

Dr. Frankenstein ran away.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
6 types / 7 tokens	1 type / 2 tokens	1 type / 2 tokens	1 type / 1 token	0 types / 0 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	4 types / 5 tokens
a (1)	Dr (2)	monster (2)	ran away (1)			eek (1)
it (1)						frankenstein (2)
oh (1)						grr (1)
said (2)						uh (1)
the (1)						
worked (1)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 2021, 3 – 6)

8.5 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 OR

OR Passage 2:

Parts of speech:

Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep. Pro. Prep. Pro. Pro. V. V. Imp. Det. N. Prep. Pro.
"You must create a female for me, with whom I can live in the interchange of those
N. Adj. Prep. Det. N.
sympathies necessary for my being.

Pro. Pro. Adv. V. V. C. Pro. V. Pro. Prep. Pro. C. Det. N. Pro. Pro. U. Adv. V.
This you alone can do; and I demand it of you as a right which you must not refuse."

Det. Adj. N. Prep. Det. N. V. U. Adv. Prep. Pro. Det. N. Pro. V. V. Adv. C. Pro.
The latter part of his tale had kindled anew in me the anger that had died away while he
V. Det. Adj. N. Prep. Det. N. C. C. Pro. V. Pro. Pro. U. Adv. Adv.
narrated his peaceful life among the cottagers, and, as he said this, I could no longer
V. Det. N. Pro. V. Prep. Pro.
suppress the rage that burned within me.

Pro. U. V. Pro. Pro. V. C. Det. N. V. Adv. V. Det. N. Prep. Pro.
"I do refuse it," I replied; "and no torture shall ever extort a consent from me.

Pro. V. V. Pro. Det. Adv. Adj. Prep. Pro. C. Pro. V. Adv. V. Pro. V. Prep. Det.
You may render me the most miserable of men, but you shall never make me base in my
Det. N.
own eyes.

V. Pro. V. Det. Prep. Pro. Pro. Adj. N. U. Adv. Det. N.
Shall I create another like yourself, whose joint wickedness might desolate the world.

V.
Begone!

Pro. V. V. Pro. Pro. V. V. Pro. C. Pro. V. Adv. V.
I have answered you; you may torture me, but I will never consent."

Pro. U. Prep. Det. Adj. V. Det. N. C. Adv. Prep. V. Pro. V. Adj. O.
"You are in the wrong," replied the fiend; "and, instead of threatening, I am content to
V. Prep. Pro.
reason with you.

Pro. V. Adj. C. Pro. V. Adj. V. Pro. Adv. V. C. V. Prep. Det. N.
I am malicious because I am miserable; am I not shunned and hated by all mankind?

Pro. Det. N. V. V. Pro. Prep. N. C. V. V. Pro. C. J. Pro. Adv. Pro.
You, my creator, would tear me to pieces, and triumph; remember that, and tell me why I
V. V. N. Adv. Rec. Pro. V. Pro.
should pity man more than he pities me?

Pro. V. Adv. V. Pro. N. C. Pro. V. V. Pro. Prep. O. Prep. Det. N. C.
You would not call it murder, if you could precipitate me into one of those ice-rifts, and
V. Det. N. Det. N. Prep. Det. Det. N.
destroy my frame, the work of your own hands.

V. Pro. V. N. C. Pro. V. Pro.
Shall I respect man, when he contemns me?

V. Pro. V. Prep. Pro. Prep. Det. N. Prep. N. C. Adv. Rec. N. Pro. V. V.
Let him live with me in the interchange of kindness, and, instead of injury, I would bestow
Det. N. Prep. Pro. Prep. N. Prep. N. Prep. Det. N.
every benefit upon him with tears of gratitude at his acceptance.

C. Pro. V. V. Det. Adj. D. V. Adj. N. Prep. Det. N.
But that cannot be; the human senses are insurmountable barriers to our union.

Adv. Pro. V. Adv. V. Det. N. Prep. Adj. N.
Yet mine shall not be the submission of abject slavery.

Pro. V. V. Det. N. C. Pro. V. V. N. Pro. V. V. N. C. Adv. Prep. Pro.
I will revenge my injuries: if I cannot inspire love, I will cause fear; and chiefly towards you
Det. N. C. Det. N. V. Pro. V. Adj. N.
my arch-enemy, because my creator, do I swear inextinguishable hatred.

V. Det. N. Pro. V. V. Prep. Det. N. C. V. Prep. Pro. V. Det. N. Adv. Det. Pro.
Have a care: I will work at your destruction, nor finish until I desolate your heart, so that you
V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N.
curse the hour of your birth."

Det. Adj. N. V. Pro. C. Pro. V. Pro. Det. N. V. V. Prep. N. Adv.
A fiendish rage animated him as he said this; his face was wrinkled into contortions too
Adj. Prep. Adj. N. O. V. C. Adv. Pro. V. Pro. C. V.
horrible for human eyes to behold; but presently he calmed himself, and proceeded—

Pro. V. O. V.
"I intended to reason.

Det. N. V. Adj. Prep. Po. C. Pro. V. Adv. U. C. Pro. V. Det. U. Prep. Det. U.
This passion is detrimental to me; for you do not reflect that you are the cause of its excess.

C. Det. N. V. N. Prep. N. Prep. Po. Pro. U. U. Pro. Det. O. C.
If any being felt emotions of benevolence towards me, I should return them an hundred and
Det. O. N. C. Po. O. N. N. Pro. V. Y. N. Prep. Det. Adj. N.
an hundred fold; for that one creature's sake, I would make peace with the whole kind!

C. Pro. Adv. Adj. Prep. N. Prep. N. Pro. V. V. V.
But I now indulge in dreams of bliss that cannot be realized.

Po. Pro. V. Prep. Po. V. Adj. C. Adj. Po. U. Det. U. Prep. Det. N. C. Adv.
What I ask of you is reasonable and moderate; I demand a creature of another sex, but as
Adj. Adv. Pro. Det. N. V. Adj. C. Pro. V. Det. Po. Po. V. V. C. Po. V. U.
hideous as myself: the gratification is small, but it is all that I can receive, and it shall content
Pro.
me.

Po. U. Adj. Po. V. V. N. V. Adv. Prep. Det. Det. N. C. Prep. Det. N. Pro. V. U.
It is true, we shall be monsters, cut off from all the world; but on that account we shall be
Adv. U. Prep. O. Pro.
more attached to one another.

Det. N. V. Adv. V. Adj. C. Pro. V. V. Adj. C. Adj. Prep. Det. N. Po. Adv. V.
Our lives will not be happy, but they will be harmless, and free from the misery I now feel.

O. Det. N. V. Po. Adj. U. Po. V. N. Prep. Po. Prep. O. N.
Oh! my creator, make me happy; let me feel gratitude towards you for one benefit!

V. Po. V. C. Po. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. Adj. U. V. Adv. U. Pro. Det. U.
Let me see that I excite the sympathy of some existing thing; do not deny me my request!"

Po. V. V.
I was moved.

Pro. U. C. Pro. V. Prep. Det. Adj. N. Prep. Det. N. C. Pro. V. Det. Adv.
I shuddered when I thought of the possible consequences of my consent; but I felt that there
V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N.
was some justice in his argument.

Det. N. C. Det. N. Pro. Adv. V. U. Pro. O. V. Det. N. Prep. Adj. N.
His tale, and the feelings he now expressed, proved him to be a creature of fine sensations;
C. V. Pro. Adv. Prep. Det. N. V. Pro. Det. Det. N. Prep. N. Pro. Pro. V. Prep. Det. N. O.
and did I not, as his maker, owe him all the portion of happiness that it was in my power to
V.
bestow?

Pro. V. Det. N. Prep. N. C. V.
He saw my change of feeling, and continued—

C. Pro. V. Pro. Pro. C. Det. Det. Adj. N. V. Adv. V. Pro. Adv. Pro. U. V. Prep.
“If you consent, neither you nor any other human being shall ever see us again: I will go to
Det. Adj. N. Prep. N. N.
the vast wilds of South America.

Det. N. V. Adv. Pro. Prep. N. Pro. V. Adv. V. Det. N. C. Det. N. O. V. Det. N.
My food is not that of man; I do not destroy the lamb and the kid, to glut my appetite;
N. C. N. V. Pro. Adj. N.
acorns and berries afford me sufficient nourishment.

Det. N. V. V. Prep. Det. Adj. N. Adv. Pro. C. U. V. V. Prep. Det. Adj. N.
My companion will be of the same nature as myself, and will be content with the same fare.

Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep. Adj. N. Det. N. V. V. Prep. Pro. Adv. Prep. N. C. U. V. Det.
We shall make our bed of dried leaves; the sun will shine on us as on man, and will ripen our
N.
food.

Det. N. Pro. V. Prep. Pro. V. Adj. C. Adj. C. Pro. V. V. C. Pro. V. V. Pro.
The picture I present to you is peaceful and human, and you must feel that you could deny it
Adv. Prep. Det. N. Prep. N. C. N.
only in the wantonness of power and cruelty.

Adj. Adv. Pro. V. U. Prep. Pro. Pro. Adv. V. N. Prep. Det. N. V. Pro. V. Det.
Pitiless as you have been towards me, I now see compassion in your eyes: let me seize the
Adj. N. C. V. Pro. O. V. Pro. Pro. Adv. Adv. V.
favourable moment, and persuade you to promise what I so ardently desire.”

Pro. V. V. Pro. O. V. Prep. Det. N. Prep. N. O. V. Prep. Det. N. Adv.
"You propose," replied I, "to fly from the habitations of man, to dwell in those wilds where

Det. N. Prep. Det. N. V. V. Det. Adj. N.
the beasts of the field will be your only companions.

Adv. V. Pro. Pro. V. Prep. Det. N. C. N. Prep. N. V. Prep. Det. V.
How can you, who long for the love and sympathy of man, persevere in this exile?

Pro. V. V. C. Adv. V. Det. N. C. Pro. V. V. Prep. Det. N. Det.
You will return, and again seek their kindness, and you will meet with their detestation; your
N. N. V. V. V. C. Pro. V. Adv. V. Det. N. O. V. Pro. Prep. Det. N. Det.
evil passions will be renewed, and you will then have a companion to aid you in the task of
N.
destruction.

Pro. V. Adv. V. V. O. V. Det. N. C. Pro. V. V.
This may not be; cease to argue the point, for I cannot consent."

Adv. Adj. V. Det. N.
"How inconstant are your feelings!

C. Det. N. Adv. Pro. V. V. Prep. Det. N. C. Adv. V. Pro. Adv. V.
but a moment ago you were moved by my representations, and why do you again harden
Pro. Prep. Det. N.
yourself to my complaints?

Pro. V. Prep. Pro. Prep. Det. N. Pro. Pro. V. C. Prep. Pro. Pro. V. Pro. C. Prep. Det.
I swear to you, by the earth which I inhabit, and by you that made me, that, with the
N. Pro. V. Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep. N. C. V. C. Pro. V. N. Prep.
companion you bestow, I will quit the neighbourhood of man, and dwell, as it may chance, in
Det. Adv. Adj. Prep. N.
the most savage of places.

Det. Adj. N. V. V. V. Prep. Pro. V. U. Prep. N. Det. N. V. V. Adv. Adv.
My evil passions will have fled, for I shall meet with sympathy; my life will flow quietly away,
C. Prep. Det. Adj. N. Pro. V. Adv. V. Det. N.
and, in my dying moments, I shall not curse my maker."

Det. N. V. Det. Adj. N. Prep. Pro.
His words had a strange effect upon me.

Pro. V. Pro. C. Adv. U. Det. N. O. V. Pro. C. C. Pro. V. Prep.
I compassionated him, and sometimes felt a wish to console him; but when I looked upon
Pro. C. Pro. V. Det. Adj. N. Pro. V. C. V. Det. N. V. C. Det. N.
him, when I saw the filthy mass that moved and talked, my heart sickened, and my feelings
V. U. Prep Pro. Prep. N. C. U.
were altered to those of horror and hatred.

Pro. V. O. V. Det. N. Pro. V. C. C. Pro. V. Adv. V. Prep. Pro. Pro. V. Det.
I tried to stifle these sensations; I thought, that as I could not sympathize with him, I had no
N. O. V. Prep. Pro. Det. Adj. N. Prep. N. Pro. U. Adv. Prep. Det. N. O.
right to withhold from him the small portion of happiness which was yet in my power to
V.
bestow.

Pro. V. Pro. V. O. V. Adj. C. V. Pro. Adv. Adv. V. Det. N. Prep. N. Pro.
"You swear," I said, "to be harmless; but have you not already shewn a degree of malice that
V. Adv. V. Pro. V. Pro. V. Adv. Adv. Pro. V. Det. N. Pro. V. U. Det.
should reasonably make me distrust you? May not even this be a feint that will increase your
N. Prep. V. Det. Adj. N. Prep. Det. N.
triumph by affording a wider scope for your revenge?"

Adv. V. Pro.
"How is this?"

Pro. V. Pro. V. V. Det. N. C. Adv. Pro. Adv. U. O. V. Prep. Pro. Det. Adj.
I thought I had moved your compassion, and yet you still refuse to bestow on me the only
N. Pro. V. V. Det. N. C. V. Pro. Adj.
benefit that can soften my heart, and render me harmless.

C. Pro. V. Det. N. C. Det. N. N. C. N. V. V. Det. N. Det. N. Prep. Pro.
If I have no ties and no affections, hatred and vice must be my portion; the love of another
V. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N. C. Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N. Det.
will destroy the cause of my crimes, and I shall become a thing, of whose existence every
N. V. U. Adj.
one will be ignorant.

Det. N. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. V. N. Pro. Pro. V. C. Det. N. V. Adv.
My vices are the children of a forced solitude that I abhor; and my virtues will necessarily
V. Adv. Pro. V. Prep. V. Prep. Det. N.
arise when I live in communion with an equal.

N. V. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. Adj. N. C. V. V. Prep. Det. N. Prep. N.
I shall feel the affections of a sensitive being, and become linked to the chain of existence
C. N. Prep. Pro. Po. V. Adv. V.
and events, from which I am now excluded."

Pro. V. Det. N. O. V. Prep. Pro. Po. V. V. C. Det. Adj. N. Pro. Po. V.
I paused some time to reflect on all he had related, and the various arguments which he had
V.
employed.

Pro. V. Prep. Det. N. Prep. N. Pro. Po. V. V. Prep. Det. N. Prep. Det. N.
I thought of the promise of virtues which he had displayed on the opening of his existence,
C. Det. Adj. N. Prep. Det. Adj. N. Prep. Det. N. C. N. Pro. Det. N.
and the subsequent blight of all kindly feeling by the loathing and scorn which his protectors
V. V. Prep. Pro.
had manifested towards him.

Det. N. C. N. V. Adv. V. Prep. Det. N. Det. N. Pro. V. V. Prep. Det.
His power and threats were not omitted in my calculations: a creature who could exist in the
N. N. Prep. Det. N. C. V. Pro. Prep. N. Prep. Det. N. Prep. Adj.
ice caves of the glaciers, and hide himself from pursuit among the ridges of inaccessible
N. V. Det. N. V. N. Po. V. V. Adj. O. V. Prep.
precipices, was a being possessing faculties it would be vain to cope with.

Prep. Det. Adj. N. Prep. N. Pro. V. C. Det. N. Adj. Pro. Prep. Pro. C. Det. N.
After a long pause of reflection, I concluded, that the justice due both to him and my fellow-
N. V. Prep. Pro. C. Po. V. V. Prep. Det. N.
creatures demanded of me that I should comply with his request.

V. Prep. Pro. Adv. Pro. V.
Turning to him, therefore, I said.-

Pro. V. Prep. Det. N. Prep. Det. Adj. N. O. V. N. Prep. Adv. C. Det. Det.
"I consent to your demand, on your solemn oath to quit Europe for ever, and every other
N. Prep. Det. N. Prep. N. Adv. Adv. Adv. V. V. Prep. Det. N. Det. N. Pro
place in the neighbourhood of man, as soon as I shall deliver into your hands a female who
V. V. Prep. Det. N.
will accompany you in your exile."

Pro. V. Pro. V. Prep. Det. N. C. Prep. Det. Adj. N. Prep. N. C. C. Pro. V. Det. N.
"I swear," he cried, "by the sun, and by the blue sky of heaven, that if you grant my prayer,
C. Pro. V. Po. V. Adv. V. Pro. Adv.
while they exist you shall never behold me again.

V. Prop. Det. N. C. V. Det. N. Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prop.
Depart to your home, and commence your labours: I shall watch their progress with
Adj. N. C. V. Adv. C. C. C. Pro. V. Adv. Pro. V. V.
unutterable anxiety; and fear not but that when you are ready I shall appear."

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

"You must create a female for me, with whom I can live in the interchange of those sympathies necessary for my being.

This you alone can do; and I demand it of you as a right which you must not refuse."

The latter part of his tale had kindled anew in me the anger that had died away while he narrated his peaceful life among the cottagers, and, as he said this, I could no longer suppress the rage that burned within me.

"I do refuse it," I replied; "and no torture shall ever extort a consent from me.

You may render me the most miserable of men, but you shall never make me base in my own eyes.

Shall I create another like yourself, whose joint wickedness might desolate the world.

Begone!

I have answered you; you may torture me, but I will never consent."

"You are in the wrong," replied the fiend; "and, instead of threatening, I am content to reason with you.

I am malicious because I am miserable; am I not shunned and hated by all mankind?

You, my creator, would tear me to pieces, and triumph; remember that, and tell me why I should pity man more than he pities me?

You would not call it murder, if you could precipitate me into one of those ice-rifts, and destroy my frame, the work of your own hands.

Shall I respect man, when he contemns me?

Let him live with me in the interchange of kindness, and, instead of injury, I would bestow every benefit upon him with tears of gratitude at his acceptance.

But that cannot be; the human senses are insurmountable barriers to our union.

Yet mine shall not be the submission of abject slavery.

I will revenge my injuries: if I cannot inspire love, I will cause fear; and chiefly towards you my arch-enemy, because my creator, do I swear inextinguishable hatred.

Have a care: I will work at your destruction, nor finish until I desolate your heart, so that you curse the hour of your birth!”

A fiendish rage animated him as he said this; his face was wrinkled into contortions too horrible for human eyes to behold; but presently he calmed himself, and proceeded—

“I intended to reason.

This passion is detrimental to me; for you do not reflect that you are the cause of its excess.

If any being felt emotions of benevolence towards me, I should return them an hundred and an hundred fold; for that one creature’s sake, I would make peace with the whole kind!

But I now indulge in dreams of bliss that cannot be realized.

What I ask of you is reasonable and moderate; I demand a creature of another sex, but as hideous as myself: the gratification is small, but it is all that I can receive, and it shall content me.

It is true, we shall be monsters, cut off from all the world; but on that account we shall be more attached to one another.

Our lives will not be happy, but they will be harmless, and free from the misery I now feel.

Oh! my creator, make me happy; let me feel gratitude towards you for one benefit!

Let me see that I excite the sympathy of some existing thing; do not deny me my request!”

I was moved.

I shuddered when I thought of the possible consequences of my consent; but I felt that there was some justice in his argument.

His tale, and the feelings he now expressed, proved him to be a creature of fine sensations; and did I not, as his maker, owe him all the portion of happiness that it was in my power to bestow?

He saw my change of feeling, and continued—

"If you consent, neither you nor any other human being shall ever see us again: I will go to the vast wilds of South America.

My food is not that of man; I do not destroy the lamb and the kid, to glut my appetite; acorns and berries afford me sufficient nourishment.

My companion will be of the same nature as myself, and will be content with the same fare.

We shall make our bed of dried leaves; the sun will shine on us as on man, and will ripen our food.

The picture I present to you is peaceful and human, and you must feel that you could deny it only in the wantonness of power and cruelty.

Pitiless as you have been towards me, I now see compassion in your eyes: let me seize the favourable moment, and persuade you to promise what I so ardently desire."

"You propose," replied I, "to fly from the habitations of man, to dwell in those wilds where the beasts of the field will be your only companions. ("You propose to fly from the..." is one clause)

How can you, who long for the love and sympathy of man, persevere in this exile?

You will return, and again seek their kindness, and you will meet with their detestation; your evil passions will be renewed, and you will then have a companion to aid you in the task of destruction.

This may not be; cease to argue the point, for I cannot consent."

"How inconstant are your feelings!

but a moment ago you were moved by my representations, and why do you again harden yourself to my complaints?

I swear to you, by the earth which I inhabit, and by you that made me, that, with the companion you bestow, I will quit the neighbourhood of man, and dwell, as it may chance, in the most savage of places.

My evil passions will have fled, for I shall meet with sympathy; my life will flow quietly away, and, in my dying moments, I shall not curse my maker."

His words had a strange effect upon me.

I compassionated him, and sometimes felt a wish to console him; but when I looked upon him, when I saw the filthy mass that moved and talked, my heart sickened, and my feelings were altered to those of horror and hatred.

I tried to stifle these sensations; I thought, that as I could not sympathize with him, I had no right to withhold from him the small portion of happiness which was yet in my power to bestow.

"You swear," I said, "to be harmless; but have you not already shewn a degree of malice that should reasonably make me distrust you? May not even this be a feint that will increase your triumph by affording a wider scope for your revenge?" ("you swear to be harmless" is one main clause)

"How is this?"

I thought I had moved your compassion, and yet you still refuse to bestow on me the only benefit that can soften my heart, and render me harmless.

If I have no ties and no affections, hatred and vice must be my portion; the love of another will destroy the cause of my crimes, and I shall become a thing, of whose existence every one will be ignorant.

My vices are the children of a forced solitude that I abhor; and my virtues will necessarily arise when I live in communion with an equal.

I shall feel the affections of a sensitive being, and become linked to the chain of existence and events, from which I am now excluded."

I paused some time to reflect on all he had related, and the various arguments which he had employed.

I thought of the promise of virtues which he had displayed on the opening of his existence, and the subsequent blight of all kindly feeling by the loathing and scorn which his protectors had manifested towards him.

His power and threats were not omitted in my calculations: a creature who could exist in the ice caves of the glaciers, and hide himself from pursuit among the ridges of inaccessible precipices, was a being possessing faculties it would be vain to cope with. ("a creature was a being possessing..." is one clause)

After a long pause of reflection, I concluded, that the justice due both to him and my fellow-creatures demanded of me that I should comply with his request.

Turning to him, therefore, I said—

"I consent to your demand, on your solemn oath to quit Europe for ever, and every other place in the neighbourhood of man, as soon as I shall deliver into your hands a female who will accompany you in your exile."

"I swear," he cried, "by the sun, and by the blue sky of heaven, that if you grant my prayer, while they exist you shall never behold me again. ("I swear by the sun..." is one main clause)

Depart to your home, and commence your labours: I shall watch their progress with unutterable anxiety; and fear not but that when you are ready I shall appear.”

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
146 types / 929 tokens	62 types / 131 tokens	93 types / 133 tokens	72 types / 105 tokens	27 words / 37 tokens	18 types / 20 tokens	77 types / 91 tokens
a (21)	ago (1)	accompany (1)	affections (2)	acceptance (1)	arch (1)	abhor (1)
after (1)	alone (1)	account (1)	altered (1)	aid (1)	commence (1)	abject (1)
again (4)	already (1)	animated (1)	anger (1)	appetite (1)	detrimental (1)	acorns (1)
all (6)	among (2)	appear (1)	anxiety (1)	arise (1)	exile (2)	afford (1)
am (5)	another (4)	argue (1)	barriers (1)	comply (1)	ignorant (1)	affording (1)
an (3)	away (2)	argument (1)	berries (1)	conclude (1)	indulge (1)	america (1)
and (56)	become (2)	arguments (1)	calculations (1)	consent (6)	inhabit (1)	anew (1)
answered (1)	by (8)	attached (1)	calmed (1)	excess (1)	loathing (1)	ardently (1)
any (2)	call (1)	base (1)	cause (3)	excluded (1)	malicious (1)	beasts (1)
are (6)	care (1)	benefit (3)	cease (1)	faculties (1)	pursuit (1)	ardently (1)
as (13)	chain (1)	birth (1)	companion (3)	filthy (1)	representations (1)	behold (2)
ask (1)	could (5)	burned (1)	companions (1)	fled (1)	shuddered (1)	begone (1)
at (2)	cried (1)	caves (1)	consequences (1)	hatred (3)	suppress (1)	benevolence (1)
be (18)	degree (1)	chance (1)	content (3)	labours (1)	sympathize (1)	bestow (5)
because (2)	dreams (1)	complaints (1)	cope (1)	moderate (1)	vice (1)	blight (1)
bed (1)	dried (1)	continued (1)	cruelty (1)	omitted (1)	vices (1)	bliss (1)
been (1)	even (1)	create (2)	cut off (1)	possessing (1)	virtues (2)	chiefly (1)
being (5)	field (1)	creature (4)	deny (2)	presently (1)	wrinkled (1)	communion (1)
blue (1)	free (1)	creatures (1)	desire (1)	proceed (1)		compassion (2)
both (1)	hated (1)	crimes (1)	destruction (2)	render (2)		compassionated (1)
but (14)	heart (3)	deliver (1)	emotions (1)	scope (1)		console (1)
can (5)	ever (3)	demand (3)	evil (2)			
cannot (4)	field (1)	demand (1)	existence (3)			
change (1)	free (1)	depart (1)	expressed (1)			
children (1)	hated (1)	destroy (3)	favourable (1)			
did (1)	heart (3)	displayed (1)	fellow (1)			
died (1)		due (1)				
do (7)						
dying (1)						
every (3)						

eyes (3)	himself (2)	earth (1)	forced (1)	slavery (1)		contemns (1)
face (1)	horrible (1)	effect (1)	harmless (3)	solitude (1)		contortions (1)
feel (4)	hundred (2)	employed (1)	heaven (1)	subsequent (1)		cottagers (1)
feeling (2)	ice (2)	enemy (1)	injuries (1)	torture (2)		creator (3)
felt (3)	if (6)	equal (1)	injury (1)	triumph (2)		curse (2)
fine (1)	instead (2)	events (1)	inspire (1)	vain (1)		desolate (2)
finish (1)	let (1)	exist (2)	joint (1)			detestation (1)
fly (1)	might (1)	existing (1)	justice (2)			distrust (1)
food (2)	mine (1)	fare (1)	kindness (2)			dwell (2)
for (11)	moment (2)	fear (2)	latter (1)			europe (1)
from (7)	moments (1)	feelings (3)	let me (3)			excite (1)
go (1)	most (2)	female (2)	linked (1)			extort (1)
had (9)	must (4)	flow (1)	maker (2)			feint (1)
hands (2)	myself (2)	fold (1)	mankind (1)			fiend (1)
happy (2)	nature (1)	frame (1)	mass (1)			fiendish (1)
have (7)	own (2)	grant (1)	misery (1)			glaciers (1)
he (12)	pieces (1)	happiness (2)	necessarily (1)			glut (1)
him (12)	pity (1)	hide (1)	neither (1)			gratification (1)
his (12)	point (1)	horror (1)	nor (2)			gratitude (2)
home (1)	reason (2)	human (4)	passion (1)			habitations (1)
hour (1)	receive (1)	increase (1)	passions (2)			harden (1)
how (3)	return (2)	intended (1)	pities (1)			hideous (1)
i (73)	shall (18)	kid (1)	portion (3)			im (1)
in (21)	should (4)	kindly (1)	propose (1)			inaccessible (1)
into (3)	sky (1)	lamb (1)	rage (2)			
is (8)	so (2)	live (1)	reflect (2)			
it (10)		miserable (2)	reflection (1)			
its (1)		monsters (1)	related (1)			
kind (1)		murder (1)	renewed (1)			
leaves (1)		necessary (1)	revenged (1)			
life (2)		neighbourhood (2)	revenge (2)			
like (1)		of (2)	sake (1)			
live (2)		owe (1)	seek (1)			
lives (1)		pause (1)	seize (1)			
long (1)		paused (1)	sensations (2)			
longer (1)		peace (1)	sensitive (1)			
looked (1)		peaceful (2)				
		persuade (1)				
		power (4)				

love (3)	south (1)	prayer (1)	sufficient (1)			inconstant (1)
made (1)	still (1)	progress (1)	swear (4)			inextinguishable (1)
make (5)	strange (1)	promise (2)	sympathies (1)			insurmountable (1)
man (8)	ties (1)	proved (1)	sympathy (3)			interchange (2)
may (5)	tried (1)	quietly (1)	tale (2)			kindled (1)
me (27)	true (1)	quit (2)	task (1)			long (1)
meet (2)	various (1)	realized (1)	threatening (1)			malice (1)
men (1)	were (3)	reasonable (1)	threats (1)			manifested (1)
more (2)	while (2)	reasonably (1)	vast (1)			narrated (1)
my (32)	whole (1)	refuse (3)	whom (1)			nourishment (1)
never (3)	wider (1)	replied (3)	wish (1)			oath (1)
no (5)	yet (3)	request (2)				persevere (1)
not (17)	yourself (2)	respect (1)				pitiless (1)
now (5)		senses (1)				precipices (1)
of (51)		sex (1)				precipitate (1)
oh (1)		shine (1)				protectors (1)
on (7)		tear (1)				ridges (1)
one (5)		tears (1)				rifts (1)
only (3)		therefore (1)				ripen (1)
opening (1)		thought (2)				savage (1)
other (2)		towards (5)				scorn (1)
our (4)		turning (1)				shewn (1)
part (1)		union (1)				shunned (1)
picture (1)		upon (3)				
place (1)		whose (2)				
places (1)		within (1)				
possible (1)						
present (1)						
ready (1)						
remember (1)						
right (2)						
said (4)						
same (2)						
saw (2)						
see (3)						
small (2)						
some (3)						

sometim es (1)						sickened (1)
soon (1)						soften (1)
sun (2)						solemn (1)
talked (1)						stifle (1)
tell (1)						submission (1)
than (1)						unutterable (1)
that (27)						wantonness (1)
the (62)						wickedness (1)
their (3)						wilds (2)
them (1)						withhold (1)
then (1)						
there (1)						
these (1)						
they (2)						
thing (2)						
this (8)						
those (4)						
thought (2)						
time (1)						
to (34)						
too (1)						
until (1)						
us (2)						
was (6)						
watch (1)						
we (3)						
what (2)						
when (6)						
where (1)						
which (7)						
who (3)						
why (2)						
will (24)						
with (14)						
words (1)						
work (1)						
work (1)						

world (2)						
would (5)						
wrong (1)						
you (45)						
your (17)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 1993, 118 – 122)

8.6 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 RR

RR Passage 2:

Parts of speech:

Adv. Det. N. V. V. V. Pro. V. Prep Pro O. V.
After the monster had finished speaking, he waited for me to reply.

C. Pro. V. Adv. Adj. O. V. Adv.
But I was too shocked to answer immediately.

Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep Pro. Pro. V.
"You must make another female for me," he repeated.

Pro. V. Pro. C. Pro. V. V. O.
"I demand it and you cannot say "no"."

Pro. V. Adv. V. Pro. Pro. V. Prep. Adv.
"I will not do it," I said at last.

Pro. V. Adv. V. Pro. V.
"Nothing will ever make me agree.

V. Pro. V. Det. N. Prep. Pro.
Shall I make another thing like you?

Adv. Pro. V. V. Det. N.
Together, you might destroy the world."

Pro. V. Adv. Adv. C. Pro. V. Adv. Det. N. V.
"I am evil only because I am unhappy," the monster said.

Adv. V. Pro. V. N. Adv. C. Pro. V. Pro.
"Why must I love humans more than they love me?"

C. Pro. V. Adv. Prep Pro. Pro. V. V. Adv.
If they are kind to me, I will be friendly.

C. Pro. V. Adv. V.
But that won't happen.

C. C. N. V. V. Pro. Pro. V. V. Pro. N. O. V. Pro.
So, if people cannot love me, I will give them reasons to fear me!"

Det. Adj. Adj. N. V. Prep Det. N. Prep Det. N.
A horrible, angry light burned in his eyes for a moment.

C. Pro. V. Adj. Pro. V.
When he became calmer, he continued.

Pro. V. V. Adv. N.
"I am being reasonable, Frankenstein.

Adv. V. Pro. Adj.
Just make me happy.

V. Pro. V. Adv. Prep Pro. Prep O. Adv. N.
Let me feel thankful to you for one kind action."

Det. N. V. Det. N.
His words touched my heart.

Pro. V. V. Det. Adv. N.
He had made a good argument.

Pro. V. V. C. Pro. V. Det. Adv. N.
I could see that he was a sensitive creature.

Pro. V. V. Pro. Det. Adv. N. C. Pro. V. Pro. V.
"I must give him a little happiness if I can," I thought.

Pro. V. Det. N. V.
He saw my feelings change.

C. Pro. V. N. Det. N. V. Adv. V. Pro. Adv. Pro. V.
"If you agree, Frankenstein, no humans will ever see us again," he said.

Pro. V. V. Prep Det. Adv. N. Prep N. N.
"We will go to the wildest parts of South America.

Pro. V. V. Prep Det. N. Prep Det. N.
We will live on the fruits of the earth.

Pro. V. V. Prep Adv. N.
We will sleep on dry leaves.

Det. N. V. V. Pro. Adv.
The sun will keep us warm."

Pro. V. O. V. Adv. Pro. V.
"You promise to live peacefully," I said.

C. Pro. V. Adv. V. Adj. U.
"But you have already done bad things.

V. Det. N. U. V. Pro. Adv. C. Adv. N
Having a female will give you twice as much power."

Pro. V. Adj. N. Det. N. V.
"I am serious, Frankenstein," the monster replied.

C. Pro. U. Det. N. Prep Det. N. N. V. U. Det. N. Adv.
"If there is no love in my life, hate will fill my heart instead.

C. Det. N. Prep Det. N. U. V. Adv. Det. N. Prep Det. N.
But the love of another creature will take away the cause of my crimes."

Pro. V. O. V. Prep Det. N.
I paused to think about his arguments.

Pro. V. Adv. V. Adj. U. Prep Det. N. Prep Det. U.
He had certainly shown good qualities at the beginning of his life.

Det. Adj. N. V. V. V. Prep Det. Adj. N. Prep Det. N. N
His kind feelings had been destroyed by his unhappy experience with the De Lacey family.

Pro. V. Adv. V. C. Pro. V. Adj. N.
I must not forget that he had great power.

C. Pro. V. Adv. V. Pro. Pro. U. U. Det. N. Prep Det. Adj. N. Pro. U.
If I don't help him, he will be a danger to all human life," I thought.

Pro. V. O. V. Pro. Pro. V.
I had to do what he asked.

Pro. V. Prep Det. N. Pro. V.
"I agree to your demand," I said.

C. Pro. C. Det. N. V. V. N. Adv.
"But you and the female must leave Europe forever."

Prep. Pro. U. V. Pro. Prep Pro. Pro. U. Adv. U. Pro. Adv.
"After you have done this for me, you will never see me again.

Pro. U. Det. N. N. Pro. U.
This is my promise, Frankenstein," he said.

V. Pro. V. V. Pro. Prep Det. N.
"Remember, I shall watch you during your work.

C. Pro. V. Adj. Pro. U. V. Adv.
When you are ready, I shall appear again.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

After the monster had finished speaking, he waited for me to reply.

But I was too shocked to answer immediately.

"You must make another female for me," he repeated.

"demand it and you cannot say "no"."

"I will not do it," I said at last.

"Nothing will ever make me agree.

Shall I make another thing like you?

Together, you might destroy the world."

"I am evil only because I am unhappy," the monster said.

"Why must I love humans more than they love me?"

If they are kind to me, I will be friendly.
But that won't happen.
So, if people cannot love me, I will give them reasons to fear me!"
A horrible, angry light burned in his eyes for a moment.
When he became calmer, he continued.
"I am being reasonable, Frankenstein.
Just make me happy.
Let me feel thankful to you for one kind action."
His words touched my heart.
He had made a good argument.
I could see that he was a sensitive creature.
"I must give him a little happiness if I can," I thought.
He saw my feelings change.
"If you agree, Frankenstein, no humans will ever see us again," he said.
"We will go to the wildest parts of South America.
We will live on the fruits of the earth.
We will sleep on dry leaves.
The sun will keep us warm."
"You promise to live peacefully," I said.
"But you have already done bad things.
Having a female will give you twice as much power."
"I am serious, Frankenstein," the monster replied.
"If there is no love in my life, hate will fill my heart instead.
But the love of another creature will take away the cause of my crimes."
I paused to think about his arguments.
He had certainly shown good qualities at the beginning of his life.
His kind feelings had been destroyed by his unhappy experience with the De Lacey family.
I must not forget that he had great power.
"If I don't help him, he will be a danger to all human life," I thought.
I had to do what he asked.
"I agree to your demand," I said.
"But you and the female must leave Europe forever."

"After you have done this for me, you will never see me again.

This is my promise, Frankenstein," he said.

"Remember, I shall watch you during your work.

When you are ready, I shall appear again.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
104 types / 295 tokens	38 types / 56 tokens	33 types / 43 tokens	6 types / 6 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	1 type / 1 token	4 types / 7 tokens
a (7)	agree (3)	action (1)	cause (1)		thankful (1)	america (1)
about (1)	already (1)	appear (1)	evil (1)			europe (1)
after (2)	angry (1)	argument (1)	peacefully (1)			De Lacey (1)
again (3)	another (3)	arguments (1)	qualities (1)			Frankenstein (1)
all (1)	away (1)	arguments (1)	sensitive (1)			
am (4)	became (1)	burned (1)	shown (1)			
and (2)	by (1)	calmer (1)				
answer (1)	certainly (1)	continued (1)				
are (2)	could (1)	creature (2)				
as (1)	danger (1)	crimes (1)				
asked (1)	dry (1)	demand (2)				
at (2)	during (1)	destroy (1)				
bad (1)	ever (2)	destroyed (1)				
be (2)	fill (1)	earth (1)				
because (1)	forget (1)	experience (1)				
been (1)	friendly (1)	fear (1)				
beginning (1)	happen (1)	feelings (2)				
being (1)	hate (1)	female (3)				
but (5)	heart (2)	forever (1)				
can (1)	horrible (1)	happiness (1)				
cannot (2)	if (6)	human (1)				
change (1)	immediately (1)	humans (2)				
do (5)	instead (1)	let (1)				
eyes (1)	just (1)	monster (3)				
family (1)	keep (1)					
feel (1)	might (1)					
finished (1)	moment (1)					
for (5)	must (5)					
fruits (1)	nothing (1)					
	reasons (1)					
	repeated (1)					

<p>give (3) go (1) good (2) great (1) had (6) happy (1) have (2) having (1) he (13) help (1) him (2) his (6) i (26) in (2) is (2) it (2) kind (3) last (1) leave (1) leaves (1) life (3) light (1) like (1) little (1) live (2) love (5) make (4) made (1) me (11) more (1) much (1) my (6) never (1) no (3) not (3) of (5) on (2) one (1) only (1) parts (1) people (1) ready (1)</p>	<p>shall (3) so (1) south (1) twice (1) unhappy (2) wildest (1) won (1)</p>	<p>paused (1) power (2) promise (2) reasonable (1) replied (1) reply (1) serious (1) shocked (1) take (1) touched (1)</p>				
--	---	---	--	--	--	--

remember (1)						
said (6)						
saw (1)						
say (1)						
see (3)						
sleep (1)						
speaking (1)						
sun (1)						
than (1)						
that (3)						
the (13)						
them (1)						
there (1)						
they (2)						
thing (1)						
things (1)						
think (1)						
this (2)						
thought (2)						
to (11)						
together (1)						
too (1)						
us (2)						
waited (1)						
warm (1)						
was (2)						
watch (1)						
we (3)						
what (1)						
when (2)						
why (1)						
will (14)						
with (1)						
words (1)						
work (1)						
world (1)						
you (14)						
your (2)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 2012, 55 – 56)

8.7 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 MR

MR Passage 2:

Parts of speech:

Pro. V. Pro. U.
"What can I say?"

Pro. V.
I repeated.

Det. N. V. V. U. C. N. Prep Det. N.
"My wickedness has brought terror and unhappiness to the world."

Pro. V. Pro.
I made you.

Adv. Pro. V. V. Det. N. O. U. Pro.
Now I must find the strength to kill you."

Det. N. V.
The monster smiled.

Pro. V. Det. Adj. N.
It was a terrible smile.

Pro. V. Adv. U. Det. U. O. U. Pro. Pro. V.
"You don't have the strength to kill me," he said.

C. Pro. V. Adv. V. O. U. Pro.
"And I do not want to kill you.

O.
No.

Pro. V. V.
You must live.

Pro. V. V. Pro. Prep Pro.
You must do something for me."

Prep Pro.
"For you?"

Adv.
Never!"

Pro. V.
I cried.

Pro. V. Det. N. V.
"You must," the Monster said.

V. Prep Pro.
"Listen to me.

Det. N. C. N. V. Adv. V. Det. N.
No man or woman will ever be my friend.

Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep Pro.
You must create a friend for me.

Pro. V. V. Det. N. Pro. V. U. Pro.
You must create a woman who can love me.

Pro. V. V. Adj. C. Adj. Prep Pro.
She must be ugly and terrible, like me."

Pro. U. Adv. V. Det. N. Pro. V.
"I will never make another Monster," I said.

Pro. V. V. Det. N. Prep Det. N.
"You have brought enough unhappiness to the world."

Pro. V. V. N. C. Pro. V. Adj. Det. N. U.
"I have brought unhappiness because I am unhappy," the Monster replied.

Adv. Adv. Pro. V. V. Pro.
"Now only you can help me.

Adv. Pro. V. V. Det. N. Adj.
Only you can make my life happy."

Pro. V. Prep Det. U.
I thought for a moment.

C. Pro. V. Pro. Adv. Pro. V. V. Adv. Adv. Pro. V.
"If I do it, then you must go far away," I said.

Pro. C. Det. N. V. V. Adv. Prep. N. C. N.
"You and your woman must live far from towns and people.

Pro. V. V. Prep. Det. Adj. N. C. Adv. V. Adj. Det. N.
You must live in a lonely place where there are no other people."

Det. N. V. Adj. Prep. Det. Adj. N.
The monster was silent for a few moments.

Adv. Pro. V.
Then he spoke.

Pro. V. Det. N. V.
"I agree," the Monster said.

V. Pro. Pro. Pro. V.
"Give me what I ask.

Adv. Pro. V. Adv. V. Pro. Adv.
Then you will never see me again.

V. Det. N. Prep. Adv.
Begin your work at once.

Pro. V. V. Adv. Det. N. V. Adj.
I shall return when the woman is ready.

Prep. Adv. O.
Until then, goodbye."

C. Prep. Det. N. Det. N. V. Pro. Adj. Prep. Det. N.
And without another word, the Monster left me alone on the mountain.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

"What can I say?"

I repeated.

"My wickedness has brought terror and unhappiness to the world."

I made you.

Now I must find the strength to kill you."

The monster smiled.

It was a terrible smile.

"You don't have the strength to kill me," he said.

"And I do not want to kill you.

No.

You must live.

You must do something for me."

"For you?"

Never!"

I cried.

“You must,” the Monster said.

“Listen to me.

No man or woman will ever be my friend.

You must create a friend for me.

You must create a woman who can love me.

She must be ugly and terrible, like me.”

“I will never make another Monster,” I said.

“You have brought enough unhappiness to the world.”

“I have brought unhappiness because I am unhappy,” the Monster replied.

“Now only you can help me.

Only you can make my life happy.”

I thought for a moment.

“If I do it, then you must go far away,” I said.

“You and your woman must live far from towns and people.

You must live in a lonely place where there are no other people.”

The monster was silent for a few moments.

Then he spoke.

“I agree,” the Monster said.

“Give me what I ask.

Then you will never see me again.

Begin your work at once.

I shall return when the woman is ready.

Until then, goodbye.”

And without another word, the Monster left me alone on the mountain.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
76 types / 185 tokens	23 types / 39 tokens	8 types / 15 tokens	3 types / 6 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	1 type / 1 token
a (6) again (1) am (1) and (6) are (1)	agree (1) alone (1) another (2) away (1)	create (2) lonely (1) monster (7) replied (1)	strength (2) terror (1) unhappiness (3)			Wickedness (1)

ask (1)	brought (3)	silent (1)				
at (1)	cried (1)	smile (1)				
be (2)	enough (1)	smiled (1)				
because (1)	ever (1)	ugly (1)				
begin (1)	far (2)					
can (4)	few (1)					
do (3)	if (1)					
find (1)	kill (3)					
for (5)	moment (1)					
friend (2)	moments (1)					
from (1)	mountain (1)					
give (1)	must (10)					
go (1)	once (1)					
goodbye (1)	repeated (1)					
happy (1)	return (1)					
has (1)	shall (1)					
have (3)	terrible (2)					
he (2)	unhappy (1)					
help (1)	without (1)					
i (16)						
in (1)						
is (1)						
it (2)						
left (1)						
life (1)						
like (1)						
listen (1)						
live (3)						
love (1)						
made (1)						
make (2)						
man (1)						
me (10)						
my (3)						
never (3)						
no (3)						
not (1)						
now (2)						
on (1)						
only (2)						
or (1)						

other (1)						
people (2)						
place (1)						
ready (1)						
said (5)						
say (1)						
see (1)						
she (1)						
something (1)						
spoke (1)						
the (12)						
then (4)						
there (1)						
thought (1)						
to (6)						
towns (1)						
until (1)						
want (1)						
was (2)						
what (2)						
when (1)						
where (1)						
who (1)						
will (3)						
woman (4)						
word (1)						
world (2)						
work (1)						
you (17)						
your (2)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 2005, 32)

8.8 Linguistic analysis Passage 2 SFB

SFB Passage 2:

Parts of speech:

O. P. V.
"Grr?" he asked.

O. V. N. P.
"No!" said Dr. Frankenstein.

P. Adv. N.
"No more monsters!"

V. Adv.
Go away!"

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

"Grr?" he asked.

"No!" said Dr. Frankenstein.

"No more monsters!"

Go away!"

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
5 types / 6 tokens	1 type / 1 token	2 types / 2 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	2 types / 2 tokens
asked (1) he (1) more (1) no (2) said (1)	Dr. (1)	Go away (1) Monsters (1)				Grr (1) Frankenstein (1)

(Passage taken from Shelley 2021, 15 – 16)

8.9 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 OR

OR Passage 3:

Parts of speech:

C. Pro. U. Det. N. Prep. Pro. C. V. U. O. U. C. Det. Adj.
But I discovered no trace of him, and was beginning to conjecture that some fortunate
N. V. V. O. V. Det. N. Prep. Det. N. C. Adv. Pro. V. Det.
chance had intervened to prevent the execution of his menaces; when suddenly I heard a
Adj. C. Adj. N.
shrill and dreadful scream.

Pro. V. Prep. Det. N. Adv. Pro. N. V. V.
It came from the room into which Elizabeth had retired.

C. Pro. U. Prep. Det. Adj. N. V. Adv. Det. N. Det. N. V. Det. N. Prep. Det.
As I heard it, the whole truth rushed into my mind, my arms dropped, the motion of every
N. C. N. V. V. Pro. V. U. Det. N. U. Prep. Det. N. C. V. Prep.
muscle and fibre was suspended; I could feel the blood trickling in my veins, and tingling in
Det. N. Prep. Det. N.
the extremities of my limbs.

Det. N. U. C. Prep. Det. N. Det. N. V. U. C. Pro. U. Adv. Det. N.
This state lasted but for an instant; the scream was repeated, and I rushed into the room.

Adj. N.
Great God!

Adv. U. Pro. Adv. Adv. U.
why did I not then expire!

Adv. V. Pro. Adv. O. U. Det. N. Prep. Det. Adj. U. C. Det. Adj. N. Prep. D.
Why am I here to relate the destruction of the best hope, and the purest creature of earth.

Pro. V. Adv. Adj. C. Adj. V. Adv. Det. N. Pro. N. U. Adv. C.
She was there, lifeless and inanimate, thrown across the bed, her head hanging down, and
Det. Adj. C. Adj. N. Adv. U. Prep. Det. N.
her pale and distorted features half covered by her hair.

Det. Adv. Pro. U. Pro. V. Det. Adj. N. Det. Adj. N. C. Adj. N. V. Prep. Det.
Every where I turn I see the same figure—her bloodless arms and relaxed form flung by the
N. Prep. Det. Adj. N.
murderer on its bridal bier.

V. Pro. V. Pro. C. V.
Could I behold this, and live?

O. N. V. Adj. C. U. Adv. Adv. Pro. U. Adv. Adj.
Alas! life is obstinate, and clings closest where it is most hated.

Prep. PP. N. Adj. V. Pro. V. N. Co. V.
For a moment only did I lose recollection; I fainted.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

But I discovered no trace of him, and was beginning to conjecture that some fortunate chance had intervened to prevent the execution of his menaces; when suddenly I heard a shrill and dreadful scream.

It came from the room into which Elizabeth had retired.

As I heard it, the whole truth rushed into my mind, my arms dropped, the motion of every muscle and fibre was suspended; I could feel the blood trickling in my veins, and tingling in the extremities of my limbs.

This state lasted but for an instant; the scream was repeated, and I rushed into the room.

Great God!

why did I not then expire!

Why am I here to relate the destruction of the best hope, and the purest creature of earth.

She was there, lifeless and inanimate, thrown across the bed, her head hanging down, and her pale and distorted features half covered by her hair.

Every where I turn I see the same figure—her bloodless arms and relaxed form flung by the murderer on its bridal bier.

Could I behold this, and live?

Alas! life is obstinate, and clings closest where it is most hated.

For a moment only did I lose recollection; I fainted.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
57 types / 125 tokens	19 types / 22 tokens	16 types / 17 tokens	11 types / 12 tokens	3 types / 3 tokens	6 types / 6 tokens	18 types / 18 tokens
a (2) am (1) an (1) and (12) arms (2) as (1) bed (1) beginning (1) best (1) but (2) came from (1) closest (1) did (2) down (1) every (2) feel (1) for (2) great (1) had (2) hair (1) half (1) head (1) heard (2) her (4) here (1) him (1) his (1) i (12) in (2) into (1) is (2) it (3) its (1)	across (1) blood (1) by (2) could (2) covered (1) form (1) god (1) hated (1) hope (1) into (2) lose (1) mind (1) moment (1) most (1) pale (1) repeated (1) thrown (1) turn (1) whole (1)	chance (1) creature (1) discovered (1) dropped (1) earth (1) figure (1) hanging (1) lasted (1) murderer (1) prevent (1) purest (1) relaxed (1) retired (1) scream (2) suddenly (1) truth (1)	destruction (1) dreadful (1) fainted (1) features (1) fortunate (1) instant (1) muscle (1) state (1) suspended (1) rush (2) trace (1)	distorted (1) fibre (1) veins (1)	clings (1) expire (1) intervened (1) motion (1) recollection (1) relate (1)	alas (1) behold (1) bier (1) bloodless (1) bridal (1) conjecture (1) elizabeth (1) execution (1) extremities (1) flung (1) inanimate (1) lifeless (1) limbs (1) menaces (1) obstinate (1) shrill (1) tingling (1) trickling (1)

life (1)						
live (1)						
my (4)						
no (1)						
not (1)						
of (6)						
on (1)						
only (1)						
room (2)						
same (1)						
see (1)						
she (1)						
some (1)						
that (1)						
the (14)						
then (1)						
there (1)						
this (2)						
to (3)						
was (4)						
when (1)						
where (2)						
which (1)						
why (2)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 1993, 165)

8.10 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 RR

RR Passage 3:

Parts of speech:

~~Adv. Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~Adj.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~
Then I heard a terrible scream from our room.

~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Pr.~~
At that moment, I understood everything.

~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~
My arms dropped to my sides.

~~Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Adj.~~
I was frozen.

~~Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~V.~~
I could not move...

~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~C.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~
The scream was repeated and I ran to our room.

~~Adv.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Adj.~~ ~~Adv.~~
Why did I not fall dead then?

~~Adv.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~Adj.~~ ~~O.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~Adj.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~N.~~
Why am I still alive to talk about the death of the best woman on earth?

~~Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~Adj.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~Adj.~~ ~~N.~~
She was there, thrown across the bed, lifeless, with her hair half covering her white face.

~~Adv.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~Pr.~~ ~~C.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~V.~~
How could I look at her and still live?

~~Pr.~~ ~~V.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~ ~~C.~~ ~~Adv.~~ ~~Prop.~~ ~~Det.~~ ~~N.~~
I collapsed on the floor, but only for a minute.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

Then I heard a terrible scream from our room.

At that moment, I understood everything.

My arms dropped to my sides.

I was frozen.

I could not move...

The scream was repeated and I ran to our room.

Why did I not fall dead then?

Why am I still alive to talk about the death of the best woman on earth?

She was there, thrown across the bed, lifeless, with her hair half covering her white face.

How could I look at her and still live?

I collapsed on the floor, but only for a minute.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
44 types / 72 tokens	13 types / 15 tokens	6 types / 7 tokens	1 types / 1 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	1 type / 1 token
a (2)	across (1)	alive (1)	collapsed (1)			lifeless (1)
about (1)	could (2)	death (1)				
am (1)	covering (1)	dropped (1)				
and (2)	dead (1)	earth (1)				
arms (1)	everything (1)	frozen (1)				
at (2)	fall (1)	scream (2)				
bed (1)	moment (1)					
best (1)	move (1)					
but (1)	repeated (1)					
did (1)	sides (1)					
face (1)	still (2)					
floor (1)	terrible (1)					
for (1)	thrown (1)					
from (1)						
hair (1)						
half (1)						
heard (1)						
her (3)						
how (1)						
i (9)						
live (1)						
look (1)						
minute (1)						
my (2)						
not (2)						
of (1)						
on (2)						
only (1)						
our (2)						
ran (1)						
room (2)						
she (1)						
talk (1)						
that (1)						
the (5)						
then (2)						

there (1)						
to (3)						
understood (1)						
was (3)						
white (1)						
why (2)						
with (1)						
woman (1)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 2012, 75 – 76)

8.11 Linguistic analysis Passage 3 MR

MR Passage 3:

Parts of speech:

Adv. Pr. V. Det. Adj. N. C. Adv. Pro.
Suddenly I heard a terrible scream – and then another.

Pr. V. Pxp. Det. N.
It came from our room.

N. V. Adj. Prep. Det. N.
Elizabeth was alone in the room.

Adv. Pr. V.
Then I understood.

Det. N. V. V. G. V. N. Adv. Pro.
The Monster was going to kill Elizabeth, not me.

Pr. V. Det. N.
This was his revenge.

Pr. V. Det. N.
I called some servants.

Adv. Pr. V. Prep. Det. N.
Together we rushed to the room.

Pr. V. Adv. Det. N.
We broke down the door.

Pr. V. Adv. Adv.
It was too late.

N. V. Adj. Prep. Det. N. N.
Elizabeth lay dead on our marriage bed.

Det. N. V. Det. N. Prep. N.
Her face had a look of terror.

Det. Adj. N. Prep. Det. Adj. N.
Her beautiful hair over her lifeless body.

Det. N. Prep. Det. N. N. V. Prep. Det. Adj. N.
The marks of the Monster's hands were on her white neck.

Det. N. Adj. Adj. N. V. V. Det. N.
The Monster's hard, wrinkled fingers had torn her body.

Det. Adj. N. V. Adj. Prep. N.
Her white dress was red with blood.

Sentence structure:

Main clauses

Subordinate clauses

Suddenly I heard a terrible scream – and then another.

It came from our room.

Elizabeth was alone in the room.

Then I understood.

The Monster was going to kill Elizabeth, not me.

This was his revenge.

I called some servants.

Together we rushed to the room.

We broke down the door.

It was too late.

Elizabeth lay dead on our marriage bed.

Her face had a look of terror.

Her beautiful hair over her lifeless body.

The marks of the Monster's hands were on her white neck.

The Monster's hard, wrinkled fingers had torn her body.

Her white dress was red with blood.

Difficulty of words:

A1	A2	B1	B2	C1	C2	Unlisted
42 types / 73 tokens	13 types / 13 tokens	6 types / 8 tokens	4 types / 4 tokens	0 types / 0 tokens	1 type / 1 token	2 types / 4 tokens
a (2) and (1) beautiful (1) bed (1) body (2) came from (1) door (1) down (1) dress (1) face (1) going (1) had (2) hair (1) hands (1) hard (1) heard (1) her (6) his (1) i (3) in (1) it (2) late (1) look (1)	alone (1) another (1) blood (1) called (1) dead (1) fingers (1) kill (1) lay (1) marks (1) neck (1) over (1) terrible (1) were (1)	broke (1) marriage (1) monster (3) scream (1) suddenly (1) torn (1)	revenge (1) rushed (1) servants (1) terror (1)		wrinkled (1)	Elizabeth (3) lifeless (1)

me (1)						
not (1)						
of (2)						
on (2)						
our (2)						
red (1)						
room (3)						
some (1)						
the (7)						
then (2)						
this (1)						
together (1)						
to (2)						
too (1)						
understood (1)						
was (5)						
we (2)						
white (2)						
with (1)						

(Passage taken from Shelley 2005, 46 – 48)

8.12 Scaffolding of reading

Planungsraster Leseverstehen

Niveau I	Niveau II	Niveau III	
Vorentlastung			vor dem Lesen
• Inhaltliche Vorentlastung			
			Informationen zum Thema sammeln <small>Lexikon konsultieren, Wissen zusammentragen</small>
			Über ein ausgewähltes Element sprechen <small>Titel, Schlüsselwort, -satz</small>
			Über die Textsorte sprechen <small>Vergleich mit bereits bekannten Texten</small>
			Die grafischen Elemente «lesen» <small>Bilder usw.</small>
• Lexikalische Vorentlastung			
			Schlüsselwörter besprechen oder nachschlagen
			Ausgewählte Wörter aus dem Lernwortschatz besprechen oder nachschlagen
			Wörter aus der Geschichte nach bestimmten Kriterien ordnen
Inhaltserfassung und -vertiefung			während dem Lesen
			Den ganzen Text ohne Wörterbuch lesen
			Eine Zusammenfassung des Textes lesen
• Gezieltes Verstehen <small>überfliegend lesen, selektiv nach Informationen suchen</small>			
			Bestimmte Informationen im Text finden <small>(Personen, Orte usw.)</small>
			Bestimmte Informationen in der Zusammenfassung finden <small>(Personen, Orte usw.)</small>
• Globales Verstehen <small>den roten Faden im Text erkennen</small>			
			Sätze aus der Zusammenfassung Stellen im Originaltext zuordnen
			Sätze aus der Zusammenfassung in der richtigen Reihenfolge ordnen
			Fragen zu den Sätzen aus der Zusammenfassung formulieren, sie jemandem zum Beantworten geben und die Antworten kontrollieren
			Bilder oder Stichwörter zum Text in der richtigen Reihenfolge ordnen
			Abschnitte des Originaltextes ordnen
			Aus einer Liste Untertitel auswählen und im Originaltext einsetzen
			Abschnitte des Originaltextes mit selber formulierten Untertiteln versehen
			Zu jedem Abschnitt ein bis zwei Sätze aufschreiben oder etwas zeichnen
			Zu jedem Abschnitt ein bis zwei Stichwörter notieren
			Ereignisse auf einem Zeitstrahl festhalten
			Inhalt in einer Gedankenkarte ordnen
			Globale Aussagen beurteilen <small>Tabelle zum Ankreuzen: Das ist richtig. / Das ist falsch. / Das kann man nicht wissen.</small>
			Richtige Sätze aus der Zusammenfassung von «faulen Eiern» trennen
			Mit Hilfe von vorgegebenen Stichwörtern nacherzählen
• Detailliertes Verstehen <small>alles genau analysieren</small>			
			Detaillierte Aussagen beurteilen <small>Tabelle zum Ankreuzen: Das ist richtig. / Das ist falsch. / Das kann man nicht wissen.</small>
			In einer Reihe von detaillierten Aussagen «faule Eier» erkennen
			Aussagen nach vorgegebenen Kriterien in einer Tabelle ordnen
			Selber eine Tabelle entwickeln und Aussagen ordnen
			Skizze zeichnen und beschriften
			Eine Situation inszenieren
			Fragen zu einem Detail beantworten <small>Mögliche Hilfe: Angeben, in welchem Abschnitt gesucht werden muss.</small>
			Mit Hilfe der eigenen Stichwörter oder Bilder nacherzählen
			Zusammenfassung schreiben
Inhaltserweiterung			nach dem Lesen
			Stellungnahme / eigene Meinung formulieren
			Vorgeschichte oder Fortsetzung zum Text erfinden
			Zum Inhalt eine Szene, ein Theaterstück, ein Interview usw. spielen

(Neugebauer 2008, 5)

8.13 Passage 1 RR

CHAPTER 5

CD1

7

The Monster

My great ambition drove me forward. I was the first to discover the secrets of life and death. I was going to bring a new light into the darkness of the world! I shut myself away in my lonely room at the top of the house. I became weak and thin as I worked. Sometimes I had to pause for a few hours. But I always returned to my horrible work with even more enthusiasm. Nothing could stop me. I even forgot my loved ones who were so far away. My father did not mention my silence in his letters. He only asked about my work.

Winter, spring and summer passed. But I did not enjoy the new flowers or the growing leaves as I used to do.

Every night, I felt hot and ill and I became very nervous. I stayed away from people as if I were a criminal. The least noise made me jump. I began to feel more like a slave* than a scientist doing the work he loved. Sometimes, I was alarmed by how unhealthy I looked. Only my love for my work drove me forward. I promised myself rest and exercise only when I had finished.

I know now that a healthy human being should always try to be calm and peaceful. If study upsets him then it means that his work does not suit him.

'But I'm slow to come to the interesting part of my story, Walton. I can see that you are impatient for me to go on...'

At last, I finished my work on a dark November night. My heart beat painfully hard as I collected the instruments of life around me. Then I caused the lifeless thing at my feet to breathe. It was already one o'clock in the morning and the rain was beating against the windows. My oil lamp had burned low. By its weak light, I saw the monster's eyes open. It breathed hard and its body moved wildly.

FRANKENSTEIN

I cannot describe my feelings at that moment. The thing that came to life had enormous arms and legs. His hair was long and black and his teeth were very white. He had a horrible grey-white face and thin, black lips*.

I had worked without rest for two years. Now that I had

I cannot describe my feelings at that moment.

CHAPTER 6

finished, my beautiful dream suddenly disappeared. Fear filled my heart. I was unable to look at the monster, and I ran from the room. For a long time, I walked around my bedroom before finally falling asleep.

I dreamt that I saw Elizabeth walking in the streets of Ingolstadt. I put my arms around her. But as I kissed her face, she became as white as death. Her face changed ... I seemed to hold the body of my dead mother in my arms.

I woke suddenly, terribly afraid. By the light of the moon through my window, I saw the monster by my bed. He was looking at me. His mouth opened and he made strange sounds. As I stood up, he put out his hand to stop me. But I managed to escape and run away. I spent the night walking around the garden. I was afraid the monster might appear again at any moment.

CHAPTER 6

The Best of Friends

CD1

8

At six o'clock the next morning, I started to walk around the streets. I was afraid to return to my rooms. I expected to meet the monster at every corner.

At last I reached the place where the public coaches from Switzerland arrived. A man was walking towards me. It was Henry Clerval!

'My dear Frankenstein,' he cried. 'I am so glad to see you. How lucky that you are here at this exact moment.'

I was so pleased to see him. He made me think of my father and Elizabeth. When I took his hand, I felt calm and peaceful for the first time in many months.

'You see, my father has let me come after all,' Clerval

8.14 Passage 1 MR

moving. Their skin would become wrinkled and yellow. I wanted to help them. I was working hard to find the secret of life.

I bought blood from living men. Was the secret of life in the blood? I looked at men's brains, soft and grey. Was the secret of life there?

Then, one night, there was a terrible storm. The sky was covered with black clouds. Thunder crashed and the rain fell. Lightning flashed in the sky. Suddenly the lightning gave me an idea. I knew what I had to do.

I began my work carefully. I took parts of dead men from hospitals and graveyards. I put the parts together to make a human body. I was making a man – a huge man – the biggest, strongest man who had ever lived. This man was going to come alive. I had found a way to create life. This man was going to live.

He was a good-looking man. His face was handsome and kind. His huge body was strong and well-made.

Day by day, I joined each part together. At last he was ready. He was ready to receive life. The body lay on a table in my laboratory. I had joined the hands, feet and head to metal wires. These wires went up to the roof of my house. Now I had to wait for a storm. When the power of the lightning flashed down through the wires, the man would live!

A few days later clouds covered the sun. The sky became dark. I knew a storm was coming. I opened the windows of the laboratory and waited.

Lightning began to flash and I heard thunder. A flash again and now the thunder was nearer. Then the lightning was all around me. It flashed blue and silver. Thunder crashed and the room was as light as day.

Suddenly it happened. The lightning hit the wires on the roof. The sparks of light came down the wires. I looked at the huge body. The silver light reached the hands, the feet and the head. The body was covered with a blue and silver light. For a moment everything was quiet. Was it moving? No, yes! An arm moved and then a leg. Then I heard breathing, yes, the man was breathing. He was alive!

The body moved and I went nearer. I held out my arms and smiled. The man sat up and turned his head. His eyes were open.

Oh, God. What had I done? What had gone wrong?

The man's skin was wrinkled and yellow. His eyes were yellow and dry. His thin, black lips opened in a terrible smile. I had not made a man. I had made a Monster!

I ran out of my laboratory and down the stairs. I heard the slow, heavy footsteps of the Monster as he followed me.

There was another flash of lightning. Thunder crashed over the house. I stopped and looked back. The Monster was standing at the top of the stairs. Behind him were red and yellow flames. Fire! My laboratory was on fire!

I gave a terrible cry as the Monster moved towards me. Then I fell down and everything went black.

The man sat up and turned his head. His eyes were open.

(Material from: SHELLEY, MARY, FRANKENSTEIN, published [2005] [Macmillan Readers] reproduced with permission of SNCSC.)

8.15 Passage 2 RR

PART IV **Frankenstein's Story continued**

CD2

2

June 1754 - August 1757

CHAPTER 18 **A Gentleman's Agreement**

After the monster had finished speaking, he waited for me to reply. But I was too shocked to answer immediately.

'You must make a female for me,' he repeated. 'I demand it and you cannot say "no".'

'I will not do it,' I said at last. 'Nothing will ever make me agree. Shall I make another thing like you? Together, you might destroy the world.'

'I am evil only because I am unhappy,' the monster said. 'Why must I love humans more than they love me? If they

FRANKENSTEIN

are kind to me, I will be friendly. But that won't happen. So, if people cannot love me, I will give them reasons to fear me!

A horrible, angry light burned in his eyes for a moment. When he became calmer, he continued. 'I am being reasonable, Frankenstein. Just make me happy. Let me feel thankful to you for one kind action.'

His words touched my heart. He had made a good argument. I could see that he was a sensitive creature. 'I must give him a little happiness if I can,' I thought.

He saw my feelings change. 'If you agree, Frankenstein, no humans will ever see us again,' he said. 'We will go to the wildest parts of South America. We will live on the fruits of the earth. We will sleep on dry leaves. The sun will keep us warm.'

'You promise to live peacefully,' I said. 'But you have already done bad things. Having a female will give you twice as much power.'

'I am serious, Frankenstein,' the monster replied. 'If there is no love in my life, hate will fill my heart instead. But the love of another creature will take away the cause of my crimes.'

I paused to think about his arguments. He had certainly shown good qualities at the beginning of his life. His kind feelings had been destroyed by his unhappy experience with the De Lacey family. I must not forget that he had great power. 'If I don't help him, he will be a danger to all human life,' I thought. I had to do what he asked.

'I agree to your demand,' I said. 'But you and the female must leave Europe forever.'

'After you have done this for me, you will never see me again. This is my promise, Frankenstein,' he said. 'Remember, I shall watch you during your work. When you are ready, I shall appear again.'

(Shelley 2012, 55 – 56)

8.16 Passage 2 MR

6

The Monster's Request

'What can I say?' I repeated. 'My wickedness has brought terror and unhappiness to the world. I made you. Now I must find the strength to kill you.'

The Monster smiled. It was a terrible smile.

'You do not have the strength to kill me,' he said. 'And I do not want to kill you. No. You must live. You must do something for me.'

'For you? Never!' I cried.

'You must,' the Monster said. 'Listen to me. No man or woman will ever be my friend. You must create a friend for me. You must create a woman who can love me. She must be ugly and terrible, like me.'

'I will never make another Monster,' I said. 'You have brought enough unhappiness to the world.'

'I have brought unhappiness because I am unhappy,' the Monster replied. 'Now only you can help me. Only you can make my life happy.'

I thought for a moment.

'If I do it, then you must go far away,' I said. 'You and your woman must live far from towns and people. You must live in a lonely place where there are no other people.'

The Monster was silent for a few moments. Then he spoke.

'I agree,' the Monster said. 'Give me what I ask. Then you will never see me again. Begin your work at once. I shall return when the woman is ready. Until then, goodbye.'

And without another word, the Monster left me alone on the mountain.

32

(Material from: SHELLEY, MARY, FRANKENSTEIN, published [2005] [Macmillan Readers] reproduced with permission of SNCSC.)

8.17 Passage 3 RR

CHAPTER 26

CD2

10

A Promise Kept

The sun was going down as we arrived at Evian. We walked beside the lake for a time, enjoying the last of the sunlight. Then we went back to the inn*.

I had been calm during the day. But darkness brought a thousand fears to worry me. My right hand, which was hidden under my coat, held a small gun. Every sound frightened me. I had decided to fight for my life and to go on fighting until I or my enemy was dead.

'What is worrying you so much, Victor?' Elizabeth asked. She had been watching my face.

'I can't tell you, my love,' I replied. 'Don't ask me. I promise you that after this night, all will be safe. But this night is dangerous - very dangerous.'

I expected the monster to attack at any minute. Then I suddenly realised that I must protect my wife. An attack on me would frighten her. 'Go to bed, Elizabeth,' I said gently. 'I will join you very soon.' But I knew I had to wait until my enemy appeared.

So she left me. For some time, I continued walking around the inn. I looked into every corner that might offer a hiding place. But I could find no sign of the monster. I began to feel safer. Perhaps something had stopped him from travelling to Lake Como.

Then I heard a terrible scream from our room.

At that moment, I understood everything. My arms dropped to my sides. I was frozen. I could not move ... The scream was repeated and I ran to our room.

Why did I not fall dead then? Why am I still alive to talk about the death of the best woman on earth? She was there, thrown across the bed, lifeless, with her hair half covering

FRANKENSTEIN

her white face. How could I look at her and still live? I collapsed on the floor, but only for a minute.

When I opened my eyes again, the people of the inn were all around me. Their faces showed great fear. Elizabeth's face was now covered. I wanted to believe she was only asleep. When I touched her cold hands, I knew that she was truly dead. The monster's mark was on her neck.

I asked them to leave me alone with her for a time. The light of the moon came in through the open window and I saw the hated figure of my creature outside. He smiled cruelly and pointed his finger at the body of my wife. I pulled out my gun and shot at him twice. But he escaped by jumping into the lake.

Later, groups of local people searched for him without success.

I had one clear thought left in my head. I must make sure that my other loved ones were safe. I paid two boatmen to take me across the lake and I started my journey back to Geneva. I cried as we travelled. I saw again the things Elizabeth and I had enjoyed the previous day. Nothing is more painful in human life than a great and unexpected change. The sun was still bright above me; the clouds still moved across the sky. But nothing could appear the same to me as it had been the day before.

I arrived in Geneva. My father and Ernest were still alive. But the old man collapsed when I told him the awful news. A few days later, my father died in my arms.

8.18 Passage 3 MR

Monster came to kill me, I would shoot him. Then I would tell Elizabeth my terrible secret. Her love would save me and protect me.

On our wedding-day, the sun was shining. All the world seemed happy. Elizabeth looked very beautiful.

After we were married, we left for our honeymoon. The journey started by boat. The sun was shining on the water of the lake and on the mountains. I heard the happy cries of our friends as they waved goodbye to us.

Those were the last happy hours that I ever spent. It was getting dark when the boat arrived at a small inn. The inn was beside the lake. The water and the mountains looked very beautiful.

We stayed in the inn that night. After dinner, we went to our room. I was sure that the Monster was near. But I was going to fight for my life and happiness. I had my gun with me.

Elizabeth saw that I was afraid.

'Why are you so afraid, Victor?' she asked. 'Why are you carrying a gun? Who can harm us in this beautiful place?'

'This is a night of great danger,' I replied, 'very great danger. But after this night, we will be happy together.'

I told Elizabeth to stay in the room. I told her to lock the door until I came back. Then I looked through the inn. I went into every room. But the Monster was not there. Perhaps nothing would happen.

Suddenly I heard a terrible scream – and then another. It came from our room. Elizabeth was alone in the room. Then I understood. The Monster was going to kill Elizabeth, not me. This was his revenge.

I called some servants. Together we rushed to the room. We broke down the door.

It was too late. Elizabeth lay dead on our marriage bed.

It was too late. Elizabeth lay dead on our marriage bed.

Her face had a look of terror. Her beautiful hair hung over her lifeless body. The marks of the Monster's hands were on her white neck. The Monster's hard, wrinkled fingers had torn her body. Her white dress was red with blood.

I ran to the window and looked out. In the moonlight, I saw the terrible shape of the Monster. I fired my gun, but the Monster was moving too quickly. In a moment, he had disappeared behind some trees.

People rushed into the room. I do not remember what I said or did. I was taken back to Geneva. I was mad with pain and sadness. When my father heard the news, he became ill. A few weeks later, he died.

For a long time, I lived alone. I saw no one. Perhaps I was mad. I do not know. One day, I went to the graveyard. All the people I loved were there. I looked at William's grave. I looked at Elizabeth's grave. And I looked at the grave of my father and mother.

(Material from: SHELLEY, MARY, FRANKENSTEIN, published [2005] [Macmillan Readers] reproduced with permission of SNCSC.)